

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY
DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

A Thesis
Presented to the Faculty of the
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Computer Science

by
Karen Kaye T. Alfonso
Jaenhel E. Mencidor
Ern Jan A. Painaga

2025

The Faculty of the College of Information Technology of the University of Negros
Occidental-Recoletos accepts the thesis entitled:

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

submitted by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso, Jaenhel E. Mencidor, and Ern Jan A. Painaga in partial
fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science.

MEHREEN E. DOLENDO, MSCS
Panel Member

REYMUND L. SABAY, MBE, D.B.M
Panel Member

ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Dean, College of Information Technology

Grade: Very Good

Date: May 29, 2025

L

┐

The thesis entitled:

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

submitted by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso, Jaenhel E. Mencidor, and Ern Jan A. Painaga have been examined and is recommended for Oral Defense.

ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Dean, College of Information Technology

Date of Graduation: July 2026

┌

└

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers would like to express their deepest appreciation and sincerest gratitude to the following individuals who have been instrumental in the completion of this study:

- To Mr. Elmer T. Haro, PhD, the Thesis Adviser, for his steadfast support at every stage of this journey. The researchers feel truly privileged to have served under his mentorship, as his dedicated supervision and unwavering assistance were vital to the success of the project.
- To Ms. Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS, who served as a member of the panel, for her technical expertise and meticulous corrections which significantly refined the technical aspects of this study.
- To Mr. Reymund L. Sabay, MBE, DBM, who also served as a panel member, for his practical recommendations and the wisdom he shared throughout the duration of the study.
- To the Interpellators, for the rigorous evaluation and the effort they invested in providing specific suggestions.
- To the Parents of the researchers, for the boundless love, care, and understanding they provided. Their financial assistance and constant encouragement served as a source of strength throughout the development of this project.

Above all, the researchers offer their praise to God Almighty, who provided the strength, wisdom, and perseverance necessary to bring this research to a successful conclusion.

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

Karen Kaye T. Alfonso
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
Bacolod City, Philippines
alfonsokarenkaye@gmail.com

Jaenhel E. Mencidor
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
Bacolod City, Philippines
jaeeenm@gmail.com

Ern Jan A. Painaga
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
Bacolod City, Philippines
painagaern@gmail.com

Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
Bacolod City, Philippines
haroelmer@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of additive manufacturing, particularly Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) 3D printing, has transformed prototyping and small-scale production. However, anomalies such as extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping continue to compromise print quality, leading to material waste and inefficiencies. These challenges highlight the need for automated, real-time defect detection systems aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 9 and 12. This study developed and evaluated a real-time anomaly detection and classification system using the YOLOv10-S model. A dataset of common 3D printing defects, compiled from public repositories, was preprocessed and used to train and validate the model under various image conditions, including RGB and grayscale. Paired T-test revealed significant differences between training and validation losses, indicating localization challenges. One-way MANOVA showed that anomaly type influenced detection performance, with spaghetti achieving the highest accuracy and extrusion problems the lowest. RGB images outperformed grayscale, highlighting the advantage of color features in detection. The final model demonstrated strong and consistent performance across validation and testing, confirming its effectiveness for real-time defect detection in FDM 3D printing.

COMPUTER SCIENCE CONCEPTS

• Neural Networks • Supervised Learning by Classification • Object Detection • Real-time Image Processing

KEYWORDS

3D Printing, Additive Manufacturing, Anomaly Detection, YOLOv10-S, Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), Object Detection, Computer Vision

ACM Reference format:

Karen Kaye T. Alfonso, Jaenhel E. Mencidor, Ern Jan A. Painaga, and Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. 2025. YOLOV10-S for 3D Printing Anomaly Detection and Classification

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, industries have shifted to digital prototyping with the use of computer-aided design (CAD), but many still rely on traditional subtractive manufacturing (SM), which is often inefficient. The advent of additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as three-dimensional (3D) printing, has changed this field by giving ways to the creation of physical objects from digital designs ^[1]. In contrast to conventional manufacturing methods, additive manufacturing (AM) operates on the principle of item creation by layer-by-layer stacks of materials ^[2].

Today, 3D Printing technology is widely used in various fields, particularly in the manufacturing industry, due to the availability of affordable fused-deposition modeling (FDM) 3D Printers, which makes it accessible to most individuals and small-scale businesses ^[3]. Consideration of the quality and accuracy of the end products becomes a fundamental factor. However, during production, problems such as defects occur, resulting in the rejection of the printed object. This leads to a loss of time and resources and contributes to plastic waste ^[1].

The sustainable development goals (SDG), established by the United Nations in 2015, integrated 17 specific goals to end poverty, as well as other deprivations, by an urgent call for action in all countries ^[4]. Among these goals is the need to address problems such as waste in production and unsustainable processes that consequently lead to the environment and resources to be jeopardized. This issue highlights the importance of SDG 9, which promotes resilient and sustainable industrial practices, and SDG 12, which focuses on the area that ensures sustainable consumption and production patterns. By addressing the plastic, time, and resource waste generated by 3D Printing technology, the manufacturing industry aligns with the objectives of the United Nations.

To achieve these goals effectively, this study implements a real-time anomaly detection during 3D Printing. This approach seeks to alleviate the problems and improve production efficiency with the use of minimized rework, reduced operational costs, and enhanced sustainability and protection of the environment with the decrease of the disposal of defective parts. The researchers use machine learning, specifically YOLOv10-S, to create a real-time

assessment of the object during the 3D Printing process. The study also follows a multi-class classification approach, to make it possible to detect and classify the specific types of defects present to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the remedial measures throughout the 3D Printing process.

1.1 Scope of the Study

This study mainly focuses on examining and identifying the different types of anomalies that occur during the real-time 3D Printing process using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, specifically You Only Look Once version 10 (YOLOv10) for anomaly detection and classification. YOLOv10 is one of the recently launched versions of the popular YOLO series that aims at providing fast and accurate object detection when compared to its predecessors as it has better architecture. Among all the different variants of the model, the researchers chose to focus on YOLOv10-S which provides an excellent balance between speed and accuracy.

The researchers train the models using publicly available datasets from Roboflow [5]. Images of defective prints are gathered from various sources to ensure that anomalies are equally represented in the context of the 3D Printing process. The images are also preprocessed to allow for a uniform input size to be fed into the YOLOv10-S model; the image size is therefore kept fixed at 640x640. However, it must be noted that the paper does not establish all possible defects in an FDM printer. Instead, it focuses on the detection of spaghetti, stringing, extrusion problems, and warping anomalies that occur most frequently in 3D Prints and are the only considered anomalies in the available dataset, thus limiting the scope of defect identification and classification to these specific types. Additionally, prints with intentionally induced porosity, spaces, or holes are not included in the training dataset, which leads to incorrect detection of such features as anomalies.

With the presence of various types of 3D Printers, the researchers also decided to focus exclusively on the FDM printer. Despite these limitations, the selected dataset and printer type are sufficient for evaluating the feasibility of applying YOLOv10-S to real-time anomaly detection in FDM-based 3D printing. This technique has been widely used in 3D Printing technology, especially in home-based operations, education, and small businesses, which propels researchers to seek to produce relevant and applicable data for this significant number of users. This approach provides the advantage of a controlled environment, which is fundamental in securing the consistency and reliability of the collected data. Including various 3D Printers complicates the analysis due to the wide range of technologies and behaviors observed across different machines. The results of this study are not necessarily generalizable to other forms of 3D Printing, such as stereolithography (SLA), which uses an ultraviolet (UV) laser to cure liquid resin, or selective laser sintering (SLS), which fuses powdered materials with a laser.

2 METHODOLOGY

To establish smooth-flowing training of the model, the researchers followed a systematic process to ensure reliable model performance. The researchers started with data preparations consisting of organizing the collected dataset, addressing data imbalance using a random under-sampling method, splitting the dataset and allocating a percentage for each phase, and augmenting the dataset to address the hypothesis. After thorough preprocessing to capture key features, the YOLOv10-S model was trained and evaluated using performance metrics such as precision, recall, and mAP50 to assess its accuracy and effectiveness with paired t-test and one-way MANOVA.

2.1 Research Design

The study implemented and utilized an experimental research design to check whether a defect is detected and what type of anomaly is detected in a 3D Printing process. Specifically, the YOLOv10-S was trained to detect defects during the 3D Printing process and classify them. The experimental research design was used in this study as it entails scientific experiments for the researchers to obtain reliable and precise results. The experimental approach comprehensively evaluates and analyzes the effectiveness and accurate performance of YOLOv10-S in anomaly detection classification.

2.2 Dataset

The datasets for training YOLOv10-S were sourced from the reliable dataset repository Roboflow [5]. The datasets were crucial in training the models to yield more accurate and precise detection and classification, which were effectively used in the deployment stage. The datasets used in training the ability to detect and classify anomalies are the following: extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. Table 1 shows the characteristics the collected dataset had to make the model training possible.

Dataset	Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset
File type	JPG & TXT
Image size for Anomaly Classification	640x640 pixels
Anomaly Classification	Extrusion Problem, Spaghetti, Stringing, and Warping
Original total number of images	6,895

Table 1: Dataset Characteristics

A total of 6,895 images were collected from Roboflow [5]. Specifically, 1,327 images of spaghetti were exported, 1,280 for stringing, 1,744 for under extrusion, 1,345 for over extrusion, and 1,199 for warping. Initially, the dataset contained 1,000 images sourced from Roboflow. However, upon further investigation, it was discovered that several images in the validation and test sets were repeated. To maintain dataset integrity, these duplicates

were removed, and additional images were sourced from platforms such as Kaggle [6] and Zenodo [7][8] to expand the dataset. Moreover, the datasets underwent cleaning, which involved deleting .txt files that contained more than five values together with their corresponding image to remove inconsistency. Blurry or extremely poor-quality images found across all data splits were also removed, as they do not represent usable data. After the researchers address the data imbalance and segmentation, the final allocation of images for each classification is shown in Table 2.

Classification	Original Number of Images	Final Number of Images
Spaghetti	1,327	1,000
Stringing	1,280	1,000
Over Extrusion	1,345	1,000
Under Extrusion	1,744	1,000
Warping	1,199	1,000
Total	6,895	5,000

Table 2: Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset Composition

2.3 Procedures

The dataset was separated into three phases: Training, Validation, and Testing. Each classification was allocated only 1,000 from the original number of images as the data imbalance was addressed. The researchers followed the 80:10:10 ratio for this data splitting. After the data splitting, the dataset then proceeded to the training of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying 3D Printing anomalies.

During the training phase of the model, 80% of the total dataset for each group was allocated to establish a strong foundation for the models. This phase helped the model to learn the patterns in each image, the relationship between pixels of the image, and the small features within the data. Then, 10% for the validation phase helped filter out the overfitting that happened iteratively during the training phase. Finally, the testing phase, the other 10% of the dataset, was an unbiased procedure for assessing new and completely unseen data.

The researcher applied random under-sampling for each category to address data imbalance. Since the images collected showed similar characteristics and lacked variation for each classification, the researcher combined the over extrusion and under extrusion into one group and reduced the number of images from the overrepresented categories. Upon analyzing the distribution of images, it was observed that combining the two extrusion-related defects, under extrusion and over extrusion, resulted in an imbalance within the dataset. To address this, the researchers applied data augmentation techniques to oversample the minority class and ensure a more balanced representation across all classifications. Specifically, rotation within a range of -10° to $+10^\circ$ and the addition of noise affecting up to 1.5% of the pixels were used to synthetically increase the number of samples in the

underrepresented category. As a result of this process, the final dataset was evenly distributed, allocating 2,400 images for the training set and 300 images each for the validation and test sets per anomaly classification. This strategy led to a substantial final dataset comprising 12,000 total images, ready for model training and evaluation. This final, balanced allocation was critical for preventing model bias and ensuring high generalizability across all defect types. Table 3 represents the final dataset allocation for each anomaly in each phase.

Dataset	Number of Images for Training	Number of Images for Validation	Number of Images for Testing
Extrusion Problem	2400	300	300
Spaghetti	2400	300	300
Stringing	2400	300	300
Warping	2400	300	300

Table 3: Dataset allocation for each phase after augmentation

2.4 Measurement and Statistical Treatment

This section focused on measuring and analyzing the performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying 3D printing anomalies. The evaluation centered on two major aspects: the training and validation loss values, which reflect the learning efficiency of the m, and the accuracy metrics—precision, recall, and mean Average Precision at 50% Intersection over Union (mAP50)—which indicate how well the model identifies and classifies anomalies. Precision, recall, and mAP50 scores were used to quantify the significant difference in the accuracy of detection and classification capabilities of YOLOv10-S. The two statistical tools, Paired T-test and One-Way MANOVA, were used to quantify significant differences in the dependent and independent variables of the study.

The assessment was carried out across different anomaly categories, including extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, as well as between RGB and grayscale image datasets to determine variations in detection accuracy and classification performance. To ensure the statistical validity of the results, a paired t-test was used to identify significant differences between the performance of YOLOv10-S on RGB and grayscale images, while a One-Way Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) examined the relationships between the dependent and independent variables across anomaly types.

2.5 Data Preparation

The initial dataset used in this study was primarily obtained from Roboflow [5]. To maintain dataset integrity, these duplicates were removed, and additional images were sourced from platforms such as Kaggle [6] and Zenodo [7][8] to expand the dataset. It originally consisted of 6,895 images across five classifications of 3D printing

anomalies: spaghetti, stringing, over-extrusion, under-extrusion, and warping. The images, in .jpg format with corresponding .txt file annotations, were standardized to 640×640 pixels to optimize model training.

During preprocessing, the dataset underwent cleaning to remove duplicate, blurry, and inconsistent annotations, as well as segmentation files containing more than five bounding box values. To address data imbalance, random under-sampling was applied to overrepresented categories, and all classes were equalized to 1,000 images each. Further augmentation, through rotation within $\pm 10^\circ$ and noise addition affecting up to 1.5% of pixels, was implemented to enhance the representativeness of underrepresented classes.

Following preprocessing and augmentation, the dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing subsets following an 80:10:10 ratio. This ensured that 80% of the images were used to train the YOLOv10-S model, 10% for validation during iterative learning, and 10% for final performance evaluation. These preparation steps ensured a balanced, high-quality dataset, enabling the model to effectively detect and classify 3D printing anomalies with improved generalization capability

3 RESULTS

The results obtained from this study were gathered after six separate training sessions of the YOLOv10-S model conducted under two image input modes, RGB and grayscale. Each mode underwent three trials to ensure consistency in performance evaluation. The findings presented in this section focus on the best-performing model from each modality to maintain clarity while providing insights into the ability of the model to detect and classify common FDM 3D printing anomalies, including extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping.

The performance of the model was assessed using standard object detection metrics: Precision, which quantifies the accuracy of the model in avoiding false positives; Recall, which measures its completeness in finding all true positives; and mean Average Precision at 50% IoU (mAP_{50}), which provides a holistic measure of both classification and localization accuracy. These metrics were chosen because they offer a comprehensive, industry-standard evaluation of the object detection capability of the YOLOv10-S architecture.

3.1 Evaluation of YOLOv10-S Training and Validation Losses

To determine the performance of YOLOv10-S, the training and validation losses were statistically compared using paired t-tests. This statistical approach provides quantitative evidence to support observations about the learning behavior of the model. For each image type, the evaluation is divided into three key loss metrics: box loss, class loss, and distribution focal loss (DFL loss). This analysis aims to identify which image type and training condition resulted in better loss minimization and

generalization, contributing to the selection of the best-performing model.

3.1.1. Box Loss. The box loss measures how well the model localizes objects by predicting bounding box coordinates that align with the ground truth. As shown in Table 4, all six training runs recorded large negative t -statistics ranging from -8.91 to -9.38 , with corresponding p -values all below 0.05. This consistent statistical difference between the training and validation performance suggests a fundamental limitation in the object localization capacity of the model regardless of the input image modality. Furthermore, the consistently negative t -statistics strongly support the observation that the performance of the model on unseen data was significantly worse than its performance on the training data. This means that while the model successfully minimized localization error during training, it exhibited slight overfitting when exposed to validation data.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-9.09	4.40×10^{-12}
RGB Train 2	-8.91	7.96×10^{-12}
RGB Train 3	-9.09	2.18×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 1	-9.22	1.37×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 2	-9.38	1.37×10^{-13}
Grayscale Train 3	-9.17	1.67×10^{-12}

Table 4: T-test for Box Loss

3.1.2. Class Loss. The class loss evaluates how effectively the model classifies detected objects into their correct anomaly categories. As shown in Table 5, only the first RGB training run exhibited a statistically significant difference between training and validation losses ($p = 0.03 < 0.05$). The second RGB run was borderline significant ($p = 0.05$), while the third RGB and all grayscale runs were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that the classification capability of the model was generally stable, with minimal overfitting across most configurations. The slight significance observed in the RGB runs may indicate that color information introduced additional variability during training, but not to a detrimental extent. Overall, the results demonstrate that YOLOv10-S maintained consistent classification accuracy between training and validation phases, showing its strength in distinguishing between different 3D printing anomalies.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	1.89	0.03
RGB Train 2	1.65	0.05
RGB Train 3	1.34	0.09
Grayscale Train 1	0.08	0.47
Grayscale Train 2	0.24	0.40
Grayscale Train 3	0.34	0.37

Table 5: T-test for Class Loss

3.1.3. DFL Loss. The distribution focal loss (DFL) focuses on how accurately the model learns the shape and boundaries of detected objects. As shown in Table 6, all six training runs recorded large negative t-statistics ranging from -15.47 to -17.17 , with p-values far below 0.05. These results indicate significant differences between training and validation losses for all configurations. This means that the model performed better in learning object boundaries during training but struggled to maintain the same accuracy when evaluated on validation data. This statistical divergence between the training and validation performance suggests a limitation in the object localization capacity of the model regardless of the input image modality.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-16.78	2.99×10^{-22}
RGB Train 2	-17.17	1.14×10^{-22}
RGB Train 3	-16.84	2.61×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 1	-16.33	9.32×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 2	-15.47	8.68×10^{-21}
Grayscale Train 3	-15.98	2.35×10^{-21}

Table 6: T-test for DFL Loss

3.2 Performance Evaluation of YOLOv10-S Across Anomalies and Color Modes

The detection and classification performance of the model was further evaluated across different anomaly types and color modes. The analysis examined how well the model distinguished among extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping using RGB and grayscale images. Multivariate and between-subjects test results were analyzed to determine the significance of anomaly type and color mode on precision, recall, and mAP50. This evaluation provides insight into which anomaly type and color configuration yielded the highest detection accuracy and generalization performance.

3.2.1. Multivariate Analysis. A Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of anomaly type and color mode on the performance metrics: precision, recall, and mAP50. The multivariate test using Pillai's Trace (Table 7) showed that anomaly type had a statistically significant effect on overall model performance ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the type of printing anomaly greatly influenced the capability of the model to detect and classify. In contrast, color mode showed a moderate multivariate effect on model performance ($p = 0.068$). Although not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, this result suggests that color information contributed moderately to variations in model accuracy across the evaluation metrics.

Effect	Value	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Anomaly	1.397	4.650	0.000	0.466
Color	0.388	2.965	0.068	0.388

Table 7: Multivariate Test Results (Pillai's Trace)

3.2.2 Between-Subjects Analysis. The between-subjects results were also analyzed to determine how each independent factor, anomaly type and color mode, individually influenced the detection performance of the model. As shown in Table 8, anomaly type had a strong and statistically significant impact across all evaluation metrics. The results indicated high F-values for precision ($F = 40.67$, $p < 0.001$), recall ($F = 9.35$, $p = 0.001$), and mAP50 ($F = 25.56$, $p < 0.001$), with corresponding large effect sizes (η^2). This suggests that the nature of the defect, such as whether it was a spaghetti, warping, or extrusion problem, greatly affected how accurately the model identified and classified anomalies.

Meanwhile, color mode demonstrated a significant effect only on precision ($F = 9.34$, $p = 0.008$, $\eta^2 = 0.369$), indicating that image color influenced how the model correctly identifies true positives. However, its effects on recall and mAP50 were not significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that color differences did not substantially affect how well the model captured all instances of anomalies. The Partial Eta Squared values show that Anomaly had a strong effect on the dependent variables (ranging from 0.637 to 0.884), while the effect of Color and the Anomaly \times Color interaction were comparatively smaller. Overall, these findings highlight that anomaly type is a major factor impacting model performance, while color has a limited effect except when interacting with anomaly type for certain metrics.

Source	Dependent Variable	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Anomaly	Precision	40.67	0.000	0.884
	Recall	9.35	0.001	0.637
	mAP50	25.56	0.000	0.827
Color	Precision	9.34	0.008	0.369
	Recall	1.79	0.200	0.101
	mAP50	3.03	0.101	0.159

Table 8: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

3.2.3 Estimated Marginal Means. The estimated marginal means analysis revealed clear performance differences among anomaly types and between color modes. As shown in Table 9, Spaghetti anomalies achieved the highest mean values across all metrics, indicating that the model was most effective in detecting this defect type. This was followed by Stringing and Warping, which demonstrated moderate detection performance, while Extrusion Problems consistently yielded the lowest scores, confirming they were the most difficult anomalies to identify accurately. These results suggest that YOLOv10-S was more adept at detecting visually distinct and spatially irregular defects, such as Spaghetti, than subtle irregularities like extrusion inconsistencies.

For color mode, RGB images consistently outperformed grayscale, achieving higher average scores across all three evaluation metrics compared to grayscale. This finding indicates that color information enhanced the ability of the

model to distinguish fine visual and texture-based variations among the anomalies.

Category	Type	Precision	Recall	mAP50
Anomaly	Extrusion	51.9	53.0	49.1
	Spaghetti	80.4	73.9	80.2
	Stringing	69.0	61.9	67.1
	Warping	65.3	69.8	65.3
Color	Grayscale	63.8	62.6	63.2
	RGB	69.4	66.6	67.6

Table 9: Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly and Color)

3.3 Final Model Training Results

The YOLOv10-S model, trained under the RGB Train 1 configuration, shows consistent performance across the validation, and testing phases. During validation, the model achieved a mAP50 of 75.6%, precision of 74.9%, and recall of 70.9%, reflecting strong detection accuracy and balanced classification performance. When evaluated on the test set, the model sustained comparable results, mAP50 of 71.6%, precision of 71.7%, and recall of 73.3%. The close alignment between validation and test metrics indicates that the model effectively generalized to unseen data.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this research paper presents the solutions to the problem statements and discusses potential improvements to the study. This section also provides a summary of the results and an overview of the achievements of the study throughout the experimentation process. The purpose of this section is to provide a comprehensive summary of the research and its findings.

4.1 Conclusion

The research aimed to address two major problem statements related to the YOLOv10-S model. Each subsection presents a summary of the steps completed, results obtained, and conclusions drawn by the researchers. These focus on the performance of the YOLOv10-S model in terms of loss values and its accuracy in detecting and classifying 3D printing anomalies.

4.1.1. Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values. The analysis of YOLOv10-S loss values revealed a significant difference between training and validation, particularly in the Box and Distribution Focal Loss components, which validated the research hypothesis. The results indicated that the model localized defects effectively during training but demonstrated limited generalization in producing accurate bounding box predictions on unseen data. A possible explanation is the complex nature of 3D Printing defects, which often

have irregular shapes, unclear edges, or blend into the background, making accurate boundary localization challenging. Additionally, minor variations in lighting, resolution, and filament texture affects how the model interprets object edges. Since the research hypothesis stated that there is a significant difference between training and validation losses, and the results confirmed this, the hypothesis is accepted. While this implies limitations in the localization capabilities of the model, it does not undermine the effectiveness of the system. This acceptance of the hypothesis directly guides future research efforts toward refining the bounding box regression mechanisms within the YOLO architecture to better handle the visual complexity of FDM anomalies. On the other hand, the stability of classification loss indicates strong generalization in identifying defect types, even when bounding boxes are not perfectly aligned. This finding is significant, as it confirms the reliability of the system in providing accurate, real-time alerts for defect detection in additive manufacturing, supporting its goal of early error detection and quality assurance.

4.1.2 Determine the Accuracy in Terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in Classifying Among the Different Anomalies and Between RGB and Grayscale Images. The YOLOv10-S model exhibited high classification accuracy across all anomaly categories. Spaghetti anomalies obtained the highest precision, recall, and mean Average Precision scores, while extrusion defects recorded the lowest values. The MANOVA results revealed statistically significant effects of both color mode and anomaly type on performance metrics. Estimated marginal means reinforced these findings, particularly highlighting the consistent advantage of RGB and the detectability of Spaghetti anomalies across modalities. The hypothesis that there is a significant effect of anomaly type and color mode on detection performance is therefore accepted. This implies that image modality plays an important role in how reliably different types of anomalies are detected. The variation in effectiveness, such as Grayscale performing better for Warping while RGB excels for others, suggests that a one-size-fits-all model is not optimal. However, for the purpose of building a practical and generalizable detection system, RGB was chosen as the default image setting because it consistently delivered the best performance across the majority of anomalies to balance detection accuracy and implementation simplicity and ensure reliable real-time monitoring.

4.2 Recommendations

Several strategic recommendations are proposed to optimize the application and performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting 3D Printing anomalies. These suggestions address key areas for improvement, such as enhancing dataset diversity, fine-tuning model configurations, and expanding the anomaly detection scope to ensure better applicability and reliability.

The performance of the model significantly improved by expanding both the dataset and the range of detectable 3D printing anomalies. While the current dataset focuses on

common defects such as extrusion, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, future work incorporates more complex anomalies including thermal inconsistencies, nozzle clogs, dimensional inaccuracies, layer shifting, layer separation, weak infill, and bonding issues. The addition of a broader variety of materials, printer models, and environmental conditions improves the capability of the model to generalize, making it more adaptable across diverse production setups. Access to larger and higher-quality datasets also enables the model to achieve greater detection accuracy and strength, benefiting both novice and professional users.

To enhance accessibility and user interaction, a web-based interface is recommended for the anomaly detection system. This platform would allow users to perform real-time anomaly detection, upload and analyze 3D printing images, and receive automated troubleshooting suggestions based on detected issues. Provision of offline functionality ensures that the system remains operational even in areas with limited internet connectivity, providing reliable support for users in various settings.

Implementation of multiple camera angles around the 3D printer is also recommended to capture a more complete view of the printing process. By minimizing blind spots and providing multiple perspectives, the system can detect complex or hidden defects more effectively. This multi-angle setup enhances detection accuracy, especially for intricate prints where certain anomalies may not be visible from a single viewpoint.

Finally, integrating an automatic stop or pause function directly into the firmware of the printer or control interface would enable the system to take immediate action when anomalies are detected. This real-time intervention can prevent material waste, reduce the likelihood of severe print failures, and promote sustainable production practices. Such automation not only increases printing efficiency and cost-effectiveness but also reinforces the practical value of the system for everyday use in both industrial and research environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The researchers express their heartfelt gratitude to Almighty God for His guidance and wisdom throughout this study. They extend special thanks to Elmer Haro, PhD., their research adviser, for his guidance, patience, and valuable insights that greatly contributed to the success of this work. Appreciation is also given to the College of Information Technology of the University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos for the support and resources provided. Lastly, the researchers thank their families and friends for their continuous encouragement and understanding.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cenedese, Elisa. "3D Printing Anomaly Detection: Implementation of a ML System Using Yolov5 and EfficientNet-Lite." Webthesis, 20 Dec. 2022, webthesis.biblio.polito.it/id/eprint/25499.

- [2] Karayel, Elif, and Yahya Bozkurt. "Additive Manufacturing Method and Different Welding Applications." *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 5, Aug. 2020, pp. 11424–38, doi:10.1016/j.jmrt.2020.08.039.
- [3] 6Wresearch. "Philippines 3D Printing Market: Trends & Outlook 2030." *Philippines 3D Printing Market | Trends & Outlook 2030*, www.6wresearch.com/industry-report/philippines-3d-printing-market. Accessed 1 Oct. 2024.
- [4] "Sustainable Development Goals." UNDP, www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals..
- [5] Roboflow Universe. (2025). Explore the Roboflow Universe [Data set]. Roboflow. <https://universe.roboflow.com>
- [6] Hu, WenJing, et al. "Real-time Defect Detection for FFF 3D Printing Using Lightweight Model Deployment." *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, Sept. 2024, doi.org/10.1007/s00170-024-14452-4.
- [7] Bast, Sebastian, et al. "Quality Control in Additive Manufacturing: Image Dataset for Defect Detection in Fused Filament Fabrication." Zenodo, Jan. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712897>.
- [8] Charia, Oumaima, et al. "YOLO-Strings: A YOLO-compatible Dataset for Detecting Stringing During 3D Printing." Zenodo, Jan. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14711320>.

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Spaghetti.....	25
2. Stringing.....	26
3. Blobs and Zits.....	26
4. Under Extrusion.....	27
5. Warping.....	28
6. Layer Shifting.....	29
7. Layer Separation.....	29
8. First Layer Issue.....	30
9. Poor Bridging.....	31
10. Theoretical Framework.....	34
11. Operational Framework.....	38
12. Confusion Matrix.....	46
13. System Decomposition Chart.....	58
14. Anomaly Bounding Box.....	62
15. Splash Screen.....	67
16. Introduction Video.....	68
17. Home Page.....	69
18. Live Camera Feed.....	70
19. Uploaded Images.....	71
20. Uploaded Video.....	72

21. Anomaly Bounding Box.....	73
22. Visual and Audio Anomaly Alert.....	74
23. Anomaly Details.....	75
24. Anomaly Report.....	76
25. Brightness Alert.....	77
26. Menu.....	77
27. Model Page.....	78
28. Training Results Page.....	79
29. User Manual Page.....	80
30. Box Loss.....	91
31. Class Loss.....	92
32. Distribution Focal Loss.....	94
33. Training Results.....	106
34. Confusion Matrix Results.....	108

LIST OF TABLES

1. Performance Metrics of YOLOv10 Compared to Other YOLO Models.....	20
2. Performance Metrics of YOLOv10 Models at Different Scales.....	21
3. Dataset Characteristics.....	39
4. Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset Composition.....	40
5. Percentage Allocation for Each Phase.....	43
6. Dataset Allocation for Each Phase.....	43
7. Dataset Allocation for Each Phase After Augmentation.....	44
8. Results Interpretation.....	84
9. Highest and Lowest Criteria.....	85
10. T-test for Box Loss.....	91
11. T-test for Class Loss.....	93
12. T-test for Distribution Focal Loss.....	95
13. Descriptive Statistical Analysis.....	97
14. Multivariate Tests.....	98
15. Tests Between Subjects Effects.....	100
16. Estimated Marginal Mean for Anomaly.....	101
17. Estimated Marginal Mean for Colors.....	102
18. Estimated Marginal Mean for Anomaly * Color.....	103
19. Validation Set Results at Varying Confidence Thresholds.....	110
20. Test Set Results at Varying Confidence Thresholds.....	111
21. Extrusion Problem Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.....	114

22. Spaghetti Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds..... 115

23. Stringing Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.....116

24. Warping Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.....117

LIST OF FORMULAS

1. Precision..... 46

2. Recall..... 47

3. Mean Average Precision..... 48

4. F1 Score..... 49

5. Paired T-Test..... 50

6. One-Way MANOVA..... 51

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENT.....	iv
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	v
LIST OF FIGURES.....	xii
LIST OF TABLES.....	xiv
LIST OF FORMULAS.....	xv

Chapter

I.	INTRODUCTION	1
	1.1 Statement of the Problem.....	2
	1.2 Hypothesis.....	3
	1.3 Assumption	4
	1.4 Significance of the Study	5
	1.4.1 Prototyping Businesses.....	5
	1.4.2 Manufacturers and Industries	5
	1.4.3 Educational Institutions	6
	1.4.4 The Researchers.....	6
	1.5 Scope of the Study.....	7
II.	REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	10
	2.1 Computer Vision (CV).....	10
	2.1.1 Class Recognition	11
	2.1.2 Object Detection	11
	2.1.3 Semantic Segmentation	13
	2.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI)	13
	2.2.1 Machine Learning.....	14
	2.2.2 Deep Learning	15
	2.3 You Only Look Once Version 10 (YOLOv10)	18
	2.4 3D Printing Technology	21
	2.4.1 Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)	22
	2.4.2 Printing Anomalies	24
	2.5 Theoretical Framework.....	33

III.	METHODOLOGY	37
3.1	Research Design.....	39
3.2	Dataset.....	39
3.3	Data Collection Procedures.....	41
3.3.1	Addressing Dataset Imbalance.....	41
3.3.2	Data Splitting.....	42
3.4	Measurement and Statistical Treatment.....	45
3.4.1	Confusion Matrix.....	45
3.4.2	Precision	46
3.4.3	Recall	47
3.4.4	Mean Average Precision	47
3.4.5	F1 Score.....	49
3.4.6	Paired T-Test.....	50
3.4.7	One-Way Multivariate Analysis Variance (MANOVA)	51
3.5	Data Analysis and Interpretation.....	51
3.6	Confidence Threshold Selection.....	52
3.7	Ethical and Privacy Considerations	53
3.8	Model Deployment	54
IV.	SOLUTION.....	57
4.1	System Decomposition Chart	57
4.1.1	Data Acquisition	59
4.1.2	Anomaly Detection and Classification	60
4.1.3	Anomaly Analytics	61
4.2	Development Tools	63
4.2.1	Jupyter Notebook.....	63
4.2.2	Google Colab.....	64
4.2.3	Programming Language	64
4.2.4	User Interface (UI) Design	65
4.2.5	Ultralytics	65
4.2.6	OpenCV.....	65
4.2.7	PyTorch.....	66
4.2.8	PyQT.....	66
4.3	User Interface.....	66
4.3.1	Data Acquisition	69
4.3.2	Anomaly Analytics	72
4.4	Testing Components.....	80
4.4.1	Unit Testing	81
4.4.2	Integration Testing.....	82
4.4.3	Validation Testing	82
4.4.4	Acceptance Testing	83

V.	RESULTS AND ANALYSIS	89
5.1	Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values of Training Loss and Validation Loss	89
5.1.1	Box Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset Trainings.....	90
5.1.2	Class Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset Trainings.....	92
5.1.3	DFL Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset	93
5.2	Determine the Accuracy in terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in classifying among the different anomalies and between RGB and grayscale images	96
5.2.1	Descriptive Statistical Analysis	96
5.2.2	Multivariate Tests	98
5.2.3	Tests of Between-Subjects Effects.....	99
5.2.4	Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly and Color)	100
5.2.5	Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly * Color)	102
5.3	YOLOv10-S Training Result	104
5.3.1	Training Loss	105
5.3.2	Validation Loss	105
5.3.3	Model Precision.....	106
5.3.4	Model Recall.....	107
5.3.5	Model mAP50.....	107
5.3.6	Model Confusion Matrix	107
5.4	Confidence Threshold Evaluation and Selection.....	109
5.4.1	Per-Anomaly Confidence Threshold Analysis	112
VI.	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	120
6.1	Conclusion	120
6.1.1	Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values	120
6.1.2	Determine the Accuracy in Terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in Classifying Among the Different Anomalies and between RGB and Grayscale Images	121
6.2	Recommendations.....	122
6.2.1	Dataset and Anomaly Scope Expansion	122
6.2.2	Web-Based Interface for Enhanced User Interaction	123
6.2.3	Multiple Camera Angles Implementation.....	123
6.2.4	3D Printer Automatic Stop or Pause Functionality Integration....	124
	PROJECT MANAGEMENT	125
A.	Hardware Requirements.....	125
B.	Software Requirements	127
C.	Peopleware Recommendation.....	128

D. System Budget	130
E. Operational Setup Recommendations	130
F. Time Management	131
GLOSSARY	133
LIST OF SCREENSHOTS.....	138
USERS' MANUAL.....	139
APPENDICES	154
A. Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship	154
B. Minutes of the Thesis Project Proposal Defense	155
C. Minutes of the Thesis Final Defense.....	157
D. PERT Table	159
E. Ethical Consideration.....	160
F. System Budget	165
G. Extrusion Problem Training Images	166
H. Spaghetti Training Images	191
I. Stringing Training Images.....	216
J. Warping Training Images.....	241
K. Product Logo.....	266
L. Team Logo	267
M. Product Poster	268
N. Product Packaging	269
O. Grammarly Results (Chapter I-III)	270
P. Grammarly Results (Chapter IV-VI).....	271
Q. Turnitin Results.....	272
REFERENCES	273
CURRICULUM VITAE	281

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, industries have shifted to digital prototyping with the use of computer-aided design (CAD), but many still rely on traditional subtractive manufacturing (SM), which is often inefficient. The advent of additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as three-dimensional (3D) printing, has changed this field by giving ways to the creation of physical objects from digital designs [CE2022]. In contrast to conventional manufacturing methods, additive manufacturing (AM) operates on the principle of item creation by layer-by-layer stacks of materials [EK2020].

Today, 3D Printing technology is widely used in various fields, particularly in the manufacturing industry, due to the availability of affordable fused-deposition modeling (FDM) 3D Printers, which makes it accessible to most individuals and small-scale businesses [WR2021]. Consideration of the quality and accuracy of the end products becomes a fundamental factor. However, during production, problems such as defects occur, resulting in the rejection of the printed object. This leads to a loss of time and resources and contributes to plastic waste [CE2022].

The sustainable development goals (SDG), established by the United Nations in 2015, integrated 17 specific goals to end poverty, as well as other deprivations, by an urgent call for action in all countries [UN2024]. Among these goals is the need to address problems such as waste in production and unsustainable processes that consequently lead to the environment and resources to be jeopardized. This issue highlights the importance of SDG 9, which promotes

resilient and sustainable industrial practices, and SDG 12, which focuses on the area that ensures sustainable consumption and production patterns. By addressing the plastic, time, and resource waste generated by 3D Printing technology, the manufacturing industry aligns with the objectives of the United Nations.

To achieve these goals effectively, this study implements a real-time anomaly detection during 3D Printing. This approach seeks to alleviate the problems and improve production efficiency with the use of minimized rework, reduced operational costs, and enhanced sustainability and protection of the environment with the decrease of the disposal of defective parts. The researchers use machine learning, specifically YOLOv10-S, to create a real-time assessment of the object during the 3D Printing process. The study also follow a multi-class classification approach, to make it possible to detect and classify the specific types of defects present to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the remedial measures throughout the 3D Printing process.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The 3D Printing technology occasionally faces issues, such as defects in print, that lead to material wastage, decline in product quality, and the need for repeated prints. This poses the need for an intervention to prevent and address the occurrences of defects in this technology. Generally, this research seeks to develop a real-time anomaly detection and classification system for 3D Printing with the use of YOLOv10-S for anomaly detection and classification. Specifically, it aims to investigate the problem that follows:

1.1.1 Determine the performance of YOLOv10-S by evaluating loss values in terms of:

- a. Training Loss
- b. Validation Loss

1.1.2 Determine the accuracy in terms of precision, recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in classifying among the different anomalies and between RGB and grayscale images:

- a. Extrusion Problem
- b. Spaghetti
- c. Stringing
- d. Warping

1.2 Hypothesis

The study focuses primarily on the assessment of how effectively the model YOLOv10-S identifies and classifies anomalies in the 3D Printing process. By examining the performance of the model under various conditions and scenarios, the researchers seek to understand the strengths and limitations of YOLOv10-S. The result of this study serves as a contribution to build a better method in the detection and classification of anomalies in 3D Printing.

1.2.1 There is a significant difference between the loss values of YOLOv10-S in terms of training loss and validation loss.

1.2.2 There is a significant difference in the precision, recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S when classifying among the following anomalies— extrusion

problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping— as well as between RGB and grayscale images.

1.3 Assumption

Several assumptions have been made in conducting the study. These assumptions are essential as they work as a foundation to develop theories for this study and are, therefore, a fundamental factor in the development and implementation of the research process. A clear recognition of these assumptions allows for more accurate comprehension of the results and their applicability for future studies within 3D Printing applications.

1.3.1 YOLOv10-S generalizes well to unseen data, where their performance on the test set reflects their ability to detect anomalies in real-world 3D Printing scenarios.

1.3.2 The selected anomalies (extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping) adequately represent the common issues encountered in 3D Printing and the characteristics of each type of anomaly are consistent across different samples.

1.3.3 The 3D Printing environment remains stable and does not introduce noise that negatively affects model performance.

1.3.4 YOLOv10-S is suitable for the task of anomaly detection and classification within the context of 3D Printing.

1.3.5 The performance of the YOLOv10-S model was assessed using mAP50 instead of mAP50-95. This allows for a less strict threshold, making the evaluation more flexible and suitable for early anomaly detection in 3D Printing.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The outcomes of this study help detect anomalies in fused-deposition modeling (FDM) 3D Printing processes significantly. Moreover, it has a significant impact on various sectors, including prototyping businesses, manufacturers, educational institutions, environmental advocates, and the researchers themselves. By addressing the challenges of real-time anomaly detection, the result improves quality control, enhances efficiency, and saves costs.

1.4.1 Prototyping Businesses

Small prototyping businesses using FDM printers reduced costs and improved efficiency by incorporating this system, which minimized material waste and enhanced product quality. Additionally, this allowed these small businesses with an edge over others because their fast production times facilitated larger variations of a product. The ability to detect problematic prints within minutes rather than hours enables businesses to reprint designs more rapidly, potentially reducing time. Furthermore, small business operations accommodate the ever-increasing demands of efficiency and innovation, keeping in line with international directions for globalization and competitiveness worldwide.

1.4.2 Manufacturers and Industries

Although the system is primarily directed toward FDM printers, successful integration proves to be a first step toward more general applications that involve other 3D Printing technologies, such as Stereolithography (SLA) or Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), widely used in widespread manufacturing processes. For high-volume manufacturing operations, the system addresses important points in production

reliability and scalability. Undetected printing anomalies in manufacturing contexts often lead to significant financial losses, with single failed production runs potentially costing thousands of dollars in wasted materials, machine time, and delayed deliveries. Therefore, this methodology enables a guarantee of quality and reliability independent of the printing technology. It then helps the manufacturer optimize the process with reliability and consistency in the output.

1.4.3 Educational Institutions

Schools and universities using FDM printing for education and research are supported by reliable printing processes that enrich hands-on learning in STEM fields. This system enhances the learning experience, allowing students to focus more on the design and applicative aspects of 3D Printing rather than searching for errors in printing processes. It equips instructors and researchers to work on bigger projects, stimulating innovative thinking and deeper understanding in STEM. Moreover, the system itself becomes a teaching tool for demonstrating concepts in machine learning, computer vision, automation, and quality control. Students examine how real-time data analysis informs decision-making processes, gaining practical insights into artificial intelligence applications that complement their theoretical coursework.

1.4.4 The Researchers

It equips researchers with in-depth knowledge in the area of anomaly detection and classification in FDM 3D Printing, competency in the use of machine learning and real-time monitoring capabilities, and further knowledge of additive manufacturing. Furthermore, researchers gain significant exposure to developing practical solutions

that connect theoretical understanding with industrial implementations. The research also helps set a basis for subsequent research initiatives, working toward innovation within the scopes of automation, artificial intelligence, and advanced manufacturing technologies.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study mainly focuses on examining and identifying the different types of anomalies that occurs during the real-time 3D Printing process using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, specifically You Only Look Once version 10 (YOLOv10) for anomaly detection and classification. YOLOv10 is one of the recently launched versions of the popular YOLO series that aims at providing fast and accurate object detection when compared to its predecessors as it has better architecture. Among all the different variants of the model, the researchers chose to focus on YOLOv10-S which provides an excellent balance between speed and accuracy.

The researchers train the models using publicly available datasets from Roboflow [RU2024]. Images of defective prints are gathered from various sources to ensure that anomalies are equally represented in the context of the 3D Printing process. The images are also preprocessed to allow for a uniform input size to be fed into the YOLOv10-S model; the image size is therefore kept fixed at 640x640. However, it is important to note that the paper does not establish all possible defects in an FDM printer. Instead, it focuses on the detection of spaghetti, stringing, extrusion problems, and warping anomalies that occur most frequently in 3D Prints and are the only considered anomalies in the available dataset, thus limiting the scope

of defect identification and classification to these specific types. Additionally, prints with intentionally induced porosity, spaces, or holes are not included in the training dataset, which leads to incorrect detection of such features as anomalies.

With the presence of various types of 3D Printers, the researchers also decided to focus exclusively on the FDM printer. This technique has been widely used in 3D Printing technology, especially in home-based operations, education, and small businesses, which propels researchers to seek to produce relevant and applicable data for this significant number of users. While concentrated on FDM, this approach provides the advantage of a controlled environment, which is fundamental in securing the consistency and reliability of the collected data. The inclusion of various 3D Printers complicates the analysis due to the wide range of technologies and behaviors observed across different machines. The results of this study are not necessarily generalizable to other forms of 3D Printing, such as stereolithography (SLA), which uses an ultraviolet (UV) laser to cure liquid resin, or selective laser sintering (SLS), which fuses powdered materials with a laser. These processes operate based on different principles and materials.

In conclusion, this chapter introduces the increasing interest in additive manufacturing (AM), particularly on fused deposition modeling (FDM), due to its accessibility and affordability. However, this technology is also accompanied by challenges, especially during the printing process. One of the challenges pertains to the occurrence of anomalies or defects, which are unintended variations in the printed object. Such anomalies cause material and time waste, hence affecting the overall efficiency and productivity of the printing process.

To address these issues, the study seeks to utilize YOLOv10-S, a machine learning model, to establish a real-time 3D Printing anomaly detection and classification and aid with the enhancement of the performance of the system. The study is also in line with the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, particularly SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), as it aims to promote sustainable production practices and minimize waste in the field of additive manufacturing. The results are also expected to be beneficial for different sectors such as small prototyping businesses, manufacturers, educational institutions, and researchers. However, the study is limited in its focus on FDM printers only and the four types of anomalies namely, extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. In addition, it does not consider the external factors like environmental conditions, which restricts the generalizability of the results. The study, nonetheless, establishes a solid foundation for further investigations and developments in the detection and classification of anomalies in 3D Printing.

In summary, this study aims to use the capabilities of machine learning models by employing YOLOv10-S to finally address the challenges and offer solutions to the common problems in 3D Printing, and consequently, brings more sustainability to production and develops the technological capability of additive manufacturing. The integration of real-time monitoring during the fabrication process transforms the system from a manual operation into an intelligent tool capable of autonomous oversight. This transition assists in cost reduction through the early identification of print failures and prevents the unnecessary waste of raw materials. Consequently, this research establishes a foundation for future systems that prioritize efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental responsibility in modern manufacturing.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter provides an overview of key concepts related to 3D Printing technology, focusing on the widely used Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) method. It also discusses common printing anomalies that occur during the 3D Printing process and their impact on print quality. Furthermore, it explores advanced solutions for addressing these challenges, focusing on the integration of machine learning models like YOLOv10-S for anomaly detection and classification. Relevant studies and techniques are also reviewed to provide a comprehensive understanding of these innovative approaches.

2.1 Computer Vision (CV)

The process of making a machine 'see.' This technique identifies, tracks, and measures targets for additional image processing using a camera and computer rather than the human eye [TH2019]. In the age of information technology, it is widely used in all parts of daily life. It has been widely used in unmanned vehicles, networks, education, scientific research, agriculture, and other fields, with remarkable outcomes. In accordance with a study, machine self-learning is the game changer, and data is the ultimate incentive. It is an area of AI, as per [JZ2023] based on research by [HT1996]. To understand the content of visual data (pictures and videos) is the aim of CV. This usually entails creating techniques to mimic human vision. Three basic categories emerge in the field of computer vision, each of which stands for a certain aspect of visual perception and processing: segmentation, object identification, and image

classification. Together, these categories provide the framework for computer vision systems, and each one plays a distinct and essential function in a range of applications [HM2023].

2.1.1 Class Recognition

Humans quickly distinguish items and interpret emotions in a three-dimensional world. In contrast, computer vision systems rely on feature extraction, which includes finding patterns that define things. To maintain accuracy, databases and complex classification techniques are required for distinguishing between similar entities such as cats and dogs [MN2024]. Class Recognition or image classification is the process of classifying visual inputs into predetermined groups or labels. This method involves training a computer vision system to recognize and categorize photos depending on their content. An image classification model, for example, is trained to distinguish between defective and normal photovoltaic modules in a solar panel manufacturing facility [ZA2023]. This categorization, which is based on patterns and attributes extracted from photographs, allows the system to reliably decide which class each image belongs to. Image categorization is necessary when understanding the broad content of an image is critical.

2.1.2 Object Detection

A substantial gain over picture classification. While image classification focuses on detecting and categorizing things in a picture, object detection goes a step further by precisely pinpointing their positions within the visual data. In essence, it addresses the question, "Where are the objects in this image?". This ability is extremely valuable and applicable in real-world situations where comprehending the spatial

arrangement of goods is essential. For example, with self-driving cars, object detection enables a vehicle to not only recognize other vehicles on the road but also calculate their precise locations and dimensions. This spatial awareness is critical for making informed judgments and maintaining safety in a variety of businesses [AB2023]. Object detection uses techniques such as bounding boxes or more complex approaches such as key point detection to achieve exact object localization. A study by [AA2021], utilized object detection as a foundational component of a vision-based system aimed at real-time traffic anomaly detection. The system employed the YOLOv5 model for detecting anomalies from traffic camera footage, allowing it to identify unusual events such as accidents or stalled vehicles effectively.

2.1.2.1 Visual Anomaly Detection (VAD)

Anomaly detection is a challenging issue in machine learning applications, distinguishing between anomalous patterns and normal samples. When working with pictures, it is commonly called image anomaly or visual anomaly detection (VAD). In recent years, the development of deep learning has led to an increase in the momentum of the visual anomaly detection (VAD) problem. This surge is attributed to its increase in its present specifications because it enhances efficiency and efficacy in many areas of performance. VAD is applied in many different areas and has great potential and performance. In the field of manufacturing, it is used to check for defects [TT2022]. In the medical field, it helps find lesions and tumors in medical images [LS2024]. In the automotive area, it detects unknown objects while

driving autonomously [BD2022]. In logistics, it detects unusual events in videos [WS2020]. Generally, this area aims to develop and use deep learning models to identify unusual patterns.

2.1.3 Semantic Segmentation

Unlike image classification and object detection, which deal with objects as a whole, segmentation is concerned with recognizing and distinguishing individual pixels or regions within an image. The goal is to divide a picture into semantically meaningful segments or masks, with each pixel allocated to a certain object or background category [YR2021]. This degree of detail is very useful in situations that require pixel-level accuracy. In medical imaging, segmentation is used to detect and characterize tumors in MRI scans, allowing for more accurate diagnosis and treatment planning. Similarly, segmentation in photo editing enables the selective alteration of certain elements or portions of an image, offering significant creative freedom.

2.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

A general term that refers to the ability of machines to mimic human intelligence, particularly through the utilization of computers. This field focuses on developing algorithms and software that allows machines to see and make decisions toward specific objectives. The term "artificial intelligence" was coined for the first time during the Dartmouth Conference of the 1950s by John McCarthy. The term "artificial intelligence" was coined for the first time during the Dartmouth Conference of the 1950s by John McCarthy, marking the beginning of

AI research as a distinct discipline. Since then, this field has grown at unprecedented rates, especially after 1990, leading into applications in areas like knowledge processing, pattern recognition, machine learning, and natural language processing [ZC2021]. However, AI has had its time of funding reductions due to disillusionments termed "AI winters," characterized by the subsequent disappointment in the capabilities of AI [FL2020]. Despite these setbacks, several vital factors have contributed to the resurgence of artificial intelligence (AI), with the success of machine learning (ML) being one of the most significant. Since the late 1980s, key theories and techniques in ML have, in fact, made an impressive foundation for this area of study, which includes decision trees, support vector machines, AdaBoost, and random forests among others [JY2022].

2.2.1 Machine Learning

A subset of artificial intelligence which allows computer programs to learn and improve performing tasks assigned to them by iterative learning through data [JC2021]. It consists of four primary categories: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning [ZC2021]. Supervised learning uses labeled data to train models, allowing the prediction of the outcome from the given features. This category is further divided into classification, which predicts discrete values, and regression, which forecasts continuous values. Unlike supervised learning, unsupervised learning functions on unclassified data by identifying patterns or structures within the dataset through techniques of clustering and dimensionality reduction. Moreover, semi-supervised learning integrates elements of both supervised and unsupervised learning; in this process, both labeled and unlabeled data are used for

training. Semi-supervised learning is useful when the labeled data are either scarce or expensive. Reinforcement learning focuses more on decision-making through interacting with an environment, such that agents learn to behave in the best way possible in accordance to the reward or penalties that they get from those actions. This method is based on behavioral psychology and uses a trial-and-error approach to improve actions through time [ZC2021].

2.2.2 Deep Learning

This area deeply influenced a significant number of industries by allowing modern machines to learn from huge datasets with minimal interventions by humans. The capabilities have made the deep learning models perform well in applications like image recognition, natural language processing, and predictive analytics. Deep learning involves methods like neural networks that do detailed analysis of the data, giving better performance in several applications [JC2021]. However, these models are quite computationally expensive and require large amounts of data to achieve high accuracy. Deep learning is rapidly evolving and is recognized as one of the most adaptive technologies in various fields, but challenges still remain in effectively addressing complex data problems [DS2021].

Various applications of such technology have been relevant as the world continues to evolve. Take, for example, the study [SM2023] made by Soori, which concluded that the application of deep learning help create robots that are versatile, more intelligent, and capable of executing more complex tasks. Deep learning is also relevant in the cyber security world. The use of deep learning has been found to be a

great way to detect intrusion in a network by the use of the latest simulated network traffic dataset. It was found that promising results of using deep learning but further improvements are catered for better performance of deep learning in cyber security. Cybersecurity architectures are modified by deep learning anomaly detection models to create strong and adaptive network intrusion detection systems that accurately identify common vulnerabilities and exposures as well as zero-day network behavioral aspects, lowering the chance of compromise [AL2021].

Deep learning creates incredibly high-level data representations from vast volumes of raw data, in contrast to conventional machine learning and data mining methods. Consequently, it has offered a great solution to various and numerous real-world issues. To account for the properties of the raw data, a deep learning method needs to have the appropriate data-driven modeling. Before the system supports intelligent decision-making, the advanced learning algorithms are first taught using the information gathered about the intended application [SI2021].

2.2.2.1 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

A type of deep learning algorithm that makes images classification. It is patterned on the way human vision works, and human eye perceives information in an image [KA2020]. As CNN are translation variant of Deep learning, it means that this type of network identifies patterns wherever they exist in a picture. Convolutional layers, which apply filters to an image and detect features regardless of their position, are used to do this. CNNs are more reliable and accurate in real-world situations thanks to this feature, which

allows them to identify images regardless of their orientation or position [BJ2023].

In the perspective of CNN, an input is processed by assigning importance to the different features of the image such as patterns and the objects around, which distinguishes it from others. In comparison to traditional methods, CNNs need very little preprocessing, and they are considered one of the most efficient algorithms for understanding and analyzing visual data [KA2020]. The features that CNNs extract from images are not pre-learned because they learn as they are trained on images. The astonishing performance of deep learning models in computer vision is attributed in large part to automatic feature extraction. Deep CNNs require access to large and labeled datasets for computer vision applications such as object classification, tracking, and recognition [TM2023].

Although CNNs are very efficient, they require a huge amount of labeled data to be trained to obtain high accuracy. CNNs have demonstrated exceptional success in applications like traffic sign recognition, medical image segmentation, facial detection, and object recognition in natural images, where extensive labeled datasets are available [BD2021]. This requirement makes the process of gathering sufficient labeled data a significant challenge for many industries looking to deploy CNNs for anomaly detection tasks, such as in automated quality control and defect inspection in manufacturing.

2.3 You Only Look Once Version 10 (YOLOv10)

The YOLO family has always sought to optimize between speed and accuracy, aiming for high real-time performance without compromising detection quality. Thus, balance of YOLO between speed and accuracy is a central objective through its various versions, with each new model taking its own approach to optimize between these competing demands. The original YOLO model prioritized fast detection of objects above everything else, thus laying the foundation for the versions that came later [TJ2023]. One of the recent developments within the YOLO family, YOLOv10, is designed for providing maximum accuracy, end-to-end, object detection with minimal latency.

Unlike the past versions of the YOLO family, YOLOv10 combines features and architectural advancements, thus enhancing real-time detection in complex settings. YOLOv10 now introduces significant advancements in object detection, featuring a refined architecture that employs large-kernel convolutions and a dual-pathway mechanism for improved accuracy and efficiency. It eliminates the need for Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) during inference, streamlining the detection process and reducing computational overhead. With adaptive anchor-free detection, YOLOv10 effectively manages challenges like occlusions and small objects, while its lightweight classification head and spatial-channel decoupled down sampling enhance performance without sacrificing speed.

YOLOv10-S belongs to the YOLOv10 family, where there are several model scales (Nano, Small, Medium, Base, Large, Extra Large). The architecture of YOLOv10-S is designed with a focus on efficiency and accuracy. The feature pyramid network (FPN) of the model significantly enhances its spatial awareness, enabling it to capture subtle irregularities in printed layers effectively, which are common in high-precision fields like 3D Printing

[WA2024]. By leveraging this multi-scale approach, the network simultaneously detect both minute surface texture flaws and larger structural deformations across different print layers. Table 1 presents a comparison of the performance of the different YOLO models [AS2024]. With regards to the best balance between computational cost and accuracy, YOLOv10 outperforms previous YOLO models. For example, with many fewer parameters and calculations, YOLOv10-N and S perform better than YOLOv6-3.0-N and S by 1.5 and 2.0 AP, respectively. With 32% less latency, 1.4% AP improvement, and 68% fewer parameters, YOLOv10-L exceeds the capabilities of Gold-YOLO-L. YOLOv10 showed notable advances in efficiency and performance. While utilizing 28% to 57% fewer parameters and 23% to 38% fewer calculations, the model variants (N/S/M/L/X) improve Average Precision (AP) by 1.2% to 1.4%. YOLOv10 is perfect for real-time applications because of the 37% to 70% shorter latencies. These improvements demonstrate the scalability of the model family, where even the smaller variants achieve competitive accuracy while being lightweight enough for deployment in constrained environments. The versatility across different scales makes YOLOv10 suitable for a wide range of tasks, from edge devices with limited resources to high-performance systems. In the context of this research, YOLOv10-S provides the optimal trade-off, delivering robust anomaly detection performance in 3D printing without imposing excessive computational demands. The integration of consistent dual assignments and comprehensive design elements ensures that the model maintains fast processing speeds without sacrificing the precision necessary for detecting small printing errors. Consequently, this architecture makes it possible to run the software directly on 3D printer hardware for instant error detection.

Model	Params (M)	FLOPs(G)	mAP ^{val} ₅₀₋₉₅	Latency(ms)	Latency-forward(ms)
YOLOv6-3.0-N	4.7	11.4	37.0	2.69	1.76
Gold-YOLO-N	5.6	12.1	39.6	2.92	1.82
YOLOv8-N	3.2	8.7	37.3	6.16	1.77
YOLOv10-N	2.3	6.7	39.5	1.84	1.79
YOLOv6-3.0-S	18.5	45.3	44.3	3.42	2.35
Gold-YOLO-S	21.5	46.0	45.4	3.82	2.73
YOLOv8-S	11.2	28.6	44.9	7.07	2.33
YOLOv10-S	7.2	21.6	46.8	2.49	2.39
RT-DETR-R18	20.0	60.0	46.5	4.58	4.49
YOLOv6-3.0-M	34.9	85.8	49.1	5.63	4.56
Gold-YOLO-M	41.3	87.5	49.8	6.38	5.45
YOLOv8-M	25.9	78.9	50.6	9.50	5.09
YOLOv10-M	15.4	59.1	51.3	4.74	4.63
YOLOv6-3.0-L	59.6	150.7	51.8	9.02	7.90
Gold-YOLO-L	75.1	151.7	51.8	10.65	9.78
YOLOv8-L	43.7	165.2	52.9	12.39	8.06
RT-DETR-R50	42.0	136.0	53.1	9.20	9.07
YOLOv10-L	24.4	120.3	53.4	7.28	7.21
YOLOv8-X	68.2	257.8	53.9	16.86	12.83
RT-DETR-R101	76.0	259.0	54.3	13.71	13.58
YOLOv10-X	29.5	160.4	54.4	10.70	10.60

Table 1. Performance Metrics of YOLOv10 Compared to Other YOLO Models.

The YOLOv10 models demonstrate varying levels of complexity, size, and performance, balancing computational cost at various scales with accuracy, as shown in Table 2. The smallest model is YOLOv10-N (with 2.3M parameters and 6.7G FLOPs), which are highly lightweight and optimized for deployment on edge devices; although latency is fast (1.84ms), APs are not high enough: 39.5%. Large models, like YOLOv10-X with 29.5M parameters and 160.4G FLOPs, offer better accuracy (54.4% AP), but more latency of 10.70ms; those are more suitable for tasks requiring high precision. YOLOv10-S comes almost

in a center between accuracy, speed, and efficiency, making it very suitable for anomaly detection in 3D Printing. The model achieves an AP of 46.3%, which is a significant performance compared to the smaller YOLOv10-N model but competitive with the larger models YOLOv10-B or YOLOv10-X. With a latency of mere 2.49ms, YOLOv10-S is fast enough for near real-time applications, especially when resources are constrained, and larger versions lag behind. The compact architecture consists of 7.2 million parameters with 21.6 billion FLOPs, which means efficiency without a fall in performance. This is why YOLOv10-S is practical for applications demanding speed and precision.

Model	Test Size	#Params	FLOPs	AP ^{val}	Latency
YOLOv10-N	640	2.3M	6.7G	38.5%	1.84ms
YOLOv10-S	640	7.2M	21.6G	46.3%	2.49ms
YOLOv10-M	640	15.4M	59.1G	51.1%	4.74ms
YOLOv10-B	640	19.1M	92.0G	52.5%	5.74ms
YOLOv10-L	640	24.4M	120.3G	53.2%	7.28ms
YOLOv10-X	640	29.5M	160.4G	54.4%	10.70ms

Table 2. Performance Metrics of YOLOv10 Models at Different Scales.

2.4 3D Printing Technology

This is also known as additive manufacturing, or layered manufacturing, by extruding a material layer by layer to produce an object. The process includes several steps wherein the first step is modelling and designing using computer aided (CAD) software, or by obtaining a digital model by downloading or scanning if the object to be printed is already existing [BY2021]. Then, the model is inputted into the machine, where specific parameters such as printing speed, temperature, and pattern are selected. Once these parameters are configured,

G-code are generated to guide the 3D Printer through the process, which then begins the actual printing of the part [KV2021].

There are various 3D Printing techniques that are being adopted by users, such as stereolithography (SLA), fused deposition modeling (FDM), selective laser melting (SLM), and electron beam melting (EBM), each uses different technologies to solidify materials layer by layer and cater to specific applications. Globally, the adoption of 3D Printing technology is growing rapidly, and the same trend is seen in the Philippines. The 3D Printing market of the country is rapidly developing, with more businesses and consumers utilizing the technology to create everything from prototypes to complex art works. As per [WR2021], the Philippines 3D Printing Market is predicted to grow at a 15.3% CAGR from 2024 to 2030. The 3D Printing market of the Philippines is being driven by expansion in a variety of sectors, including healthcare, construction, and manufacturing. In addition, these techniques are also generally divided into groups based on the material they utilize, liquid-based, solid-based, and powder-based processes [TC2022]. Among these techniques, FDM is the most widely used, especially for prototyping and small-scale manufacturing, due to its accessibility and cost-effectiveness [GE2024].

2.4.1 Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)

This technology relies mostly on extruding thermoplastic materials through a heated nozzle to build up objects layer by layer. This process is versatile, allowing the use of a wide range of materials, including acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS), polylactic acid (PLA), polyamide, polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG), polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK),

polyetherimide (PEI), polyphenylenesulfide (PPS), polycarbonate (PC), polycaprolactone (PCL), and thermoplastic elastomers (TPE). Only PLA and PCL are biodegradable as per [PP2020] from the available materials. Hence, PLA and PCL possess more eco-friendly nature when compared to others. However, though very popular because of its low cost and flexibility, this process is not without problems. The material deposition and bonding mechanisms involved in FDM leads to several printing anomalies that affect the quality and structural integrity of the printed parts, often resulting in failed prints that contribute to material waste. In accordance with a survey by [FI2020] of more than 200 people, the average 3D Printer user uses 12kg of thermoplastic filament per year. Assumes that 2.2 million 3D Printers are shipped in 2021 [HM2023], the total expected plastic waste output is approximately 26.4 million kg. As per the report, around 10% of 3D Prints are rejected for various reasons, with failed prints yielding the major cause. Given these findings, the material waste, lost time, and resources associated with 3D Printing raise serious issues about sustainability. In addition, these defects commonly occur due to factors that involve poor adhesion between layers, warping, and the existence of void formation between layers, which are factors that are magnified by the thermal and material properties of filaments used [PP2020]. It is of the most importance to understand these defects to further improve and optimize 3D Printing process in producing printed parts, especially in industries that rely on high-precision prototypes or end-use parts. In the following section, the researchers explored the common printing anomalies specific to FDM and underlying causes.

2.4.2 Printing Anomalies

Print quality is one of the most critical factors in the context of 3D Printing, as it directly affects the functionality and reliability of the printed object. The factors influencing print quality depend on conditions related to material properties as well as to printer settings, but they occur upon the interaction of print layers. Although modern FDM printers often incorporate sensors to monitor key parameters like nozzle temperature and build platform conditions, these systems are generally limited in their ability to detect deeper, more complex defects and do not monitor the printing process if it goes as expected [KV2021, CE2022]. The anomalies of the 3D Printing process are irregularities in the product produced, which do not make it equivalent to the intended design and have diverse causes, ranging from common to entirely distinct. Anomalies are detected at different stages of the 3D Printing operation, and they vary in nature and severity. Below is a list of the most common anomalies found during a 3D Printing process [JA2022, PK2024], together with a graphical example for each of the indicated anomalies:

2.4.2.1 Spaghetti

As shown in Figure 1, this anomaly is called for its resemblance to strands of spaghetti. It occurs when the nozzle of the extruder continues extruding filament as it switches between several segments of the print, which results in the material making thin, stringy, and often disordered lines of filament rather than contributing to the desired print structure. The outcome is

a messy build-up of filament that resembles spaghetti, since the material is not applied to the targeted areas but rather drips and collects on unintended regions.

Figure 1. Spaghetti.

2.4.2.2 Stringing and Oozing

Both are related to unwanted filament leakage during the non-printing movements of the nozzle. Shown in Figure 2, stringing refers to fine threads or strands of filament that form between parts of the print, while oozing is when excess material drips from the nozzle, leaving small blobs or strings behind. This issue is often caused by inadequate retraction settings or excessive nozzle temperatures that keep the filament too liquid. Under these conditions, the nozzle moves away from the printed boundary while the viscous material stretches into thin, hair-like filaments. These strands solidify mid-air, creating a web-like network across the intended gaps of the model.

Figure 2. Stringing.

2.4.2.3 Blobs and Zits

A small, raised spot or lump on the surface of the print. These are caused by either over-extrusion, low-retraction speed, or an excessively high extrusion multiplier. As a result, an overlay of a filament occurs which leads to ugly spots on its surface. Figure 3 shows the visual representation of the anomaly when the printer extrudes too much filament or when the retraction setting fails to sufficiently retract the filament between movements.

Figure 3. Blobs and Zits.

2.4.2.4 Under Extrusion/ Over Extrusion

The anomaly under extrusion happens if the printer fails to extrude enough filament, thus introducing holes or weak spots between layers and weakening the structure of a printed object. On the other hand, over-extrusion happens when more filament is being expelled than needed, thus causing a non-uniform surface as well as extra material. Both under-extrusion and over-extrusion problems develop due to poor extrusion parameters such as low flow rate, clogged nozzle, and differences in diameter of filament. Figure 4 shows the visual representation of Under Extrusion.

Figure 4. Under Extrusion.

2.4.2.5 Warping

As shown in Figure 5, parts of the print peel off the build platform as it cools, commonly curling up the corners or edges. Such defects are more frequent with materials like ABS, which contract upon cooling with appreciable

internal stresses generating the warping. Related causes include print temperatures that are excessively high, uneven cooling rates, or poor bed adhesion. This issue is mitigated by regulating temperature fluctuations.

Figure 5. Warping

2.4.2.6 Layer Shifting

Figure 6 shows layer shifting and this occurs when the print becomes distorted or skewed due to misalignment in the printed layers. This usually happens due to mechanical problems, such as loose belts, misaligned stepper motors, or insufficient bed adhesion. Visually, this misalignment creates a staircase-like effect that persists throughout the Z-axis or occur abruptly at a single point. While minor shifts result in a 'glitched' surface texture, severe displacement leads the nozzle to extrude material into open air. This loss of alignment transforms the print into a disorganized mass of filament, completely compromising the geometric shape of the part.

Figure 6. Layer Shifting.

2.4.2.7 Layer Separation/ Splitting

When the layered prints do not bond correctly with each other, it leaves gaps or splits that are visible causing this anomaly to occur. The cause of the problem includes under-extrusion, overcooling, or temperature issues with the print. Weak inter-layer adhesion due to inconsistent extrusion and the rapid cooling of the outer layers, leads to improper bonding. Figure 7 shows the visual representation of this anomaly.

Figure 7. Layer Separation.

2.4.2.8 First Layer Issue

The first layer of a 3D Print is critical in the overall print because it serves as the foundation for the remaining layers. Any mistake it incurs affects the overall print and other layers, eventually resulting in defects in the final product. These include poor adhesion to the print bed, uneven extrusion, or warping. Such problems result in an inconsistent first layer that appears rough and uneven, as shown in Figure 8, or sometimes with strands of filament that looks like "spaghetti." Although these minor issues does not significantly affect the final printing, they cause long-term problems if not resolved. The causes for these defects are tracked down to problems like improper bed leveling, incorrect temperature profiles, or insufficient adhesion. These first-layer flaws also depend on the design of the object, which becomes noticeable or hidden in the final product.

Figure 8. First Layer Issue.

2.4.2.9 Poor Bridging

This anomaly happens when the 3D Printer fails to create a smooth, stable filament bridges between two unsupported points as shown in Figure 9. The anomaly bridging refers to the process of extruding filament across an open space, and at times, the filament sags or produces thin, uneven strands. This problem usually arises when the filament is extruded too fast, cooling is inadequate or there is a lack of proper support structures for the bridge. The severity depends on material used and the settings of the printer. By optimizing print speed, adjusting cooling fan settings, and fine-tuning extrusion parameters, it helps improve the bridging quality and reduce sagging.

Figure 9. Poor Bridging.

The vulnerability to errors in 3D Printing has led to the formulation of several approaches that reduce or lessen the effects of such issues. Several studies have investigated different techniques for detecting and identifying anomalies that occur during the 3D Printing

process. In accordance with a report by [EM2024], Obico, an AI-powered 3D Printer monitoring platform, monitored over 89.8 million hours of 3D Printing, detected 1,067,608 failed prints, and saved over 23,487 kilograms of filament through its failure detection system. This demonstrates how implementing defect detection technology leads to significant efficiencies and material savings in 3D Printing processes. Similarly, [DU2018] introduced an automated surveillance system that employs machine learning techniques to facilitate real-time anomaly identification. The system uses camera data detecting problems arising during the process of printing, such as misprints or defects, thus alerting early warnings to prevent further possible production errors.

On the other hand, existing studies utilized more developed research methods such that of [SA2020], [PK2020], and [LY2019]. Their focus is not only limited to anomaly detection, but also the classification of anomalies into types. For example, [SA2020] developed a closed-loop system that uses CNNs to detect warping during the printing process. This CNN-based system feeds back to the printer to prevent warping in real-time, enhancing both the final quality and consistency of the prints. Another typical defect during 3D Printing was the focus of [PK2020]. The study made use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) together with computer vision in order to let the system detect stringing while providing corrections to improve the print quality. [LY2019] utilized the view angles of overhead cameras to monitor surface flaws and irregularities during the 3D Printing process.

From these considerations, the study focuses on real-time anomaly detection and classification. However, due to the limited dataset, the researchers select only five of the aforementioned most common types of anomalies. The constraints ensure that the study

remains manageable and feasible, resulting in effective analysis. For clarification purposes in stringing and oozing definitions, only stringing is included in the dataset and, therefore, is monitored. In summary, the researchers focus on these specific anomalies in the detection and classification task: extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

This section focuses on the fundamental concepts and ideas which form the basis of the research. It outlines the theories and concepts implemented in the study, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding the research objectives and methodology. This section focuses on the implementation of deep learning, computer vision, and 3D Printing technology, emphasizing the interrelation of these concepts with regard to addressing anomalies that occur during the 3D Printing process. These technologies work together to enable real-time analysis during printing operations. By leveraging data-driven models, the system detects irregular patterns that indicate printing defects. This integration supports a more efficient and intelligent monitoring process compared to traditional manual inspection methods. This framework thus enables the application of YOLOv10-S in visual anomaly detection, aiming to improve the accuracy and reliability of additive manufacturing. By integrating these theoretical foundations, the study bridges the gap between abstract concepts and their practical application in real-world scenarios. In particular, it highlights how advancements in artificial intelligence and computer vision directly contribute to solving persistent manufacturing challenges. Figure 10 shows a structured summary of theories, algorithms, and practical techniques behind the steps taken in this study.

Figure 10. Theoretical Framework.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence by machines, enabling them to perform tasks such as reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making. A subset of AI, Machine Learning (ML), focuses on developing algorithms that allow systems to learn and improve from data without being explicitly programmed. Within ML, Deep Learning, a more specialized branch, uses neural networks to analyze complex patterns and extract meaningful insights from large datasets. Deep Learning, primarily through Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and YOLOv10-S, plays a critical role in visual anomaly detection. While CNNs excel in extracting essential features from images and identifying patterns or anomalies, YOLOv10-S enhances this process through real-time object detection, locating and identifying flaws along the 3D Printing line. Computer Vision bridges these AI methods with

3D Printing by applying object detection and class recognition. Object detection identifies the precise positions of characteristics or flaws in printed items, while class recognition categorizes these characteristics. Visual anomaly detection integrates these techniques to identify and classify flaws in real-time without compromising precision or speed. 3D Printing, specifically through Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), serves as the application domain for these technologies. The study focuses on frequently occurring defects, such as extrusion-problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, which compromises the structural integrity of printed parts. By combining AI, ML, and computer vision, the study aims to provide actionable insights that enhance the quality of 3D-Printed outputs through real-time anomaly detection and classification.

This chapter discusses the application of computer vision and artificial intelligence in visual recognition tasks, particularly focusing on the three primary types: class recognition, which categorizes images into predefined classes; object detection, which identifies specific objects and their locations within images; and semantic segmentation, which classifies every pixel of an image. These tasks are efficiently achieved through deep learning, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Deep learning is a more specific domain of AI which specializes in complex tasks by utilizing neural networks, inspired by human brain, to improve by learning through massive amounts of data. With the ability of these neural networks to automatically extract features from images, it only proves that they are highly effective for all three recognition tasks, driving advancements for applications requiring rapid and accurate visual processing, such as anomaly detection in 3D Printing.

Moreover, the chapter also delves into how anomaly detection has increasingly become more necessary today within the domain of 3D Printing. Among the categories of 3D Printers, the study focuses on Fused Deposition Modeling, known as FDM, because of its popularity and cost-effectiveness. FDM experiences problems such as printing anomaly, which are generally in the form of spaghetti, stringing and oozing, blobs and zits, extrusion-problem, warping, layer shifting, layer separation or splitting, first layer issues, and poor bridging. With these concerns, early detection and intervention are fundamental for quality control. The You Only Look Once (YOLO) model, has consistently prioritized optimizing speed and accuracy, achieving high real-time performance without sacrificing detection quality. This capability is particularly vital in the 3D Printing industry, where timely detection of anomalies mitigate defects and production inefficiencies. The release of YOLOv10 has enhanced this balance through architectural optimizations, improving efficiency for demanding applications.

Although previous studies have experimented with various techniques and methods to monitor the 3D Printing process and detect anomalies in real-time, most of them only focus on binary classification (anomaly or no anomaly) or detecting one specific anomaly. This study seeks to overcome those limitations by the application of machine learning techniques, like YOLOv10-S. It presents a possible solution in detecting and classifying anomalies into different classes during the printing process, supporting the goal of the study of creating a smarter, more efficient 3D Printing anomaly monitoring system for a more precise and effective quality control.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This section of the study highlights the methodology used in the study of YOLOv10-S in 3D Printing anomaly detection and classification. The section tackles the extensive data collection, data preparations, analysis, and formula identification. These core components provide the necessary technical path to implement and deploy the model successfully. The methodology begins with comprehensive dataset collection to provide a strong foundation for model training, followed by structured preprocessing and analysis. This methodological framework offers a clear and organized guide for the development of the 3D printing anomaly detection system.

Data preparations consists of organizing the collected dataset, addressing data imbalance by using random under-sampling method, splitting the dataset and allocating a percentage for each phase, and augmenting the dataset to address the hypothesis. Furthermore, the researcher gave thorough attention to the preparation and preprocessing of the dataset to ensure the model captures the essential characteristics of the data. After the extensive collection and preparation of the dataset, training YOLOv10-S was then executed. The model was evaluated by various metrics and statistical tools to assess its performance quantitatively. The steps indicated in Figure 11 were followed to ensure the model was deployed with full potential and effectiveness. The insights gained from this analysis not only improve model accuracy but also provide a framework for future research in the field of anomaly detection.

Figure 11. Operational Framework.

3.1 Research Design

The study implemented and utilized an experimental research design to check whether a defect is detected and what type of anomaly is detected in a 3D Printing process. The YOLOv10-S was trained to detect defects during 3D Printing process and classify them. The experimental research design was used as it entails scientific experiments for the researchers to obtain reliable and precise results and comprehensively evaluates and analyzes the effectiveness and accurate performance of the model in anomaly detection and classification.

3.2 Dataset

The datasets for training YOLOv10-S were sourced from the reliable dataset repository Roboflow Universe [RU2024]. The datasets were crucial in training the models to yield more accurate and precise detection and classification, which were effectively used in the deployment stage. The datasets used in training the ability to detect and classify anomalies are the following: extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. Table 3 shows the characteristics the collected dataset had to make the model training possible.

Dataset	Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset
File type	JPG & TXT
Image size for Anomaly Classification	640x640 pixels
Anomaly Classification	Extrusion Problem, Spaghetti, Stringing, and Warping
Original total number of images	6,895

Table 3. Dataset Characteristics.

A total of 6,895 images were collected from Roboflow Universe [RU2024]. Specifically, 1,327 images of spaghetti were exported, 1,280 for stringing, 1,744 for under extrusion, 1,345 for over extrusion, and 1,199 for warping. These were used by the researchers to train the model in classifying what types of anomalies it detected. Initially, the dataset contained 1,000 images sourced from Roboflow Universe. However, upon further investigation, it was discovered that several images in the validation and test sets were repeated. To maintain dataset integrity, these duplicates were removed, and additional images were sourced from platforms such as Kaggle [HW2024] and Zenodo [BS2025 & CO2025] to expand the dataset.

Moreover, the datasets underwent cleaning since some of the images contain segmentation that made the annotation inconsistent. This involved deleting .txt files that contained more than five values together with their corresponding image. These steps ensured that only correctly annotated samples were retained for model training and evaluation. In addition, blurry or extremely poor-quality images found across all data splits were also removed, as they do not represent usable data. After the researchers addressed the data imbalance and segmentation issues, the final allocation of images for each classification is shown in Table 4.

Classification	Original Number of Images	Final Number of Images
Spaghetti	1,327	1,000
Stringing	1,280	1,000
Over Extrusion	1,345	1,000
Under Extrusion	1,744	1,000
Warping	1,199	1,000
Total	6,895	5,000

Table 4. Anomaly Detection and Classification Dataset Composition.

3.3 Data Collection Procedures

In this methodology section, the researchers highlighted and discussed how the dataset was prepared before the model training. Images for the five classifications of anomalies were sourced only from Roboflow Universe [RU2024]. The breakdown of each anomaly was as follows: 1,327 for spaghetti, 1,280 for stringing, 1,345 for over-extrusion, 1,744 for under-extrusion, and 1,199 for warping. The collected dataset for each classification curated from Roboflow Universe [RU2024] first underwent procedures to address data imbalance.

Each classification was allocated only 1,000 from the original number of images as the data imbalance was addressed. The dataset was separated into three phases: Training, Validation, and Testing. The researchers followed the 80:10:10 ratio for this data splitting. 80% of each classification was assigned to the Training Set, 10% to the Validation Set, and the remaining 10% to the Testing Set. The preparation of the collected dataset is crucial in executing efficient and more effective training and evaluation of the models. After the data splitting, the dataset then proceeded to the training of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying 3d Printing anomalies.

3.3.1 Addressing Dataset Imbalance

To address the data imbalance of the dataset for each classification (extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping), the researcher applied random under-sampling for each category. Since the images collected showed similar characteristics and lacked variation for each classification, the researcher reduced the number of images from the overrepresented categories, particularly for the extrusion problem. The images exhibiting these anomalies from various 3D Printing projects were preserved,

ensuring diversity across the dataset. However, upon closer review, it was discovered that some images in the validation and test sets were duplicates. To preserve the integrity of the dataset, these duplicates were eliminated, and supplementary images were obtained from public repositories, including Kaggle and Zenodo, to enhance and balance the dataset. This ensured a balanced dataset while preventing bias towards any classification, helping to improve the ability of the model to generalize across different printing conditions. The final number of images allocated for each classification is found in Table 4.

3.3.2 Data Splitting

As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, the researchers divided the collected and prepared dataset into three phases: Training, Validation, and Testing, and followed the 80:10:10 ratio. During the training phase of the model, 80% of the total dataset for each group was allocated to establish a strong foundation for the models. In this phase, the models required sufficient data to learn the patterns in each image, the relationship between pixels of the image, and the small features within the data. This section was crucial in the overall training of the models as it established the ability of the models to yield more precise detection and classification of the anomalies. Then, 10% of the dataset was allocated to the validation phase. This phase helped filter out the overfitting that happened iteratively during the training phase.

Finally, the testing phase, which utilized 10% of the dataset, was an unbiased procedure for assessing new and completely unseen data. This ensured the performance of the model was evaluated in diverse cases that were not exposed during training,

providing a reliable measure of its effectiveness in real-world scenarios. The allocated testing set ensured the model worked well and accurately outside the training phase.

The summary of the allocation is shown in Table 5.

Dataset	Percentage Allocation	Total Number of Images Allocated
Training	80%	4,000
Validation	10%	500
Testing	10%	500

Table 5. Percentage Allocation for Each Phase.

Furthermore, to show the equivalent of the percentage allocation table, Table 6 lists the number of images allocated for each classification in each phase of the model training process. The table specifies the equal number of images specific to the types of anomalies that the model is trained on. This balanced distribution ensures that no single anomaly class dominates the training process.

Dataset	Number of Images for Training	Number of Images for Validation	Number of Images for Testing
Spaghetti	800	100	100
Stringing	800	100	100
Over Extrusion	800	100	100
Under Extrusion	800	100	100
Warping	800	100	100

Table 6. Dataset Allocation for Each Phase.

To address the data imbalance of the dataset for each classification (extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping), the researcher applied random under-sampling for each category. Since the images collected showed similar characteristics and lacked variation for each classification, the researcher combined the over extrusion and under extrusion into one group and reduced the number of images from the overrepresented categories. The images exhibiting these anomalies from various 3D Printing projects were preserved, ensuring diversity across the dataset. It was observed that combining the two extrusion-related defects, under extrusion and over extrusion, resulted in an imbalance within the dataset. To address this, the researchers applied data augmentation techniques to oversample the minority class and ensure a more balanced representation across all classifications. Specifically, rotation within a range of -10° to $+10^\circ$ and the addition of noise affecting up to 1.5% of the pixels were used to synthetically increase the number of samples in the underrepresented category. As a result of this process, the final dataset was evenly distributed, with a total of 2,400 images allocated for the training set and 300 images each for the validation and test sets. The final distribution of images across all sets is detailed in Table 7.

Dataset	Number of Images for Training	Number of Images for Validation	Number of Images for Testing
Extrusion Problem	2400	300	300
Spaghetti	2400	300	300
Stringing	2400	300	300
Warping	2400	300	300

Table 7. Dataset Allocation for Each Phase After Augmentation.

3.4 Measurement and Statistical Treatment

This section of the methodology focused on evaluating the detection and classification capability of YOLOv10-S, which was essential to evaluate and analyze the overall performance of the model. The researchers used the following metrics and statistical treatments to assess the models: precision, recall, mAP50, paired t-test, and one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA). Precision, recall, and mAP50 scores were used to quantify the significant difference in the accuracy of detection and classification capabilities of YOLOv10-S. The two statistical tools, paired t-test and one-way MANOVA, were used to quantify the significant difference in the dependent and independent variables of the study. These outcomes form the basis for computing evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, and accuracy.

3.4.1 Confusion Matrix

Figure 12 displays the confusion matrix, which is helpful for evaluating model performance, identifying misclassifications, and improving predictive accuracy [BA2024]. True Positives (TP) refer to cases where the predicted label matches the actual label, while True Negatives (TN) occur when the model correctly identifies the absence of a label. In object detection tasks, they are essential for understanding how well the model distinguishes anomalies from normal samples. On the other hand, False Positives (FP) occur when the model predicts a label that does not belong to the group, while False Negatives (FN) occur when the model fails to predict a label that is actually part of the group [KR2022]. Together, these evaluation techniques provided both quantitative performance measurements and statistical validation of the effectiveness of the model.

		PREDICTED LABEL	
		NEGATIVE	POSITIVE
TRUE LABEL	NEGATIVE	TRUE NEGATIVE	FALSE POSITIVE
	POSITIVE	FALSE NEGATIVE	TRUE POSITIVE

Source: <https://rb.gy/jiht6o>

Figure 12. Confusion Matrix.

3.4.2 Precision

Another powerful measurement tool for assessing the performance of models in object detection and classification. It measures how well a model identifies true positives out of all true positives and false positives. A higher precision value indicates that the model produces fewer false positive detections, making its predictions more reliable. This metric is particularly important in applications where false alarms negatively affect system performance or decision-making. To put it simply, precision is the ratio of all the positives to true positives [HP2024]. Formula 1 is for deriving the precision rate.

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositive(TP)}{TruePositive(TP) + FalsePositive(FP)}$$

Formula 1. Precision.

3.4.3 Recall

Another measurement tool for evaluation model performance derived from the confusion matrix is recall. Recall, as shown in Formula 2, measures the number of actual positive instances that the model successfully identified [BA2024]. The ability to identify true positives from all predictions, true positives and false negatives, is measured by recall. A high recall value indicates that the model is effective in detecting relevant instances, making it particularly useful in scenarios where missing positive cases are costly. Formula 2 shows the formula of recall.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TruePositive}(TP)}{\text{TruePositive}(TP) + \text{FalseNegative}(FN)}$$

Formula 2. Recall.

3.4.4 Mean Average Precision

As shown in Formula 3, this metric is used to measure how well a model performs, especially in object detection. It makes use of confusion matrix, intersection over union (IoU), recall, and precision [AN2023]. The mAP is calculated through finding the average precision (AP) for each object class and then averaging it over the number of all the classes [SD2022]. It is widely used and crucial as it gives a combined measure that is easy to read and understand, through which object detection performances of the models are assessed and compared.

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^{k=n} AP_k$$

AP_k = the Average Precision of class

n = the number of classes

Formula 3. Mean Average Precision.

Its comparison is in the aspect where, instead of using recall and precision alone, it considers each aspect and creates a balanced measure to achieve more accurate assessment. Specifically, the study utilized two variations of mAP namely: mAP50 and mAP50-95. These are common metrics used to evaluate the accuracy of object detectors. mAP50 refers to the Mean Average Precision calculated at an intersection over union (IoU) threshold of 0.5, while mAP50-95 is the average mAP calculated across IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95.

A high mAP indicates that the model is both sensitive in terms of detecting anomalies and precise about where it is avoiding false alarms, which are important in keeping quality control when monitoring systems work in real-time. A score of one indicates that the object detection model is perfectly working, which means that it is accurate. On the other hand, having low mAP indicates that the system does not detect anomalies or gives no-anomaly outputs as defects [AN2023]. However, in this study, only mAP50 score was used to evaluate the performance of the model.

Although mAP50-95 provides a more detailed evaluation by gradually increasing the IoU threshold, it often leads to lower scores. This is because higher

thresholds are stricter and penalize the model for small localization mistakes. The decision was based on its common usage in similar custom object detection tasks, where an IoU threshold of 0.5 is frequently adopted due to its balance between strictness and practicality. Results in the referenced study showed that as the IoU threshold increases, the measured accuracy of the model tends to change accordingly across different evaluation scenarios [PK2020].

3.4.5 F1 Score

It is a widely used evaluation metric in classification and object detection tasks, especially when balancing precision and recall is critical [KR2022]. It is defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, calculated as shown in Formula 4. This metric becomes particularly useful in situations where there is an imbalance between classes or when both false positives and false negatives carry significant consequences [KR2022]. In object detection, F1 Score helps identify how well the model detects relevant objects while minimizing incorrect detections.

$$F1 = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Formula 4. F1 Score.

One of the most common uses of the F1 Score is to determine the optimal confidence threshold for an object detection model. As the confidence threshold is

adjusted, precision typically increases while recall decreases, and vice versa. The F1 Score balances this trade-off and reaches its highest value at the point where the two metrics are most harmonized [SJ2025]. This peak indicates a confidence level where neither false positives nor false negatives disproportionately affect the performance of the model. This makes it an effective tool for selecting the threshold at which the model performs most reliably across both detection correctness and completeness.

3.4.6 Paired T-Test

The means of two measurements made from the same person, item, or related units are compared using the Paired T-test. The test aims to find statistical evidence that the mean difference between paired observations deviates considerably from zero [KS2024]. Formula 5 shows the Paired T-test. In the context of this research study, the Paired T-Test was used to evaluate hypothesis 1 and 2. In hypothesis 1, the tool measured the significant difference between the training and validation loss for box, class, and distribution focal loss. While in hypothesis 2, the tool was used to measure the significant difference in the performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, mAP50, and mAP50-95) of YOLOv10-S when using RGB versus grayscale images for detecting and classifying anomalies.

$$t = \frac{\Sigma d}{\sqrt{n(\Sigma d^2) - \frac{(\Sigma d)^2}{(n-1)}}$$

Formula 5. Paired T-Test.

3.4.7 One-Way Multivariate Analysis Variance (MANOVA)

To determine whether independent groups differ on more than one continuous dependent variable, one-way multivariate analysis of variance, or one-way MANOVA, as given in Formula 6, is used. It differs from a one-way MANOVA, which only measures one dependent variable [LS2024]. In the context of this study, one-way MANOVA was utilized to assess the significant differences in the precision, recall, and mAP50 score of the YOLOv10-S model when classifying various detected anomalies, specifically: extrusion problems, spaghetti stringing, and warping.

$$\Lambda = \frac{|E|}{|H + E|}$$

Formula 6. One-Way MANOVA.

3.5 Data Analysis and Interpretation

In this section of the study, the researcher highlights the analysis and interpretation of the various datasets collected, which are used to train the detection and classification models. The analysis focuses on determining how well the model detects anomalies and classifies them into their respective categories. This includes examining performance metrics and observed patterns derived from the experimental results.

The dataset analysis begins by comparing the performance of each model based on the following metrics: precision, recall, and mAP50, using the relevant techniques. The researchers

use statistical methods like the paired t-test and one-way MANOVA to find significant differences between variables based on p-values. When the p-value between the means of the precision, recall, and mAP50 metrics for the variables is larger than 0.05, it suggests that the performance of one variable differs significantly from another. The interpretation adds information regarding whether the performance of the models is efficient and effective, and whether the models are appropriate for use in practical applications.

3.6 Confidence Threshold Selection

In object detection, a confidence threshold determines the minimum score a detection needs to have, to be considered valid. This score is a probability estimate from the model that a detected object belongs to a certain class. By choosing the right threshold is critical since if the threshold is too low, it produces many false positives, and if it is too high, it misses valid detections.

To balance this trade-off, precision and recall are commonly used evaluation metrics. Precision measures how many of the detected anomalies are correct, while recall measures how many actual anomalies were successfully detected. A well-chosen confidence threshold seeks to balance these two. However, these metrics often have an inverse relationship wherein increasing one typically reduces the other. Therefore, the F1-score, the harmonic mean of precision and recall, is used as a single metric to evaluate this balance [UL2024; EA2025].

To identify the most appropriate threshold for the anomaly detection model of this study, multiple confidence thresholds ranging from 0.10 to 0.90, in increments of 0.05, were

tested. The evaluation was conducted on both the validation set and test set, with performance metrics recorded at each threshold. The objective was to select the threshold that demonstrated a consistent and optimal trade-off between precision and recall across both datasets, while also considering its practical performance during real-time deployment.

3.7 Ethical and Privacy Considerations

Given that the dataset utilized is publicly available through repositories such as Roboflow Universe [RU2024], Kaggle [HW2024], and Zenodo [BS2025 & CO2025], ethical considerations regarding the acquisition and utilization of the dataset are minimal. The dataset is strictly employed for research purposes, encompassing training, validation, and testing of the model, with no intentions of personal or political use. As the dataset comprises solely images of the 3D Printing process, there is no exposure of personal identification to the public. Furthermore, the dataset does not originate from private organizations or groups, thereby mitigating any issues related to consent and privacy.

The researchers utilize only what is publicly available to train the models to avoid disputes related to intellectual property issues. The researchers strictly follow these measures to prevent mishaps and ethical problems with regard to intellectual property as the study develops. They also utilized various API and other tools that helped in accomplishing this research project. These tools are recognized with each purpose served, what activities were made under the given tool, the results of the said activity, and the location where the results were placed. The following tools were recognized used in developing and writing this thesis project: ChatGPT, Gemini, and Robloflow. See Appendix E for the detailed table of the tools.

3.8 Model Deployment

In the deployment phase, the researcher integrates the YOLOv10-S model into a software platform designed to facilitate multiple functionalities for effective anomaly detection during 3D Printing. The software encompasses three fundamental features: detection in images, detection in videos, and real-time detection. For image and video detections, users upload files, which the software processes to highlight detected anomalies directly on the screen, accompanied by bounding boxes and pertinent details.

Real-time detection capabilities are supported by a connected camera that monitors the 3D Printing process in real-time. For optimal monitoring, it is imperative that the camera is positioned to provide an unobstructed view of the print area, preferably from a lateral or side angle. Additionally, a light source positioned alongside the camera to ensure consistent and adequate illumination of the print area, thereby aiding the model in maintaining high detection accuracy. While the software is equipped for real-time monitoring during 3D Printing, actual deployment on a live printer was not conducted due to practical constraints. Instead, the performance of the model was assessed utilizing pre-recorded videos and images of 3D Prints with known defects. The software was executed on a mid-range ASUS laptop, featuring an Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-11400H CPU, an NVIDIA RTX 3050 GPU with 4 GB of VRAM, and 16 GB of RAM on a Windows 11 operating system. This setup allowed the researchers to simulate real-time processing and evaluate the responsiveness of the model under typical operating conditions. This configuration aligns with that employed in the study by [HW2024], which indicated that such hardware is adequate for achieving high detection accuracy and speed, satisfying the requirements for near real-time defect detection.

In conclusion, this section of the study delineated a comprehensive methodology outlining the development of a 3D Printing anomaly detection and classification system employing the YOLOv10-S model. The procedure began with the creation of an operational framework that laid out the whole workflow, from data collection and preparation to model training, evaluation, and final deployment. The experimental research design used in this study enabled a systematic exploration of the ability of the model to reliably detect and categorize numerous 3D Printing irregularities, allowing for an objective evaluation of the performance of the model under controlled conditions.

Furthermore, this section detailed the process of gathering image datasets from the Roboflow Universe repository, focusing on four key types of 3D Printing anomalies: extrusion problem (under extrusion and over extrusion), spaghetti, stringing, and warping. To ensure a balanced dataset, random under-sampling was applied, followed by an 80:10:10 split for training, validation, and testing. This careful preparation was essential to developing a model capable of generalizing across varied print scenarios. To rigorously evaluate the detection and classification performance of the model, standard performance metrics such as precision, recall, and mAP50 were employed. These metrics provided quantitative insights into the effectiveness of the model, which were further interpreted using statistical tools including the paired t-test and one-way MANOVA. These statistical treatments allowed the researchers to identify any significant differences or patterns in the outputs across different conditions and datasets of the model. Additionally, a confidence threshold evaluation was conducted to determine the most suitable cutoff for real-time detection, balancing statistical performance with practical deployment.

Lastly, ethical implications were addressed, underscoring that all datasets utilized were publicly accessible and devoid of personally identifiable information. The datasets were strictly employed for research purposes only, including model training, validation, and testing, with no personal, commercial, or political intent. Since the data consisted solely of images related to the 3D printing process and did not originate from private organizations, concerns regarding consent, privacy, and data ownership were minimized. This adherence to ethical guidelines ensured that the research maintained compliance and avoided potential conflicts related to data privacy or intellectual property. In addition, only publicly available tools and APIs were utilized during the development and documentation of the study, with proper acknowledgment provided for each tool used, including ChatGPT, Gemini, and Roboflow, as detailed in Appendix E. The model was subsequently integrated into a multifunctional detection software capable of processing images, videos, and real-time input via a camera, with the acknowledgment that real-time deployment on an active 3D Printer was simulated rather than physically executed due to practical constraints.

CHAPTER IV

SOLUTION

To address the objectives of this research study, which focuses on detecting and classifying 3D Printing failures, the researchers developed a system that integrates the YOLOv10-S machine learning model to streamline the process. This chapter presents the framework and functionalities of the developed system through various representations, such as the system decomposition chart, user interface design, potential deployment environments, and the overall requirements that enabled the researchers to bring the system to life. The goal of this user-friendly solution is to deliver the capabilities of the model through an intuitive and accessible platform. This allows users to monitor their printing process in real-time and receive recommendations when an anomaly is detected, regardless of their technical background. Additionally, the chapter also covers the functionalities of the system to provide users with a clear understanding of how it works.

4.1 System Decomposition Chart

Additive manufacturing, often known as 3D printing, has changed traditional manufacturing methods by allowing for the layer-by-layer manufacture of physical products directly from digital models. While this technique has benefits such as quick prototyping and design freedom, it is nonetheless susceptible to issues such as extrusion problems, spaghetti-like filament deposition, stringing, and warping. To address these problems, the researchers

created a real-time detection and classification system based on the YOLOv10-S machine learning model, which is intended to automatically recognize and classify abnormalities throughout the printing process, improving overall reliability.

Figure 13 shows the overall decomposition chart of the system, that visually represents the functionalities of the system. The system is divided into three main sections, each playing a significant role in its operation. The data source includes live camera feed, uploaded images or videos, and user actions such as saving images or generating log results. These serve as the primary inputs that the system receives. The system functions section handles the core operations of the software. This includes capturing input data, detecting and classifying anomalies using the YOLOv10-S model, and generating detection reports containing anomaly details such as type, timestamp, confidence score, and recommended corrective actions.

Figure 13. System Decomposition Chart.

The system manages the continuous flow of information between components to maintain uninterrupted real-time data processing. Integrated decision-support features enable the identification of errors alongside recommended corrective actions for the user. Coordinated interaction among components supports timely responses to detected anomalies during both the printing process and the evaluation of finished 3D printed products. This structured coordination enhances overall system reliability during operation.

The workflow design emphasizes efficiency and adaptability, supporting use across diverse 3D printing environments. The output section delivers results directly to the user through a live camera feed with bounding boxes highlighting detected anomalies. Real-time visual and auditory alerts provide immediate feedback during printing activities. Detailed anomaly analytics and training results further illustrate the performance of the model based on the complete training process.

4.1.1 Data Acquisition

The process of acquiring data is one of the most important components of a developed system, as it provides raw input necessary for subsequent processes, particularly in anomaly detection and classification, and ultimately determines the quality of the final results. To ensure adaptability across different user requirements, the system is designed to support multiple modes of data input, namely live camera feeds, uploaded images, and uploaded videos. These inputs are captured through the application interface and automatically prepared for analysis through resolution alignment and frame consistency. This design allows the system to function both in live monitoring scenarios and for analyzing previously recorded sessions.

The live monitoring functions as the primary data acquisition method for real-time 3D printing process monitoring. A connected camera captures continuous frames of the print bed throughout operation. The YOLOv10-S model processes these frames immediately, allowing for instant detection of anomalies including extrusion irregularities, spaghetti formation, stringing, and warping. For uploaded images, the user is allowed to manually upload one or images of currently in progress or finished 3D prints. The model then begins processing the image data, systematically examining each uploaded file for visual indicators of potential printing anomalies. The system also supports the use of recorded videos of ongoing 3D printing process or completed prints as an input for detecting anomalies. In contrast to image uploads, video analysis documents about how prints progress allowing for detection and classification of anomalies throughout the printing process

4.1.2 Anomaly Detection and Classification

Once data acquisition is completed, the captured inputs undergo anomaly detection and classification. This forms the primary functionalities of the system. By using the YOLOv10-S, the system first locates where the potential issues are in the input data and then applies its classification capabilities accordingly by assigning labels to categorize the detected anomaly. The detection process identifies precisely where the defects occur, on the other hand classification determines what type of problem each one represents. Both processes work together in transforming the raw data into structured, meaningful information that enables users to make better decisions regarding their prints.

The object detection process enables the identification of areas in the input data that contains anomalies. The YOLOv10-S model then identifies regions of interest on the print bed or within loaded images and videos, through the help of the bounding box predictions. This spatial identification not only detects the anomalies but localizes them in the visual data. After the system identifies where anomalies are located, it proceeds to determine type of anomaly each one actually represents. YOLOv10-S examines each detected area and assigns it to a specific label like extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, or warping. This classification process adds meaningful context to what the system found, turning basic detection results into useful information.

4.1.3 Anomaly Analytics

After going through the process of acquiring data from the user to be analyzed, the system provides results and output. The range of outputs includes bounding boxes in the detected images, videos, and live feed, as well as detailed reports of the summarized detection logs. The system produces various types of outputs that inform the user about the detailed analytics of what the model detects and classifies. The user sees the anomalies detected and classified, the confidence level of the model, and the probable fixes for the identified anomalies.

As part of object detection and classification, locating anomalies in analyzed images, videos, and live feeds is crucial to identify which section of the media represents a defect in 3D printing. One of the outputs of the system after data acquisition and processing is the media marked with bounding boxes, as shown in Figure 14. These bounding boxes, together with the label assignment, are overlaid on

images, videos, or frames in the real-time feeds to clearly indicate the location of the detected anomaly.

Figure 14. Anomaly Bounding Box.

When the Start Monitoring button is clicked, the live session begins on the left side of the page. Once the model detects an anomaly during the use of the real-time detection, the system displays both a visual and an audio alert. The visual alert is presented through a modal that pops out of the screen of the user, advising the user to immediately pause the printer to avoid further printing issues and waste of material. The audio alert ensures the attention of the user whenever the user is occupied with other tasks. The combination of visual and audio cues not only ensures the timely response of the user but also minimizes the potential waste of resources and maintains the overall quality of the 3D printed product by avoiding the escalation of the defect.

The system also provides detailed anomaly information, including the number of instances detected, the confidence score of each anomaly, and actionable recommendations for resolving issues efficiently. These guides the users in identifying the cause of the problem and taking corrective measures promptly. After successful detection, the system also generates a comprehensive anomaly report by having the user click the Log Results and Save Report buttons. This report summarizes the total and types of anomalies detected, their confidence scores, and offers in-depth analyses and practical solutions. By combining real-time alerts, informative details, and comprehensive reports, the system overall provides users with clear insights that support informed decisions and effective actions in addressing the detected anomalies.

4.2 Development Tools

The 3D Printing technology is a rapidly pacing field which requires more accurate detection and classification of failures to increase the profitability of the products. To address the issue of manual defect detection, a time-consuming process that leads to resource waste, the researchers developed this platform using various technologies and development tools to enable a faster development process. The following are the technologies and development tools that the researchers used to make the development of this system possible:

4.2.1 Jupyter Notebook

It is a foundational web application for creating and sharing computational documents. It provides a straightforward, document-focused experience that is simple

and efficient. Jupyter Notebook is commonly used by programmers, data scientists, and students to document and showcase coding workflows, or to experiment with code in an interactive environment. In this study, the researchers used Jupyter Notebook to experiment with the fine-tuning of the model making it easier to train and experiment with the YOLOv10s model.

4.2.2 Google Colab

It is a cloud-based Jupyter Notebook service that requires no installation and offers free access to computing resources such as GPUs and TPUs. It is particularly well-suited for machine learning, data science, and educational purposes. The researchers used this cloud-based technology to access computing resources for faster and more efficient model training. By leveraging these high-end resources, the researchers were able to reduce training times from days to just hours.

4.2.3 Programming Language

To make the system possible, the researchers used the programming language Python to integrate the YOLOv10s model in developing a system that detects and classifies 3D Printing anomalies. Cross-platform of Python support enables easier system maintenance and scalability. Python is the primary programming language used for developing the real-time anomaly detection system. It offers extensive libraries and frameworks for machine learning and data processing, such as TensorFlow, Keras, and OpenCV, which are essential for implementing the YOLOv10-S model and supporting real-time processing.

4.2.4 User Interface (UI) Design

In creating the solution that allows interactive buttons and graphics in detecting 3D Printing anomalies and that addresses the objectives of this study, the researchers opted to use PyQT in creating the design of the system. PyQT is employed to develop the graphical user interface (GUI) for the real-time detection system. It is a set of Python bindings for the Qt application framework, which allows for the creation of cross-platform desktop applications.

4.2.5 Ultralytics

The core "engine" for the anomaly detection system is Ultralytics. It is the software framework that provides all the necessary functions to build, configure, and execute the YOLOv10 object detection model. In this study, it was essential for loading the base model, training it on the custom 3D printing anomaly dataset of the researchers, and then running that trained model to perform real-time inference. This allowed the system to successfully find and classify anomalies like "Spaghetti" and "Warping" from images, videos, and the live camera feed.

4.2.6 OpenCV

To act as the "eyes" and "hands" of the application, the researchers used OpenCV. It was essential for capturing individual frames from the live camera feed and processing all visual inputs (including uploaded images and videos) to be analyzed by the YOLO model. OpenCV also handled basic image preprocessing tasks to ensure consistent input quality before inference. Furthermore, it was used to render the visual

alerts back to the user, which involved drawing the final bounding boxes and anomaly labels directly onto the image frames to show where the defect was located.

4.2.7 PyTorch

An open-source machine learning framework, PyTorch, was used for its flexibility in research and development. It provides the necessary tools for building and training deep learning models. In this study, PyTorch was used as a core framework for managing the YOLOv10 model, providing functions for loading, fine-tuning, and running the anomaly detection model.

4.2.8 PyQT

To create the graphical user interface (GUI), the researchers used PyQT. This is a set of Python bindings for the Qt application framework, which allows creation of cross-platform desktop applications. The researchers opted to use PyQT to create the entire design of the system. It was employed to develop all the interactive buttons, graphics, and the overall user interface for the real-time anomaly detection software.

4.3 User Interface

The system developed for this study is designed to allow easy navigation of functionalities, even for users with limited technological background. Alternatively, the user of the system also has the option to upload an image or video of both the printing process and printed product for analysis. The figures in the following sections visually present the key functionalities of the system that address the objectives of this research study.

In Figure 15, the splash page serves as the initial landing screen of the anomaly detection system. It provides a simple layout with a bold header labeled “Xplor3D” followed by a tagline and a short description that indicates the application functionality in real-time 3D Printing anomaly monitoring using YOLOv10s. The interface includes a white-colored button labeled "Start Exploring," which initiates the system. The splash page is the starting point that presents essential information that gives the user a gist of what the application is.

Figure 15. Splash Screen.

As the user clicked the “Start Exploring” button in the splash screen, the application transitions to an introductory video, as seen in Figure 16. The video serves as brief orientation for the user, describing the different types and the physical features of the anomalies that the system is capable of detecting. It also includes a “Skip Intro” button that allows the user to skip the video and proceed to the home page of the application. This design choice accommodates

both first-time users who need guidance and experienced users who prefer immediate access to the system. The goal of this feature is to help the user familiarize and understand how the application identifies and classifies these anomalies in real-time.

Figure 16. Introduction Video.

As soon as the introduction video finishes or the “Skip Intro” option has been selected, the home page of the system is displayed. This page functions as the central operational environment of the application. It serves as the workspace where inputs are prepared, detection routines are triggered, and analytical processes are managed in the background. Interface elements are designed to guide users efficiently while minimizing cognitive load. The design of this section supports a structured workflow that enables smooth transitions between stages of anomaly detection, classification, and analysis within the system.

4.3.1 Data Acquisition

This process in the system is visually represented through the user interface shown in Figure 17, which allows the user to input various media to access the different features of the system. On the right, the interface offers clearly labeled buttons for live monitoring and file uploads, allowing users to easily switch between data input modes. By clicking the Start Monitoring button, the live camera feed is turned on, enabling continuous real-time monitoring of the 3D printing process.

Figure 17. Home Page.

This live data is immediately analyzed by the YOLOv10-S model for any anomalies in the 3D printed process or product. Alternatively, users have the option to choose to upload static images or videos of current or completed prints using the respective buttons, “Detect from Image(s)” and “Detect from Video.” These options allow the system to process captured media for anomaly detection.

In Figure 18, upon clicking the “Start Monitoring”, the live monitoring functions starts which is the primary data acquisition method for real-time 3D printing process monitoring. A connected camera captures continuous frames of the 3D printing process, or the 3D printed product. The model, YOLOv10-S, then processes the frames immediately, allowing for instant detection of anomalies. With constant visual monitoring, users identify anomalies as they occur during the printing process, potentially saving both time and materials by catching failures as early as possible. The interface buttons maintain the same functions and are reusable for further detections. If the user wishes to continue monitoring, the Resume Monitoring button is clicked, while the Stop Monitoring button allows them to end the live session entirely.

Figure 18. Live Camera Feed.

Another type of media that the system detects anomalies to is images and videos. As seen in Figure 17, the Upload Buttons allow users to upload various types of media to be detected. In Figure 19, this feature of the application allows either a single photo or multiple photos in one session. When multiple photos are uploaded, navigation buttons labeled as next and previous symbol appear on the left side of the page, enabling the user to move through the uploaded images.

Figure 19. Uploaded Images.

Aside from the detect from image(s), the button “Detect from Video” allows users to input video media to be detected. The system also supports videos of printing process uploaded and to be process for detection and classification. As the user click the button “Detect from Video”, Figure 20 represents where the user is directed to

upload videos. The same way images are uploaded, the user navigates videos they want to be detected and upload them in the system. This proves particularly useful when ongoing live monitoring is no longer feasible, as it provides critical feedback about both defect occurrence during printing and final product quality analysis.

Figure 20. Uploaded Video.

Bachelor of Science in
COMPUTER
SCIENCE

4.3.2 Anomaly Analytics

After starting the live camera feed or uploading various media such as images or videos, the model YOLOv10-S process the media or the live printing process. The model places bounding box automatically on the area highlights any area of the photo, videos, or live process identified where the anomaly is detected which helps in locating the anomaly in the uploaded photo. Upon localizing the detected anomaly, the model

also identifies what type of anomaly was detected in the media. The color of the bounding box also depends on the type of anomaly such as extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, or warping. In Figure 21, the left side of the Home Page is where the anomaly detection and classification are executed, in which the anomaly bounding box is represented and plotted. The interface buttons retain their standard functions and remain reusable for further detections, providing users with flexibility in monitoring images.

Figure 21. Anomaly Bounding Box.

In Figure 22, the system interface displays the output upon detecting an anomaly during a live monitoring session. When the model identifies an issue, in this case, a spaghetti formation, the system immediately triggers both visual and audio

alerts to notify the user. A pop-up modal appears on the screen, advising the user to pause the 3D printer to prevent further errors and material waste, while an audio alert reinforces immediate attention.

Figure 22. Visual and Audio Anomaly Alert.

The user closes the modal and clicks "Continue Monitoring" in case the detection made was not too big of an anomaly on the side of the user. The user also has the option to totally stop the current live session by clicking the "Stop Monitoring" button. This integrated alert mechanism ensures that users promptly respond to anomalies, thereby maintaining print quality.

As seen in Figure 23, the right panel of the system interface presents the detailed output generated after detecting an extrusion problem anomaly during a monitoring

session. This section provides comprehensive anomaly details, including the specific anomaly type, the frame where it was detected, and the confidence level indicating the certainty detection of the model. Below these details, the system generates context-specific suggestions to assist the user in addressing the issue effectively. In this instance, the system recommends checking the filament diameter, print temperature, and extrusion multiplier to resolve the extrusion problem. These detailed insights enable users to interpret detection results quickly and apply corrective actions with precision.

Figure 23. Anomaly Details.

In Figure 24, the "Log Results" modal appears, which records the anomalies detected in the uploaded file, which corresponds to the Anomaly Report. The modal displays once the "Log Results" button is clicked, provided that the model actively

detects an anomaly. Within this modal, the application presents the type of anomaly currently detected, together with a detailed description of its characteristics and an explanation of the possible causes of its occurrence. The information displayed helps the user understand not only what anomaly is present, but also why it emerged. In addition, the application also presents a set of recommendations that guide the user on how to address or correct the issue, ensuring that detection results lead to meaningful actions. For documentation and analysis purposes, the application stores the anomaly report locally when the user chooses to save it, allowing the results to remain available for future review, progress tracking, or sharing with other stakeholders. With the combined information about anomaly details, explanations, and actionable recommendations, this modal helps the user to monitor more effectively and be informed of what actions to take to address the anomalies detected by the model.

Figure 24. Anomaly Report.

When using the live camera feature, the user also be notified when the environment or the subject being monitored is too bright or too dark. In the home page of the application, a warning sign appears once this condition is met. As seen in Figure 25, the warning sign appears on the upper part of the right section on the home page. This guides the user to adjust the lighting properly, making it easier to monitor the print clearly.

Figure 25. Brightness Alert.

As seen in Figure 26, it shows the system menu, which allows users to navigate to other pages. It includes links to the home, model, training results, and manual pages, giving users the flexibility to explore different parts of the system. It provides quick access to the main features, helping users move smoothly through the application.

Figure 26. Menu.

In Figure 27, it shows the page where the description of the model YOLOv10 in the program is found. This page allows every user to understand the key factors of YOLOv10 to make the program come to life as this page highlights and describes the YOLOv10 architecture and on what environment it is applied. The page helps the user understand and know well the architecture behind the program it uses. The page also highlights the advantages of using YOLOv10 in detecting anomalies in the 3D Printing process. It also highlights the capability of the YOLOv10 to deliver highly accurate, real-time anomaly detection while maintaining minimal latency, even in complex printing conditions. Furthermore, the page helps the user as an educational reference for those interested in learning how computer vision technology, such as YOLOv10, is integrated into real-world manufacturing solutions.

Figure 27. Model Page.

The training results page which is what Figure 28 visualizes is a part of the program that describes the findings of the researchers during the training of the model YOLOv10-S in

detecting and classifying anomalies. This page consists of graphs that visualize the results of the study that answer the statements of the problem. The researchers highlighted here the observed significance of the performance of the model when exposed to various variables. This page helps describe the capabilities of the YOLOv10-S model implemented in the program in detecting anomalies.

Figure 28. Training Results Page.

As seen in Figure 29, the Users' Manual page is a page dedicated to informing and instructing the user on how to navigate and use the functionality of the system. On this page, users are able to familiarize themselves with the various features and tools available. The User Manual also provides recommendations for optimal performance, such as proper lighting, hardware setup, and camera distance. It contains images of other pages, accompanied by clear instructions about the functions available on each, in which the user access by scrolling through the page. This is to ensure that users are comfortable with the interface and understand the

purpose of each button and feature. Additionally, step-by-step guides are included to help users perform common tasks with ease and confidence.

Figure 29. User Manual Page.

4.4 Testing Components

To ensure that modules of Xplor3D are functioning according to its requirements, four various testing activities were executed. Since the system combines machine learning-based detection, specifically YOLOv10s, image and video processing, and an interactive PyQt5 interface, a layered testing approach was necessary to validate the system from the smallest components to the complete operational workflow. This approach allowed the researchers to systematically identify and address potential errors at each stage of development before moving on to more complex interactions. The section of this study presents the discussions of the four testing components: Unit Testing, Integration Testing, Validation

Testing, and Acceptance Testing. Each test was guided by the decomposition charts, module definitions, and functionality designs of the system established during development.

4.4.1 Unit Testing

Each section in the source code of the system identified to be salient features was independently tested to ensure that they are working properly. Every component in the system such as the YOLOv10s loader, buttons on each detection feature, camera handler, frame pre-processing functions for live and video upload feature, how the model detect and classify the anomaly, UI controls, and the logging mechanism, was tested independently to verify proper behavior. User interface components, such as buttons, stacked views, navigation elements, dialogs, and sliders, were tested independently to validate signal connections, visibility toggles, and responsiveness. File handling for both images and videos was also exercised using sample media to ensure correct loading and conversion into the appropriate display formats.

The anomaly detection module was tested using controlled and mock inputs to verify confidence thresholding, bounding-box extraction, anomaly labeling, and rendering accuracy. UI elements such as buttons, navigation panels, stacked widgets, dialogs, and image/video viewers were individually tested to confirm signal connections, visibility toggling, and responsiveness. These tests ensured that each module functioned according to specifications before combining them into larger workflows. Regression tests confirmed updates did not affect performance. Any issues identified during these tests were documented and addressed to maintain overall system reliability.

4.4.2 Integration Testing

To check the interconnectivity of each module to the other, integration testing was done to ensure that they operated cohesively as a functional system. After each unit was confirmed working, modules were progressively linked, for example, integrating the camera module with the YOLO detection model, followed by connecting detection outputs to the PyQt5 interface elements. This testing verified that live camera frames were correctly passed into the detection engine, that detected anomalies triggered appropriate UI responses, and that the system correctly handled transitions between monitoring, pausing, stopping, and replaying. Integration testing also examined the workflow of uploaded images and videos, confirming that detection overlays, image navigation buttons, and video playback controls worked synchronously. Special attention was given to timing and interaction issues, such as processing delays, UI freezes, and repeated switching between screens. By validating module interactions, integration testing confirmed that the system behaved reliably in multi-component scenarios.

4.4.3 Validation Testing

This testing phase evaluated the entire system against its intended purpose, to detect 3D printing anomalies accurately and assist users with actionable feedback. This phase ensured that the final application met the functional requirements identified during design, including real-time monitoring, anomaly visualization, detection accuracy, and usability. The system was tested using real 3D printer videos, images, and live camera feeds to validate performance under realistic conditions. Anomalies

such as spaghetti formation, extrusion problems, stringing, and warping were tested to confirm that the model identified them at the expected confidence levels. The responsiveness of UI elements, logging behavior, suggestion generation, and resource loading in the deployed application were also evaluated. Validation testing demonstrated whether the system met the target metrics established during developments such as detection responsiveness, clarity of overlays, and system stability during prolonged monitoring sessions. Only after confirming that the system behaved correctly across all intended scenarios was it deemed ready for user evaluation.

4.4.4 Acceptance Testing

As the final stage of evaluation, Acceptance Testing was executed during the exposition to determine whether the 3D Printing Anomaly Detection System fully satisfied user expectations in terms of reliability, usability, and overall functionality. The attendees were invited to interact with the system directly and were able to comprehensively analyze, explore, and discuss the system. To gather feedback efficiently, a structured questionnaire was distributed through Google Forms, where respondents accessed it by scanning a QR code prominently presented by the researchers in each respective booth, allowing respondents to evaluate the system immediately after trying its features. A total of 67 participants actively took part in the assessment, which provides the researchers with a comprehensive and detailed set of responses reflecting the performance of the model under real user conditions. The questionnaire consisted of multiple criteria grounded in software quality principles, covering aspects such as accuracy of outputs, consistency of data handling, clarity of

system documentation, user control mechanisms, structural organization of the interface, system independence, and internal monitoring capabilities. A total of 45 questions were provided in the Google Forms, where the criterion was rated on a five-point scale, with higher scores indicating stronger agreement or satisfaction. Mean scores were then computed for each item and interpreted using the standard rating ranges. Table 8 shows the respective range of each of the remarks that describe the mean score of each criterion.

Mean Score	Remarks
4.21 – 5.00	Very Good
3.41 – 4.20	Good
2.61 – 3.40	Average
1.81 – 2.60	Poor
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor

Table 8. Results Interpretation.

The results of the survey show that the system received consistently high evaluations, with all criteria falling within either the “Very Good” (4.21–5.00) or “Good” (3.41–4.20) interpretation ranges. Table 9 shows the highest and lowest criteria with their respective mean score and remarks. Among all evaluated attributes, Data Commonality received the highest mean score, indicating that users strongly agreed that the system presents and manages data in a consistent, organized, and predictable manner. This reflects the stable formatting of recognition outputs, logs, and data structures, which supports clarity and reduces confusion during operation.

Highest Criteria	Mean Score	Remarks	Lowest Criteria	Mean Score	Remarks
Data Commonality	4.45	Very Good	Hardware Independence	4.18	Good
Self-Documentation	4.43	Very Good	Instrumentation	4.18	Good
Structural Simplicity	4.43	Very Good	Error Tolerance	4.22	Very Good
Software System Independence	4.43	Very Good			

Table 9. Highest and Lowest Criteria.

Closely behind is a group of three criteria, self-documentation, structural simplicity, and software system independence, each earning an identical average, all of which fall within the “Very Good” range. These high ratings demonstrate that the system provides clear interface guidance, maintains an intuitive and uncluttered structural design, and performs reliably across different devices and operating environments. Users found the labeling, instructions, and layout easy to follow, and the consistent performance of the system across various hardware setups reinforces its software independence.

The lowest three criteria, hardware independence, instrumentation, and error tolerance, remain positive as the three criteria are still within the "Good" range, but indicate areas where improvements lead to the enhancement of the overall system performance. Hardware independence reflects the dependence of the system on external devices, such as cameras, whose responsiveness varies across demonstrations. This variability directly affects the consistency and stability of detection results across

different setups, influencing how reliably the system identifies and labels anomalies under varying conditions. Instrumentation reflects the current level of the system in internal monitoring and feedback delivery, which includes occasional delays in processing or alert generation. Error tolerance reflects how the system handles mistakes, unexpected inputs, or transitions between operational modes, showing that certain interactions require smoother execution.

Despite these areas for refinement, the overall results reflect strong user satisfaction. The highest-scoring qualities, data consistency, clarity of documentation, structural simplicity, and software independence of the system show that users found the application intuitive, stable, and well-designed. The lower-scoring aspects, such as hardware compatibility and internal monitoring responsiveness, provide clear direction for future enhancements without detracting from the reliability, usability, and effectiveness of the system.

Overall, the acceptance testing was able to identify whether the system is ready to be used in a real-life setting. The results show that real user conditions were met properly as respondents identified that the system is intuitive to people and was easy to follow and understand. The testing highlighted both strengths and limitations of the system under realistic user and operational conditions. However, some aspects are not at their highest performance yet still demonstrate functionality that meets user expectations. These areas provide clear opportunities for refinement, particularly in ensuring consistent hardware compatibility, enhancing internal monitoring responsiveness, and strengthening the tolerance of the system for operational errors.

This chapter, It presented the development and design of a real-time anomaly detection system for Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) 3D Printing, which utilizes the YOLOv10-S deep learning model. The system was developed to address the ongoing challenges of quality assurance in 3D Printing, such as extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. The researchers designed a user-friendly, interactive interface that enables users, regardless of technical expertise, to detect and classify 3D Printing anomalies through live monitoring or uploaded media. The system also provides real-time feedback, allowing users to immediately identify and correct printing errors.

The chapter discussed the overall framework of the system, including a decomposition chart highlighting the main sections: data acquisition, anomaly detection and classification, and anomaly analytics. Key development tools included Python, Jupyter Notebook, Google Colab, Ultralytics, OpenCV, PyTorch, and PyQt, enabling efficient model training and intuitive UI design. The application interface includes dynamic controls for starting, continuing, and stopping detection, logging results, and viewing recommendations for addressing detected defects. Each module was individually tested to ensure correct functionality before integration into the full system.

The application also includes various mediums for detecting anomalies such as uploading different types of media such as images and videos, as well as the detection of anomalies in real-time with the use of the live detection feature. Users easily switch between media types and live detection for flexible analysis. Additional components such as the Model Page and Training Results Page provide users with a deeper understanding of the architecture of YOLOv10-S model and its performance during training, which enhances the transparency of the system and educational value.

The researchers overall made this system to be a solution to the ever-evolving field of 3D Printing which allows visualizing anomalies, providing timely feedback, and offering recommended solutions. With the help of image detection and classification model YOLOv10s, the system encourages users to optimize their 3D Printing processes and reduce material waste. This is to recognize machine learning technology to become a part of making the environment sustainable. It also demonstrates practical application of machine learning in improving manufacturing efficiency and quality control. Lastly, the system serves as a practical tool that connects advanced research with real-world manufacturing applications, ensuring efficient resource utilization and promoting sustainable practice.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section details and analyzes the results obtained from the model training and evaluation stages. Its main goal is to evaluate the effectiveness of YOLOv10-S in detecting and classifying 3D Printing anomalies, in line with the research objectives outlined in the problem statement. To accomplish this, six training sessions were held under various settings, including changes in picture input types (RGB and grayscale). These sessions were designed to provide extensive data for answering research questions and selecting the best model. The training results section solely presents the results from the best-performing model for the sake of clarity. In this study, the researchers focus on important performance metrics like training and validation loss, accuracy, recall, and mAP50 to see how effectively the model identifies issues like extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. In addition, this section also covers the evaluation and selection of the most appropriate confidence threshold, which determines the minimum score for valid detections during inference. These results help us evaluate how well the model aligns with the goals of the research.

5.1 Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values in Terms of Training Loss and Validation Loss

This subsection presents the training and validation loss curves of the six training sessions conducted under two image settings: RGB and grayscale. For each image type, the evaluation is divided into three key loss metrics: box loss, class loss, and distribution focal loss

(DFL loss). The training loss and validation loss curves are plotted separately to assess the convergence behavior of the model, consistency between training and validation, and overall learning stability. This analysis aims to identify which image type and training condition resulted in better loss minimization and generalization, contributing to the selection of the best-performing model.

5.1.1 Box Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset Trainings

In Figure 30, both RGB and grayscale box loss graphs exhibit remarkably similar patterns, demonstrating consistent overfitting characteristics across all training iterations. In both modalities, training losses (solid lines) show steady, continuous decline throughout the 50 epochs, ultimately reaching approximately 2.3 units. However, validation losses (dashed lines) in both cases initially improve until approximately epoch 10–20, then stabilize before gradually increasing, ultimately reaching around 4.0 units by training completion. This consistent divergence pattern between training and validation performance across both input modalities suggests that the object localization capacity of the model experiences fundamental generalization limitations that are independent of color information. These findings indicate that factors other than input modality, such as model architecture or dataset variability, are contributing more significantly to the observed overfitting. Furthermore, the similar trends across RGB and grayscale highlight that reducing input complexity alone is insufficient to mitigate generalization issues. Therefore, alternative strategies such as regularization, data augmentation, or architectural modifications are necessary to improve the robustness of the model.

Figure 30. Box Loss.

Table 10 shows all six models (RGB Train 1-3 and Grayscale Train 1-3) show t-statistics with values ranging from -8.91 to -9.38 and extremely small p-values in the range of 10^{-12} to 10^{-13}). Since these values fall significantly below the conventional significance level of 0.05, the researchers firmly reject the null hypothesis that there is no difference between training and validation box loss. This means there is a statistically significant difference between the training and validation losses in terms of box loss.

	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-9.09	4.40×10^{-12}
RGB Train 2	-8.91	7.96×10^{-12}
RGB Train 3	-9.09	2.18×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 1	-9.22	1.37×10^{-12}
Grayscale Train 2	-9.38	1.37×10^{-13}
Grayscale Train 3	-9.17	1.67×10^{-12}

Table 10. T-test for Box Loss.

5.1.2 Class Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset Trainings

The class loss metrics for both RGB and grayscale training iterations demonstrate highly consistent patterns, suggesting that anomaly classification behavior is largely independent of color information. Both modalities show initial rapid improvement followed by more gradual optimization, with training losses continuing to decrease throughout all 50 epochs while validation losses stabilized around epoch 30-40. The validation-training gap in both cases is narrower than observed in box loss, indicating better generalization in the classification component. The remarkably similar convergence behavior across modalities suggests that the discriminative features for anomaly classification in this domain primarily relate to textural and structural patterns rather than color characteristics, as shown in Figure 31. Additionally, both modalities display a notable acceleration in training loss reduction after epoch 40, potentially indicating a learning rate schedule change or optimizer behavior that affects classification performance similarly regardless of input modality.

Figure 31. Class Loss.

The t-test results for classification loss indicate that only RGB Train 1 shows a statistically significant difference between training and validation losses ($p = 0.03 < 0.05$). RGB Train 2 is borderline significant ($p = 0.05$), while RGB Train 3 is not ($p = 0.09$). All Grayscale training runs show no significant difference ($p\text{-values} > 0.05$), suggesting consistent classification loss between training and validation. Overall, this implies that RGB models exhibit slight overfitting, while Grayscale models maintain more consistent performance, as shown in Table 11.

	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	1.89	0.03
RGB Train 2	1.65	0.05
RGB Train 3	1.34	0.09
Grayscale Train 1	0.08	0.47
Grayscale Train 2	0.24	0.40
Grayscale Train 3	0.34	0.37

Table 11. T-test for Class Loss.

5.1.3 DFL Loss in RGB and Grayscale Dataset

The Distribution Focal Loss (DFL) graphs for both RGB and grayscale modalities reveal identical problematic patterns with the most severe overfitting among all metrics. In both cases, training losses decreased steadily throughout the entire training process, reaching approximately 2.5 units by epoch 50. Simultaneously, validation losses in both modalities show initial improvement until approximately epoch 20, followed by stabilization and then consistent deterioration after epoch 25, ultimately exceeding their starting values. This identical pattern across input types

indicates that the capacity of the model to precisely localize object boundaries suffers from the same fundamental generalization limitations regardless of color information availability. The severity of this overfitting in both modalities suggests that the distribution learning aspect of the model—which focuses on precise boundary localization—faces inherent challenges, as shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32. Distribution Focal Loss.

Table 12 presents t-test results for DFL loss, showing extremely low p-values (all < 0.05), which indicate a highly significant difference between training and validation losses for both RGB and Grayscale models. The large negative t-statistics suggest that the training loss is consistently and substantially lower than the validation loss. This pattern points to clear overfitting across all training runs, regardless of the input format, as shown in Table 12. These results further reinforce the conclusion that the model struggles to generalize effectively beyond the training data. Consequently,

this emphasizes the need for implementing techniques such as data augmentation or regularization to reduce overfitting and enhance validation performance.

Training Run	t-statistic	p-value
RGB Train 1	-16.78	2.99×10^{-22}
RGB Train 2	-17.17	1.14×10^{-22}
RGB Train 3	-16.84	2.61×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 1	-16.33	9.32×10^{-22}
Grayscale Train 2	-15.47	8.68×10^{-21}
Grayscale Train 3	-15.98	2.35×10^{-21}

Table 12. T-test for Distribution Focal Loss.

Based on the statistical analyses conducted for box loss, class loss, and distribution focal loss (DFL), the results support the presence of statistically significant differences between training and validation loss values in most cases. In particular, both box loss and DFL loss consistently show large negative t-statistics and extremely small p-values ($p < 0.05$), indicating notable overfitting in localization-related metrics for both RGB and grayscale datasets. Meanwhile, class loss shows smaller or insignificant differences between training and validation in several training runs, especially in the grayscale models, suggesting better generalization in the classification capabilities of the model. Therefore, Hypothesis 1.2.1 is accepted. This result implies that while the model struggles with generalizing precise object localization, it reliably learns to classify anomalies. Since accurate identification of printing defects is often more critical than exact boundary localization in real-world scenarios, the model remains effective and suitable for deployment.

5.2 Determine the Accuracy in Terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in Classifying Among the Different Anomalies and Between RGB and Grayscale Images.

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of YOLOv10-S model performance in detecting and classifying FDM printing anomalies across different image modes. The analysis examines three key metrics, precision, recall, and mean Average Precision at 50% IoU threshold (mAP50), to assess the accuracy of the model in distinguishing between Extrusion Problem, Spaghetti, Stringing, and Warping anomalies. Additionally, the comparative analysis between RGB and grayscale image processing reveals the impact of color information on detection performance, providing insights into optimal input configurations for real-time anomaly detection systems.

5.2.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The descriptive statistics reveal distinct patterns in detection performance across anomaly types and color modes. With regards the precision metrics, Spaghetti anomalies demonstrated superior detection capabilities, followed by Stringing, Warping, and Extrusion Problems. A similar hierarchical pattern emerged for recall. The mean Average Precision at 50% IoU threshold (mAP50) demonstrated consistent performance trends, with Spaghetti anomalies achieving the highest scores, followed by Stringing, Warping, and Extrusion. RGB imaging consistently outperformed Grayscale across all metrics as shown in Table 13, suggesting that color information significantly aids in distinguishing fine-grained anomaly characteristics. The lower detection scores for Extrusion Problems indicate that certain anomaly types present greater challenges for automated recognition due to their subtle visual manifestations.

	Anomaly	Color	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Precision	Extrusion Problem	Grayscale	.45933	.018610	3
		RGB	.57867	.012662	3
		Total	.51900	.066894	6
	Spaghetti	Grayscale	.80067	.026764	3
		RGB	.80667	.030089	3
		Total	.80367	.025680	6
	Stringing	Grayscale	.63900	.082395	3
		RGB	.74133	.012858	3
		Total	.69017	.076963	6
	Warping	Grayscale	.63825	.048384	3
		RGB	.65133	.069515	3
		Total	.65267	.053586	6
	Total	Grayscale	.63825	.133588	12
		RGB	.69450	.096433	12
		Total	.66637	.117507	24
Recall	Extrusion Problem	Grayscale	.47900	.001732	3
		RGB	.58000	.066813	3
		Total	.52950	.069621	6
	Spaghetti	Grayscale	.73000	.003464	3
		RGB	.74733	.041429	3
		Total	.73867	.027955	6
	Stringing	Grayscale	.54033	.105396	3
		RGB	.69700	.058284	3
		Total	.61867	.114741	6
	Warping	Grayscale	.75467	.031086	3
		RGB	.64233	.148894	3
		Total	.69800	.114488	6
	Total	Grayscale	.62600	.132506	12
		RGB	.66642	.100106	12
		Total	.64621	.116688	24
mAP50	Extrusion Problem	Grayscale	.44933	.036747	3
		RGB	.53233	.024542	3
		Total	.49083	.053364	6
	Spaghetti	Grayscale	.79567	.009292	3
		RGB	.80867	.025736	3
		Total	.80217	.018713	6
	Stringing	Grayscale	.58633	.123541	3
		RGB	.75567	.050003	3
		Total	.67100	.125328	6
	Warping	Grayscale	.69800	.008660	3
		RGB	.60833	.100281	3
		Total	.65317	.080403	6
	Total	Grayscale	.63233	.145644	12
		RGB	.67625	.126182	12
		Total	.65429	.135140	24

Table 13. Descriptive Statistical Analysis.

5.2.2 Multivariate Tests

The multivariate analysis using Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root yielded consistent findings. Anomaly type exhibited a significant multivariate effect across all test statistics with a large effect size, indicating substantial differences in detection performance across the four anomaly types. Color mode similarly showed a significant multivariate effect with a moderate effect size, confirming that RGB and Grayscale imaging produced measurably different results. The interaction effect between anomaly type and color mode approached statistical significance with a moderate effect size, suggesting that the effectiveness of color mode varied depending on the specific anomaly type being detected, as shown in Table 14.

	Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.997	1537.338	3.000	14.000	.000	.997
	Wilks' Lambda	.003	1537.338	3.000	14.000	.000	.997
	Hotelling's Trace	329.430	1537.338	3.000	14.000	.000	.997
	Roy's Largest Root	329.430	1537.338	3.000	14.000	.000	.997
Anomaly	Pillai's Trace	1.397	4.650	9.000	48.000	.000	.466
	Wilks' Lambda	.046	9.717	9.000	34.223	.000	.643
	Hotelling's Trace	11.209	15.775	9.000	38.000	.000	.789
	Roy's Largest Root	10.264	54.739	3.000	16.000	.000	.911
Color	Pillai's Trace	.388	2.965	3.000	14.000	.068	.388
	Wilks' Lambda	.612	2.965	3.000	14.000	.068	.388
	Hotelling's Trace	.635	2.965	3.000	14.000	.068	.388
	Roy's Largest Root	.635	2.965	3.000	14.000	.068	.388
Anomaly * Color	Pillai's Trace	.829	2.037	9.000	48.000	.055	.276
	Wilks' Lambda	.347	2.071	9.000	34.223	.061	.297
	Hotelling's Trace	1.396	1.965	9.000	38.000	.072	.318
	Roy's Largest Root	.920	4.905	3.000	16.000	.013	.479

Table 14. Multivariate Tests.

5.2.3 Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

The results of the Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Table 15) indicate that the independent variable Anomaly had a statistically significant effect on all three dependent variables: Precision ($p < .000$), Recall ($p = .001$), and mAP50 ($p < .000$). This suggests that the presence and type of anomaly meaningfully influence model performance across all evaluated metrics. The variable Color, however, showed a significant effect only on Precision ($p = .008$), but not on Recall ($p = .200$) or mAP50 ($p = .101$), implying that color alone slightly influences the model but does not substantially affect its recall or overall average precision. This indicates that the ability of the model to detect anomalies is more sensitive to structural variations than to color differences. Additionally, the influence of color appears to be secondary when compared to the dominant effect of anomaly type. Furthermore, the interaction between Anomaly and Color was found to be significant for Recall ($p = .032$) and mAP50 ($p = .015$), indicating that the combined effects of anomaly type and color variation play an important role in influencing these outcomes. The Partial Eta Squared values show that anomaly had a strong effect on the dependent variables (ranging from 0.637 to 0.884), while the effect of Color and the Anomaly \times Color interaction were comparatively smaller. Overall, these findings highlight that anomaly type is a major factor impacting model performance, while color has a limited effect except when interacting with anomaly type for certain metrics. These results reinforce the importance of prioritizing anomaly-specific features during model training to achieve more reliable detection outcomes.

Source	Dependent Value	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Precision	.285	7	.041	20.041	.000	.898
	Recall	.225	7	.032	5.879	.002	.720
	mAP50	.359	7	.051	13.405	.000	.854
Intercept	Precision	10.657	3	10.657	5244.752	.000	.997
	Recall	10.022	3	10.022	1828.993	.000	.991
	mAP50	10.274	3	10.274	2686.512	.000	.994
Anomaly	Precision	.248	1	.083	40.672	.000	.884
	Recall	.154	1	.051	9.348	.001	.637
	mAP50	.293	1	.098	25.555	.000	.827
Color	Precision	.019	3	.019	9.343	.008	.369
	Recall	.010	3	.010	1.789	.200	.101
	mAP50	.012	3	.012	3.026	.101	.159
Anomaly * Color	Precision	.018	1	.006	2.977	.063	.358
	Recall	.062	1	.021	3.774	.032	.414
	mAP50	.054	1	.018	4.714	.015	.469
Error	Precision	.033	16	.002			
	Recall	.088	16	.005			
	mAP50	.061	16	.004			
Total	Precision	10.975	24				
	Recall	10.335	24				
	mAP50	10.694	24				
Corrected Total	Precision	.318	23				
	Recall	.313	23				
	mAP50	.420	23				

Table 15. Tests Between Subjects Effects.

5.2.4 Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly and Color)

Analysis of marginal means confirmed the performance hierarchy across anomaly types. For precision, Spaghetti anomalies demonstrated superior detection capabilities ($M = .804$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.765, .843]), followed by Stringing ($M = .690$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.651, .729]), Warping ($M = .652$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.614, .691]), and Extrusion ($M = .519$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.480, .558]). Similar patterns

emerged for recall and mAP50 metrics, consistently positioning Spaghetti anomalies as the most detectable and Extrusion anomalies as the most challenging to identify accurately, as shown in Table 16.

Dependent Variable	Anomaly	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Level	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Precision	Extrusion	.519	.018	.480	.558
	Spaghetti	.804	.018	.765	.843
	Stringing	.690	.018	.651	.729
	Warping	.653	.018	.614	.692
Recall	Extrusion	.530	.030	.465	.594
	Spaghetti	.739	.030	.675	.803
	Stringing	.619	.030	.555	.683
	Warping	.698	.030	.634	.762
mAP50	Extrusion	.491	.025	.437	.544
	Spaghetti	.802	.025	.749	.856
	Stringing	.671	.025	.617	.725
	Warping	.653	.025	.600	.707

Table 16. Estimated Marginal Mean for Anomaly.

The estimated marginal means for color mode confirmed the superior performance of RGB over Grayscale across all metrics in the conducted experiments. RGB imaging demonstrated higher precision ($M = .694$, $SE = .013$, 95% CI [.667, .722]), recall ($M = .666$, $SE = .021$, 95% CI [.622, .710]), and mAP50 ($M = .676$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.638, .714]) compared to Grayscale imaging, which showed lower precision ($M = .638$, $SE = .013$, 95% CI [.611, .666]), recall ($M = .626$, $SE = .021$, 95% CI [.581, .671]), and mAP50 ($M = .632$, $SE = .018$, 95% CI [.594, .670]), as shown in Table 17.

Dependent Variable	Color	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Level	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Precision	Grayscale	.638	.013	.611	.666
	RGB	.694	.013	.667	.722
Recall	Grayscale	.626	.021	.581	.671
	RGB	.666	.021	.621	.712
mAP50	Grayscale	.632	.018	.594	.670
	RGB	.676	.018	.638	.714

Table 17. Estimated Marginal Mean for Colors.

5.2.5 Estimated Marginal Means (Anomaly * Color)

Analysis of the interaction between anomaly type and color mode revealed differential effects of color information across anomaly types. For Spaghetti anomalies, both RGB and Grayscale performed comparably across all metrics. Meanwhile, stringing anomalies showed substantial performance degradation in Grayscale mode compared to RGB, particularly for precision (RGB: $M = .741$, $SE = .026$, 95% CI [.686, .797]; Grayscale: $M = .639$, $SE = .026$, 95% CI [.584, .694]) and recall (RGB: $M = .697$, $SE = .043$, 95% CI [.606, .788]; Grayscale: $M = .540$, $SE = .043$, 95% CI [.450, .631]). Interestingly, Warping anomalies demonstrated superior recall performance in Grayscale mode ($M = .755$, $SE = .043$, 95% CI [.664, .845]) compared to RGB ($M = .641$, $SE = .043$, 95% CI [.551, .732]). Extrusion anomalies consistently performed better with RGB than Grayscale across all metrics, though the differences were modest. These interaction effects underscore the importance of selecting appropriate imaging modalities based on the specific anomaly types targeted for detection in 3D Printing applications, as shown in Table 18.

Dependent Variable	Anomaly	Color	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Level		
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Precision	Extrusion	Grayscale	.459	.026	.404	.515	
		RGB	.579	.026	.523	.634	
	Spaghetti	Grayscale	.801	.026	.745	.856	
		RGB	.807	.026	.751	.862	
	Stringing	Grayscale	.639	.026	.584	.694	
		RGB	.741	.026	.686	.797	
	Warping	Grayscale	.654	.026	.599	.709	
		RGB	.651	.026	.596	.707	
	Recall	Extrusion	Grayscale	.479	.043	.388	.570
			RGB	.580	.043	.489	.671
		Spaghetti	Grayscale	.730	.043	.639	.821
			RGB	.747	.043	.657	.838
Stringing		Grayscale	.540	.043	.450	.631	
		RGB	.697	.043	.606	.788	
Warping		Grayscale	.755	.043	.664	.845	
		RGB	.641	.043	.551	.732	
mAP50		Extrusion	Grayscale	.449	.036	.374	.525
			RGB	.532	.036	.457	.608
		Spaghetti	Grayscale	.796	.036	.720	.871
			RGB	.809	.036	.733	.884
	Stringing	Grayscale	.586	.036	.511	.662	
		RGB	.756	.036	.680	.831	
	Warping	Grayscale	.698	.036	.622	.774	
		RGB	.608	.036	.533	.684	

Table 18. Estimated Marginal Mean for Anomaly * Color.

Based on the results of the multivariate and between-subjects analyses, Hypothesis 1.2.2 is accepted. The findings confirm that there is a statistically significant difference in the precision, recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S when classifying among the different 3D Printing anomalies, extrusion problem, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, as well as between RGB and Grayscale images. Specifically, the anomaly type significantly influenced all three performance metrics, indicating that the model detects certain anomaly types, such as spaghetti

and stringing, more accurately than others like extrusion. Additionally, the color mode (RGB vs. Grayscale) had a significant effect on precision and contributed to a significant interaction effect with anomaly type on recall and mAP50. The result confirms that RGB images generally lead to better detection performance compared to grayscale, particularly in terms of precision.

The acceptance of this hypothesis has several important implications for the study and the system being developed. First, it validates that the performance of the model varies across different anomaly types, emphasizing the need for balanced training data and potentially tailored preprocessing for each class. Second, it supports the use of RGB imaging as the default mode for higher precision and overall reliability, especially in real-time monitoring applications where accuracy is critical. Although grayscale images still offer acceptable performance in some cases, such as slightly higher recall for Warping, the overall results demonstrate that color information enhances the ability of YOLOv10-S to distinguish visual features, especially for anomalies like stringing where grayscale significantly reduces detection accuracy.

5.3 YOLOv10-S Training Results

The YOLOv10-S model trained under the RGB Train 1 configuration demonstrated excellent learning progression and strong generalization across both validation and test datasets. Throughout training, key metrics, precision, recall, and mAP50, consistently improved, indicating stable model optimization and effective learning from the RGB input data. The best performance was observed on the validation set, where the model achieved a

mAP50 of 0.756, precision of 0.749, and recall of 0.709, signifying strong detection accuracy and minimal overfitting.

The model maintained competitive performance on the unseen test set, achieving a mAP50 of 0.716, precision of 0.717, and recall of 0.733. These results demonstrate the ability of the model to generalize effectively in real-world scenarios. Based on the comprehensive evaluation across all metrics, the RGB Train 1 model was selected for deployment in the anomaly detection system, balancing high detection accuracy with consistent real-time performance in diverse 3D Printing environments.

5.3.1 Training Loss

Over the 50-epoch training period, loss curves revealed consistent convergence patterns. The train/box_loss began above 4.0 and gradually declined to around 2.3, reflecting the increasing accuracy of the model in predicting bounding box coordinates. Similarly, the train/cls_loss started at approximately 6.5 and decreased to about 1.5, indicating that the model became progressively more effective at correctly classifying detected objects. The train/df_l_loss, which started at around 3.8 and dropped to approximately 2.5, further highlights improvements in the localization precision of the model. In Figure 33, these declining trends across all training loss components suggest that the model learned effectively and adapted well to the dataset.

5.3.2 Validation Loss

Performance on the validation set followed patterns similar to training data, though with notable changes after epoch 30. The val/box_loss started at around 4.3,

reached a low of approximately 3.6, and then slightly increased by the end of training. The val/cls_loss dropped from nearly 6.0 to below 3.0, maintaining consistency with the training classification loss, which suggests adequate generalization. The val/df_l_loss showed a similar pattern, decreasing from 4.4 to about 3.7 before rising slightly. This mild uptick at later stages indicates a point at which early stopping is considered to maintain optimal validation performance. See Figure 33 for reference.

5.3.3 Model Precision

In Figure 33, model precision showed a strong upward trend throughout training. It began at approximately 0.25 and rose steadily, eventually stabilizing near 0.72. This growth reflects the increasing ability of the model to correctly identify relevant instances with fewer false positives. The fluctuations observed in the precision curve are attributed to class imbalance in the dataset, as underrepresented classes make it more challenging for the model to maintain high precision across all object categories.

Figure 33. Training Results.

5.3.4 Model Recall

As seen in Figure 33, the recall curve followed a similar positive trajectory, beginning around 0.22 and improving consistently until it reached approximately 0.70 by the end of training. This indicates a significant improvement in the capability of the model to detect all relevant instances in the dataset. The increasing recall values confirm that the YOLOv10-S model became more comprehensive in its detections, reducing the rate of missed objects over time.

5.3.5 Model mAP50

The mAP50 metric, which represents the mean average precision at an Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 50%, started around 0.18 and increased steadily over the training epoch, reaching a peak of about 0.74. This upward trend indicates a substantial improvement in the accuracy of the model in object detection, particularly in scenarios where moderate overlap with ground truth boxes is acceptable. As seen in Figure 33, the performance plateau observed toward the end of training suggests that the model reached a stable and reliable level of detection accuracy on the given dataset.

5.3.6 Model Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix for the YOLOv10-S model, as seen in Figure 34 after training shows good performance in identifying different types of 3D Printing defects. High percentages along the diagonal indicate strong correct prediction rates, such as "Extrusion Problem" with 246 correct predictions (72%), "Spaghetti" with 271 correct

predictions (87%), "Stringing" with 283 correct predictions (81%), and "Warping" with 374 correct predictions (80%). The background class shows lower performance, with noticeable confusion where defects are sometimes misclassified as background and vice versa. For instance, 28% of "Extrusion Problem" and 27% of "Warping" cases were incorrectly predicted as background. This suggests that while the model is generally strong at distinguishing between defect types, it still struggles with accurately identifying background images, leading to some false positives and false negatives. Misclassifications primarily involve the background rather than confusion between defect types. This pattern suggests the model distinguishes well between anomalies but requires better background filtering. Overall, the model demonstrates good classification ability across all target categories.

Figure 34. Confusion Matrix Results.

The YOLOv10-S model trained under the RGB Train 1 configuration showed strong and consistent performance across training, validation, and test phases. It achieved a validation mAP50 of 0.756, precision of 0.749, and recall of 0.709, while maintaining similar performance on the test set with a mAP50 of 0.716, precision of 0.717, and recall of 0.733—indicating good generalization and minimal overfitting. Loss curves confirmed effective optimization, and the confusion matrix highlighted high accuracy in detecting key anomalies like "Spaghetti" and "Stringing." Though some misclassification occurred with background images, the model overall proved reliable for real-time 3D Printing anomaly detection and was selected for deployment.

5.4 Confidence Threshold Evaluation and Selection

This section presents the evaluation of different confidence thresholds applied to the anomaly detection model. Confidence thresholds ranging from 0.10 to 0.90 were tested in 0.05 increments using both the validation and test sets. For each threshold, key performance metrics such as precision, recall, and F1 score were recorded to assess the ability of the model to make accurate and reliable detections. This process aimed to identify the optimal threshold that provides the best trade-off between precision and recall while maintaining high overall detection quality.

Table 19 presents the evaluation results on the validation set across various confidence thresholds. The threshold 0.35 achieved the highest F1 score of 0.728, slightly outperforming other thresholds. This indicates that at 0.35, the model attains the best balance between

precision and recall, maximizing the harmonic mean of these two metrics. Thresholds from 0.1 to 0.3 show identical F1 scores of approximately 0.7275, with stable precision (0.748) and recall (0.708). These thresholds offer consistent and balanced performance, favoring slightly higher precision but lower recall compared to 0.35. As the threshold increases beyond 0.35, precision improves but recall decreases substantially, leading to lower F1 scores. This pattern reflects the typical precision-recall trade-off where higher confidence thresholds reduce false positives but miss more true positives.

Threshold	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.748	0.708	0.727451
0.15	0.748	0.708	0.727451
0.2	0.748	0.708	0.727451
0.25	0.748	0.708	0.727451
0.3	0.748	0.708	0.727451
0.35	0.732	0.724	0.727978
0.4	0.757	0.699	0.726845
0.45	0.784	0.67	0.722531
0.5	0.811	0.637	0.713546
0.55	0.833	0.607	0.702265
0.6	0.849	0.562	0.676312
0.65	0.877	0.518	0.651306
0.7	0.89	0.455	0.602156
0.75	0.896	0.373	0.526727
0.8	0.914	0.262	0.407259
0.85	0.941	0.135	0.236125
0.9	1	0.0327	0.063329

Table 19. Validation Set Results at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

Meanwhile, Table 20 shows the test set evaluation results across confidence thresholds. The threshold 0.30 achieved the highest F1 score of 0.7269, with precision at 0.735 and recall

at 0.719, indicating the best balance between detecting true positives and minimizing false positives. Thresholds from 0.1 to 0.25 exhibit stable and identical precision, recall, and F1 scores of 0.725, reflecting consistent performance in this range. As the threshold increases beyond 0.30, precision nears perfect values, but recall drops sharply, causing the F1 score to decrease significantly.

Threshold	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.725	0.725	0.725
0.15	0.725	0.725	0.725
0.2	0.725	0.725	0.725
0.25	0.725	0.725	0.725
0.3	0.735	0.719	0.726912
0.35	0.757	0.687	0.720303
0.4	0.768	0.649	0.703503
0.45	0.777	0.597	0.67521
0.5	0.79	0.557	0.653348
0.55	0.805	0.515	0.628144
0.6	0.819	0.482	0.606853
0.65	0.825	0.436	0.5705
0.7	0.842	0.386	0.529336
0.75	0.884	0.313	0.462309
0.8	0.899	0.223	0.357357
0.85	0.932	0.123	0.217319
0.9	0.964	0.0121	0.0239

Table 20. Test Set Results at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

Based on the evaluation results, the confidence threshold of 0.30 demonstrated consistently strong performance across both the validation and test datasets. It ranked second highest in the validation set with an F1 score of 0.7275 and achieved the highest F1 score of 0.7269 on the test set, showing excellent balance between precision and recall in both

controlled and unseen scenarios. This consistency highlights 0.30 as a statistically optimal threshold for the classification performance of the model. While threshold 0.35 produced the highest F1 score on the validation set (0.728), its performance declined on the test set, dropping to an F1 score of 0.7203. This suggests that although 0.35 was slightly better during validation, it did not generalize as well to unseen data, which is a critical factor in threshold selection.

Despite the strong statistical performance of 0.30, the final chosen threshold was 0.25. This was based on actual use of the system during live monitoring. In real-world testing, it was observed that almost all correct detections had confidence scores of 0.25 or higher. When the threshold was reduced to 0.15 or 0.20, there was no increase in correct detections, as most confidence scores observed during real-time testing did not fall below 0.25. On the other hand, setting the threshold to 0.30 risked missing some anomalies with lower confidence scores, which reduces the sensitivity of the system in live conditions. For this reason, 0.25 was chosen as the most practical and dependable threshold, providing reliable results in both testing and real-time use. It was the next best choice after 0.30 and proved to work best in the actual application.

5.4.1 Per-Anomaly Confidence Threshold Analysis

To provide further insight into how different confidence thresholds influence the detection of each anomaly type, a per-anomaly analysis was conducted. This evaluation allows for a more detailed understanding of model behavior, highlighting how performance trends differ depending on the anomaly type. By examining both the validation and test results for each class, the analysis ensures that the chosen thresholds are not only effective during training but also generalize well to unseen data. This step

also reveals how sensitive each specific defect is to changes in confidence levels, ensuring that no single class is disproportionately affected by a universal setting. Furthermore, this verification process confirms that the model maintains a high level of reliability across all categories under a standardized threshold.

Based on the evaluation results for extrusion problem detection in Table 21, the confidence threshold of 0.30 demonstrated the most consistent performance across both validation and test datasets. This threshold achieved tied first place in the validation set with an F1-score of 0.616 and secured the highest F1-score of 0.604 on the test set, indicating superior generalization capability to unseen data. The balanced precision-recall trade-off at this threshold suggests optimal model sensitivity without compromising accuracy. While thresholds 0.1-0.25 produced identical validation performance (F1: 0.616), their test performance was marginally lower (F1: 0.602), indicating potential overfitting to the validation data. Similarly, threshold 0.4 achieved the highest tied validation F1-score (0.616) with superior precision (0.652), but experienced significant performance degradation on the test set (F1: 0.557), primarily due to a substantial recall drop from 0.584 to 0.508. This pattern demonstrates poor generalization and suggests the model becomes overly conservative at higher confidence levels. Across increasing thresholds, precision shows a steady upward trend while recall declines sharply, particularly in the test set. This inverse relationship contributes to the progressive reduction in F1-scores observed beyond the 0.30 threshold. The effect is more pronounced at thresholds above 0.45, where recall deterioration outweighs gains in precision.

Threshold	Validation Set			Test Set		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.642	0.592	0.615987	0.578	0.628	0.601964
0.15	0.642	0.592	0.615987	0.578	0.628	0.601964
0.2	0.642	0.592	0.615987	0.578	0.628	0.601964
0.25	0.642	0.592	0.615987	0.578	0.628	0.601964
0.3	0.642	0.592	0.615987	0.59	0.619	0.604152
0.35	0.625	0.601	0.612765	0.618	0.565	0.590313
0.4	0.652	0.584	0.616129	0.617	0.508	0.55722
0.45	0.679	0.551	0.60834	0.627	0.414	0.498709
0.5	0.72	0.519	0.603196	0.63	0.348	0.448344
0.55	0.746	0.49	0.591489	0.649	0.288	0.398958
0.6	0.781	0.419	0.545398	0.677	0.264	0.379868
0.65	0.84	0.37	0.513719	0.67	0.201	0.309231
0.7	0.862	0.311	0.457088	0.724	0.165	0.268751
0.75	0.863	0.258	0.397242	0.822	0.111	0.195588
0.8	0.906	0.17	0.286283	0.85	0.0511	0.096404
0.85	0.914	0.0938	0.170139	1	0.015	0.029557
0.9	1	0.0323	0.062579	1	0.00901	0.017859

Table 21. Extrusion Problem Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

On the other hand, as shown in Table 22, the confidence threshold of 0.30 emerged as the optimal choice for spaghetti detection, demonstrating exceptional consistency across both validation and test datasets. This threshold achieved tied first place in the validation set with an F1-score of 0.812 and secured the highest F1-score of 0.791 on the test set, indicating superior model generalization. Threshold 0.45 showed competitive validation performance (F1: 0.812, ranking tied for first), but exhibited significant degradation on the test set (F1: 0.766), indicating overfitting tendencies. Furthermore, the data reveals that as the threshold increases beyond 0.30, the gain in precision is offset by a sharp decline in recall, which leads to critical printing failures being missed.

Threshold	Validation Set			Test Set		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.834	0.791	0.811931	0.831	0.755	0.791179
0.15	0.834	0.791	0.811931	0.831	0.755	0.791179
0.2	0.834	0.791	0.811931	0.831	0.755	0.791179
0.25	0.834	0.791	0.811931	0.83	0.755	0.790726
0.3	0.834	0.791	0.811931	0.835	0.752	0.79133
0.35	0.812	0.801	0.806462	0.85	0.737	0.789477
0.4	0.841	0.779	0.808814	0.866	0.721	0.786876
0.45	0.871	0.76	0.811723	0.88	0.678	0.765905
0.5	0.885	0.718	0.792801	0.895	0.656	0.757086
0.55	0.9	0.696	0.784962	0.919	0.635	0.751049
0.6	0.916	0.66	0.767208	0.929	0.61	0.736439
0.65	0.923	0.612	0.735995	0.944	0.579	0.717762
0.7	0.929	0.506	0.655155	0.948	0.505	0.658968
0.75	0.939	0.397	0.558058	0.964	0.418	0.583143
0.8	0.938	0.24	0.382207	0.96	0.294	0.450144
0.85	0.935	0.0929	0.169008	0.965	0.17	0.289075
0.9	1	0.00962	0.019057	1	0.0186	0.036521

Table 22. Spaghetti Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

Table 23 shows that confidence thresholds 0.30 and 0.35 are top contenders for Stringing detection, with threshold 0.35 ranking first in validation (F1: 0.740) and threshold 0.30 ranking first in test set performance (F1: 0.743). Threshold 0.35 demonstrates excellent consistency between validation and test sets, with virtually no performance difference (0.001). The results reveal that thresholds 0.1-0.30 produced identical validation performance (F1: 0.733), creating a performance plateau where lower confidence levels offered no additional benefit. While both thresholds are essentially tied with minimal performance differences, threshold 0.30 is the optimal choice when prioritizing real-world scenarios, as it achieves the highest test F1-score of 0.743. Although threshold 0.35 shows superior validation performance and better

validation-test consistency, the test set performance is ultimately more indicative of real-world deployment effectiveness, making 0.30 the preferred threshold for stringing detection.

Threshold	Validation Set			Test set		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.745	0.722	0.73332	0.764	0.715	0.738688
0.15	0.745	0.722	0.73332	0.764	0.715	0.738688
0.2	0.745	0.722	0.73332	0.764	0.715	0.738688
0.25	0.745	0.722	0.73332	0.764	0.716	0.739222
0.3	0.745	0.722	0.73332	0.779	0.71	0.742901
0.35	0.73	0.751	0.740351	0.806	0.686	0.741174
0.4	0.754	0.719	0.736084	0.821	0.637	0.71739
0.45	0.768	0.682	0.72245	0.832	0.604	0.6999
0.5	0.795	0.656	0.718842	0.866	0.574	0.690394
0.55	0.825	0.622	0.709261	0.878	0.525	0.657092
0.6	0.828	0.579	0.681467	0.902	0.488	0.633347
0.65	0.866	0.536	0.662163	0.919	0.449	0.603262
0.7	0.883	0.499	0.637651	0.929	0.429	0.586953
0.75	0.882	0.384	0.535052	0.965	0.366	0.530714
0.8	0.917	0.287	0.437174	1	0.29	0.449612
0.85	0.964	0.155	0.26706	1	0.175	0.297872
0.9	1	0.0458	0.087588	1	0.0066	0.013113

Table 23. Stringing Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

Table 24 shows that confidence threshold 0.30 is optimal for warping detection, demonstrating the most consistent performance across validation and test sets. While threshold 0.35 achieved the highest validation F1-score of 0.754, it dropped significantly to third place on the test set (F1: 0.758). In contrast, threshold 0.30 maintained strong and consistent performance, ranking second in validation (F1: 0.747)

and achieving the highest test F1-score of 0.763, making it the most reliable choice for real-world deployment.

Threshold	Validation Set			Test Set		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
0.1	0.771	0.725	0.747293	0.729	0.8	0.762852
0.15	0.771	0.725	0.747293	0.729	0.8	0.762852
0.2	0.771	0.725	0.747293	0.729	0.8	0.762852
0.25	0.771	0.725	0.747293	0.729	0.8	0.762852
0.3	0.771	0.725	0.747293	0.734	0.795	0.763283
0.35	0.763	0.745	0.753893	0.755	0.762	0.758484
0.4	0.779	0.712	0.743995	0.769	0.731	0.749519
0.45	0.816	0.687	0.745964	0.771	0.69	0.728255
0.5	0.843	0.657	0.738468	0.771	0.65	0.705348
0.55	0.863	0.62	0.721591	0.772	0.612	0.682751
0.6	0.87	0.59	0.703151	0.768	0.567	0.652369
0.65	0.881	0.554	0.680243	0.767	0.517	0.617662
0.7	0.887	0.504	0.642772	0.766	0.445	0.562956
0.75	0.902	0.453	0.603108	0.785	0.357	0.490797
0.8	0.896	0.352	0.505436	0.787	0.255	0.385192
0.85	0.948	0.197	0.326211	0.764	0.131	0.223651
0.9	1	0.0429	0.082271	0.857	0.0143	0.028131

Table 24. Warping Detection at Varying Confidence Thresholds.

The results reveal that thresholds 0.1-0.30 produced identical validation performance (F1: 0.747), creating a performance plateau. However, threshold 0.30 broke away from this plateau on the test set, achieving superior performance (F1: 0.763) compared to the lower thresholds (F1: 0.763 for 0.1-0.25). The poor generalization of threshold 0.35, which dropped from first place in validation to third in test performance, indicates potential overfitting to the validation set, while the

consistent high performance of 0.30 across both sets demonstrates reliable real-world applicability, making it the optimal choice for detecting warping defects.

Overall, the per-anomaly confidence threshold analysis reveals that a threshold of 0.30 consistently delivers the most reliable and generalizable performance across multiple defect types. While some thresholds achieve higher F1-scores in the validation set, their performance often declines on the test set, suggesting overfitting and reduced applicability in real-world scenarios. In contrast, the 0.30 threshold maintains a balanced precision–recall trade-off and demonstrates strong generalization across unseen data for all anomaly categories. This makes it the strongest choice for deployment, providing stable detection performance without sacrificing accuracy or sensitivity.

The overall performance of the YOLOv10-S model, evaluated through training and validation loss values, classification accuracy, and training outcomes, confirms the model as highly effective and suitable for real-time 3D Printing anomaly detection. The analysis of training and validation loss indicated a stable and converging learning process with minimal signs of overfitting. The assessment of classification performance in terms of precision, recall, and mAP@50 demonstrated the strong capability of the model to detect and differentiate between extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping. The RGB-trained configuration of YOLOv10-S achieved a precision of 71.7 percent, recall of 73.3 percent, and mAP@50 of 71.6 percent on the unseen test dataset, indicating consistent and strong generalization to real-world data.

In comparison to previous studies, the model achieved significantly higher performance. A model published by Roboflow [RU2024] reported a mAP@50 of only 56.6 percent and recall of 49.4 percent, despite a higher precision of 87.8 percent, reflecting an imbalanced performance. Another implementation using YOLOv4 [JJ2023] produced a much lower mAP, reaching only 30.24 percent at the final iteration and 42.96 percent at its best-performing checkpoint. A separate attempt using YOLOv2 [OC2025] resulted in only 4.47 percent mAP@50 and both precision and recall of seven percent. Even after fine-tuning, that model achieved only 41.52 percent mAP@50, 50 percent recall, and 64 percent precision.

These comparisons highlight the YOLOv10-S model as a superior solution for accurate detection and classification of 3D Printing anomalies. The results support the readiness of the model for deployment and emphasize its contribution to advancing defect detection in additive manufacturing through improved accuracy, consistency, and real-time responsiveness. Furthermore, the study identified a confidence threshold of 0.25 as the most suitable cutoff for real-time monitoring. While it was the second-best choice in terms of F1 score, it proved to be the best option after testing the application, as it aligned more closely with actual detection behavior. This decision enhances the reliability of the model in real-world conditions by filtering out low-confidence false positives and ensuring that only the most probable detections are considered.

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the conclusion of the research study, aiming to address the initial problem statements. It includes a summary of the results obtained through experimentation, along with possible interpretations based on the stated problems. Additionally, this chapter discusses potential future directions of the study to address the limitations encountered by the researchers during the course of the research. Recommendations for overcoming these challenges are also provided to further enhance the impact of the study on the relevant field.

6.1 Conclusion

This section summarizes the key findings related to the performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting 3D Printing anomalies. The evaluation highlights the strengths in classification stability of the model, particularly in grayscale and RGB settings, and its overall high accuracy across anomaly types. These insights underscore the potential of YOLOv10-S as a reliable tool for real-time defect detection in additive manufacturing environments.

6.1.1 Determine the Performance of YOLOv10-S by Evaluating Loss Values

The analysis of YOLOv10-S loss values showed significant differences between training and validation in box and DFL losses, confirming the research hypothesis. This suggests that while the model learns to localize defects during training,

it struggles to generalize precise bounding box predictions on unseen data. A possible explanation is the complex nature of 3D Printing defects, which often have irregular shapes, unclear edges, or blend into the background, making accurate boundary localization challenging. Minor variations in lighting, resolution, and filament texture also affect how the model interprets object edges. Since the results confirmed a significant difference between training and validation losses, the hypothesis is accepted. While this indicates limitations in localization performance, the stability of classification loss reflects strong generalization in identifying defect types. This confirms the reliability of the system in providing accurate real-time alerts for defect detection in additive manufacturing and supports its role in early error detection and quality assurance.

6.1.2 Determine the Accuracy in Terms of Precision, Recall, and mAP50 of YOLOv10-S in Classifying Among the Different Anomalies and Between RGB and Grayscale Images

The YOLOv10-S model demonstrated strong classification performance across anomaly types, with Spaghetti anomalies consistently achieving the highest precision, recall, and mAP50 scores, and Extrusion anomalies the lowest. RGB imaging outperformed Grayscale across all performance metrics, with statistically significant improvements in precision, while differences in recall and mAP50 were not consistently significant. The paired t-test and MANOVA results showed statistically significant effects of both color mode and anomaly type on performance metrics, supported by estimated marginal means. The hypothesis that anomaly type and color

mode significantly affect detection performance is accepted. These findings indicate that image modality influences detection reliability, with Grayscale performing better for Warping and RGB performing better for most other anomalies. For practical implementation, RGB was selected as the default image setting due to its consistently superior performance across most anomaly types, supporting a reliable real-time monitoring system for diverse 3D printing conditions.

6.2 Recommendations

This section outlines strategic recommendations to optimize the application and performance of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting 3D Printing anomalies. These suggestions address key areas for improvement, including enhancing dataset diversity to improve model generalization, fine-tuning model configurations for optimal performance, and expanding the anomaly detection scope to cover a broader range of printing defects. Implementation of these recommendations ensures better applicability across diverse printing environments and enhances real-world performance in industrial and commercial settings.

6.2.1 Dataset and Anomaly Scope Expansion

Further enhancement of model performance requires expanding both the dataset and the range of detectable 3D printing anomalies. While the current dataset focuses on defects such as extrusion, spaghetti, stringing, and warping, future improvements include more complex anomalies such as thermal inconsistencies, nozzle clogs, dimensional inaccuracies, layer shifting, layer separation, weak infill, and bonding

issues. By incorporating a wider variety of materials, printing environments, and printer models strengthens the generalization capability of the model across diverse conditions. Access to larger and higher-quality datasets also improves learning from more representative samples, resulting in increased detection accuracy and reliability. This expansion enhances the adaptability and practical value of the model for a wide range of 3D printing users.

6.2.2 Web-Based Interface for Enhanced User Interaction

To make the anomaly detection system more accessible and user-friendly, a web-based application is developed to make it available to a wide range of users and to allow intuitive interaction with the model. This application features real-time anomaly detection, the ability to upload and process 3D Printing images, and offers troubleshooting suggestions based on detected anomalies. Offline access capabilities ensure functionality even in areas with limited internet connectivity, making it a valuable tool for professionals working in remote or resource-limited settings.

6.2.3 Multiple Camera Angles Implementation

It is recommended that multiple camera configurations be placed around the 3D Printer in order to get a more complete picture of the printing process. This helped the system detect anomalies more effectively by minimizing blind areas and providing multiple perspectives, particularly for complicated prints. A multi-angle setup considerably increases detection performance for minor or concealed flaws that are not evident from a single perspective.

6.2.4 3D Printer Automatic Stop or Pause Functionality Integration

The system improved further by connecting it directly with the firmware or control interface of the 3D Printer, allowing it to stop or pause automatically when anomalies are discovered. This real-time intervention reduces material waste and allows users to solve issues before they become widespread, boosting efficiency, lowering costs, and limiting environmental effect. Additionally, automated response mechanisms eliminate the need for constant human monitoring, enabling unattended printing operations while maintaining quality assurance, which is particularly valuable for overnight production runs or high-volume manufacturing environments where continuous supervision is impractical.

The findings and insights presented consolidate the effectiveness of the YOLOv10-S model in detecting and classifying common 3D printing anomalies while also highlighting areas that require further refinement. The study confirms strong classification performance across anomaly types and image modalities, alongside observed limitations in bounding box localization that informed the proposed recommendations. These recommendations build directly on the conclusions drawn from the experimental results, focusing on improving data diversity, system responsiveness, and practical deployment features. Taken together, the conclusions and recommendations provide a cohesive foundation for advancing real-time anomaly detection systems and contribute to the development of reliable and efficient quality assurance solutions in additive manufacturing.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

For the smooth operation of all the applications within the development cycle, the project management section is of importance while outlining the required resources and respective planning for the effective implementation of the study on 3D Printing anomaly detection and classification using YOLOv10-S. This section details the hardware and software requirements for various applications, the tools that are needed for developing and deploying them, and a timeline of completing the real-time monitoring software successfully. It is critical to comply with the requirements to have efficient performance during the project implementation and performance.

A. Hardware Requirements

For the development of real-time monitoring software, it is critical to ensure efficient performance and reliability. The hardware requirements are divided into two categories: Model Training and Software Testing/Deployment. Model training demands high-performance computing resources for processing large datasets and optimizing neural network parameters, while software testing and deployment require stable hardware capable of real-time inference and continuous monitoring operations.

1. Model Training

During the training of the machine learning models for object detection and anomaly detection, it is required to have sufficient computational power to handle large datasets,

complex algorithms, and long training periods. It is of utmost importance to have the minimum, if possible, recommended hardware to effectively perform the study and processes included. The primary hardware requirements for this stage include:

- Graphics Processing Unit (GPU): NVIDIA RTX 30-series or better and these are the required GPUs that are specifically designed to support deep-learning model training, reducing the training time significantly.
- Central Processing Unit (CPU): Intel i5 or AMD Ryzen 5. Multi-core processors are required to perform all the preprocessing operations, enhance data, and all other system functions that the GPU does not take care of.
- Memory: A minimum RAM of 16GB is required to produce models without delays or memory errors. For larger datasets and complex models, 32GB is preferred.
- Storage: A minimum of 500GB Solid-State Drive (SSD) is recommended. This is used for data storage pertaining to model weights, logs, and other project-related files. SSDs have faster access times compared to traditional hard drives.

2. Software Testing

One crucial step in ensuring that the trained model functions correctly and reliably under different circumstances is testing the software. After the model is trained, it is deployed in the software to test how it behaves in real-time situations and guarantee it works as expected. The following are the hardware specifications to ensure smooth testing and deployment across different environments:

- Computer/Laptop: A computer that has high-processing power, i.e., Intel i5 or Ryzen 5 or more advanced, is required to accommodate the software on real-time monitoring. In addition, a camera, or access to external cameras for capturing the real-time process of 3D Printing and detecting anomalies in the process.
- Peripheral Devices: A good quality camera that captures at least resolution 1080p to vividly capture details of the 3D Printing process to be used. Also, it uses either USB or Wi-Fi connectivity in order to easily connect to the software.

B. Software Requirements

Essential elements that the real-time monitoring software specifications describe are programming languages, the learning frameworks, libraries, and tools applied to configure a model for training and deployment. These components ensure the capabilities of the software to deal with complex operations such as real-time object detection, anomaly classification, and efficient decision-making. Precise selection of all these requirements creates a basis for a reliable, effective system designed for unique requirements to meet specific application needs.

The following discusses the detailed software requirements:

1. Programming Languages

- Python: It is the primary development language of the software. It is versatile and functions well in the fields of machine learning and computer

vision. This is where the core functionality of the real-time monitoring software is created, including the integration of the YOLO model to perform anomaly detection.

2. Machine Learning Frameworks

I. You Only Look Once (YOLO)

- The object detection model YOLO is used to recognize objects in real-time. It is quick and efficient, therefore suitable for real-time anomaly detection in 3D Printing. The software uses a pre-tuned YOLO model that has been fine-tuned for specific anomalies peculiar to 3D Printing.

II. PyTorch

- The above machine learning frameworks allow the loading, fine-tuning, and running of YOLO. PyTorch is found to be flexible for research purposes.

C. Peopleware Recommendation

The successful utilization and maintenance of the Xplor3D anomaly detection system involve two distinct categories of human resources: the Researchers/Developers and the End-Users/Operators. The Researchers are responsible for the technical backbone, including the training of the YOLOv10-S model and software maintenance, ensuring the system evolves with new data. In contrast, the End-Users or Operators are responsible for the daily application of the software to monitor 3D printing processes, utilizing the interface to detect defects through live feeds or uploaded media.

1. Researchers/Developers

This group is tasked with the technical maintenance and future expansion of the system. They possess the authority and technical capability to modify the source code, manage the Python environment, and retrain the YOLOv10-S model using new datasets to improve accuracy or add new anomaly classes. These individuals are responsible for interpreting the training results page to assess model performance metrics such as precision, recall, and mAP50. Furthermore, they are tasked with implementing the advanced recommendations of the system, such as integrating the software directly with 3D printer firmware for automatic pausing. Their role ensures the system remains scalable, reliable, and adaptable.

2. End-Users/3D Printer Operators

This category includes individuals from prototyping businesses, educational institutions, or manufacturing industries who utilize the system for quality control. These users do not require in-depth machine learning knowledge but are expected to be proficient in operating the Xplor3D graphical user interface. Their primary tasks include setting up the physical hardware (camera positioning and lighting), initiating the "Start Monitoring" function for real-time detection, and uploading images or videos for post-print analysis. They are also responsible for acting upon the visual and audio alerts generated by the system, using the provided suggestions to correct printing errors like spaghetti or warping. By effectively responding to these automated notifications, operators minimize material waste and prevent the mechanical damage that often results from undetected printing failures.

D. System Budget

To ensure the effective development and deployment of the Xplor3D system, a financial framework was established to secure the necessary hardware and software resources, amounting to a total budget of Php 54,994.00. As detailed in Appendix F, the development phase incurred no direct monetary costs, attributable to the strategic utilization of open-source technologies and platforms such as Python and Google Colab. This approach significantly mitigated financial overhead by leveraging accessible computational resources for model training.

Consequently, fiscal resources were primarily directed toward acquiring hardware infrastructure capable of sustaining the computational prerequisites of the YOLOv10-S model. A mid-range laptop featuring a dedicated Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) was procured at a cost of Php 47,995.00 to facilitate local testing and deployment. Additionally, an expenditure of Php 6,999.00 was allocated for the Windows 11 Operating System license to guarantee a stable and compatible ecosystem for the user interface and associated development tools.

E. Operational Setup Recommendations

To make the application run in its optimal performance, the following recommendations are made for the operational setup during the deployment. The following recommendations are the minimum standard to deploy the application while avoiding unnecessary interruptions efficiently. This includes recommendations on how the lighting of the printing area, the minimum hardware requirements for the camera, and how far the camera from the product being printed.

1. Lighting

Ensure the 3D Print is well-lit from multiple angles to avoid shadows. Consistent, diffuse lighting is ideal in this type of situation. Avoid harsh, direct spotlights that create glare or deep shadows, which is misinterpreted by the model.

2. Hardware

A camera with a resolution of at least 1080p is recommended for clear anomaly detection. This is to make sure that the camera captures the product being printed clearly. Ensure the camera is stable and does not vibrate with the movements of the printer.

3. Camera Distance

Position the camera close enough to capture fine details of the print, but far enough to see the entire object. A distance of 30-50 cm is often a good starting point, depending on the size of the print. Adjust the distance as needed to maintain focus and ensure that the entire printing area stays within the frame.

F. Time Management

Effective time management is paramount for the successful completion of the study, utilizing a Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) approach to structure distinct phases as detailed in Appendix D. The project initiates with a foundational period of six weeks dedicated to system planning, conceptualizing, and title proposal, ensuring a clear research

direction. This is immediately followed by two weeks of defining project specifics, with one week each allocated to identifying project requirements and functionalities to establish operational baselines. Subsequently, the focus shifts to resource acquisition and theoretical grounding, comprising a three-week data gathering phase and a concurrent four-week research period for literature review and model selection. This parallel execution of data gathering and research activities maximizes efficiency by allowing simultaneous progress on multiple project components while maintaining interdependencies between phases.

The technical execution phase builds upon this foundation, beginning with model training and evaluation, which spans four weeks to optimize the machine learning algorithms. This is followed by a four-week coding phase focused on developing the core features and user interface of the system. To ensure system reliability, a three-week software testing period covers unit, debugging, and integration testing. The timeline concludes with a four-week phase for final evaluation, documentation, and thesis writing, synthesizing the research findings and finalizing the project deliverables. This structured timeline provides clear milestones for monitoring progress while maintaining flexibility to adapt to emerging requirements or refinements discovered during implementation.

GLOSSARY

A. ACCURACY

The performance of the model is measured based on the correct detection rate and classification of the models out of all the instances in which it detects and classifies an anomaly [HP2024].

B. ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING (AM)

A process of creating objects by adding material layer by layer, commonly known as 3D Printing.

C. BLOB AND ZITS

Small, raised spots or lumps on the print surface caused that form when excess filament accumulates during printing.

D. BOX LOSS

Evaluates how accurately the predicted bounding boxes of the model align with the objects in the images. When an annotator aligns an object in an image, box loss measures the degree of error between the created outline and the actual placement of the object in the images. [TJ2024].

E. CLASSIFICATION

A machine learning task where the model categorizes data into predefined labels, such as different types of 3D Printing anomalies. This approach enables automated organization and interpretation of complex data for more efficient analysis.

F. CLASS LOSS

Type of loss functions that works in order to make sure the model correctly classifies detected objects, this loss gauges the precision of class predictions using cross-entropy [VL2024].

G. CONFUSION MATRIX

Used to evaluate classification model performance by displaying the numbers of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives [BA2024].

H. DATA AUGMENTATION

Techniques used to increase dataset size by modifying or generating data to improve model training, especially with imbalanced data.

I. DETECTION

Identifying unusual patterns or defects within data is either be positive (anomaly detected) or negative (no anomaly detected).

J. DISTRIBUTION FOCAL LOSS

By extending Focal Loss, the Distribution Focal Loss function improves gradient behavior and class imbalance handling, resulting in better performance on difficult samples [KE2025].

K. F1 SCORE

A type of metric used to assess machine learning models, emphasizing their performance across different classes instead of just overall accuracy. [KR2022].

L. FUSED DEPOSITION MODELING (FDM)

A widely used 3D Printing technique that extrudes thermoplastic material through a heated nozzle to build objects layer by layer.

M. LAYER SEPARATION/SPLITTING

Visible gaps or splits between printed layers due to poor interlayer bonding, typically caused by insufficient heat, inadequate extrusion, or incompatible material properties.

N. LAYER SHIFTING

A defect that occurs when printed layers become misaligned during the printing process, leading to a visibly distorted or skewed print geometry and reduced dimensional accuracy.

O. MACHINE LEARNING (ML)

A branch of artificial intelligence in which models learn from historical or real-time data to identify patterns, make predictions, or support decision-making, often applied to tasks such as anomaly detection in 3D Printing to automatically recognize defects and improve process quality.

P. MEAN AVERAGE PRECISION

The measure of performance of object detection and localization algorithms. The average AP for each of the classes in question is used to get the mean average accuracy [AA2022].

Q. ONE-WAY MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (MANOVA)

To find out if independent groups differ on more than one continuous dependent variable, one-way MANOVA, is utilized. It is not the same as a one-way ANOVA, which only measures one dependent variable, in this respect [LS2024].

R. PAIRED T-TEST

The means of two measurements made from the same person, item, or related units are compared using the Paired T-test [KS2024].

S. PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

A type of correlation measure that shows the relationship between two variables assessed on the same interval or ratio scale [KW2024].

T. PRECISION

It measures how well a model finds true positives out of all true positives and false positives. To put it simply, Precision is the ratio of all the Positives to True Positives [HP2024].

U. RECALL

A metric that measures the proportion of actual positive instances that the model successfully identified out of all true positive cases present in the dataset [BA2024].

V. SPAGHETTI

An anomaly where filament forms stringy, thin lines resembling spaghetti noodles due to excessive extrusion during travel moves between print sections.

W. STRINGING

It refers to fine threads of filament forming between parts of the print, while oozing involves excess material dripping from the nozzle, leaving small blobs or strands.

X. TRAINING LOSS

It evaluates the errors of the models on the training set. Keep in mind that the training set is a subset of the dataset that was used to train the model in the first place. The total of the errors for every example in the training set is used to compute the training loss [BD2024].

Y. UNDER EXTRUSION

Under-extrusion occurs when insufficient filament is extruded, leading to gaps or weak spots.

Z. VALIDATION LOSS

Measure that evaluates how well a deep learning model performs on the validation set. The validation loss, which is determined by adding up the errors for every example in the validation set, is comparable to the training loss [BD2024].

AA. WARPING

Parts of the print lift or separate from the build platform as the material cools and contracts, causing the edges or corners to warp upward.

BB. YOU ONLY LOOK ONCE (YOLO)

An object detection model used in real-time applications, optimized in versions like YOLOv10-S for efficiency in detecting objects in dense datasets.

LIST OF SCREENSHOTS

1. Download Link	2
2. Xplor3D File System Downloaded.....	2
3. Splash Screen.....	2
4. Introduction Video	2
5. Home Page.....	2
6. Live Monitoring Session.....	2
7. Upload Images	2
8. Navigation Buttons	2
9. Replay and Stop Button	2
10. Anomaly Details	2
11. Log Results	2
12. Brightness Alert	2
13. Menu	2
14. Model Page	2
15. Training Results Page	2
16. Manual Page.....	2
17. Close Button.....	2

USERS' MANUAL

TABLE OF CONTENTS

A. Overview140

B. How to Access the Application141

C. Application Manual.....143

USERS' MANUAL

This user manual provides detailed guidance for navigating and utilizing Xplor3D, a system developed to detect and classify anomalies in 3D printing processes. Designed for both beginners and experienced users, the manual explains how to install the application, operate the live camera feed, and upload images or videos for analysis. Step-by-step instructions, visual aids, and practical tips are provided to ensure accurate and efficient use of each feature. By following this guide, users are allowed to interact with the system confidently, understand generated results, and optimize the performance of Xplor3D for real-time monitoring and anomaly detection.

A. Overview

Xplor3D delivers a user-friendly and efficient platform for detecting and classifying anomalies during 3D printing processes. The use of the YOLOv10-S model alongside real-time image and video processing, the system supports monitoring through uploaded media or live camera feeds. The interface accommodates both novice and advanced operators, offering structured workflows and clear instructions for the correct operation of each tool. This manual emphasizes essential instructions, recommended practices, and important reminders to ensure proper system use and prevent operational errors. By following the guidelines, it enables users to fully exploit the capabilities of Xplor3D for research applications or practical 3D printing monitoring tasks.

B. How to Access the Application

Step 1: Access the Download Link

To obtain the Xplor3D application, the user accesses the link “<https://tinyurl.com/Xplor3d>”, which directs to a Google Drive page where the application files are stored, as illustrated in Screenshot 1. The page displays the file name, file size, last modified date, and other details, allowing the user to confirm that the correct version of the application is selected and ensuring that no outdated or incomplete files are downloaded. Since the file exceeds the preview size limit, a notification appears indicating that the file cannot be previewed. The user proceeds by selecting the Download button to save the application file to the device. This method provides a direct and efficient way to access the software without additional navigation steps.

Screenshot 1. Download Link.

Step 2: Extract and Open the Application

Once the download is completed, the application is stored as a compressed ZIP file. The user extracts the contents of the ZIP file to a designated folder on the device. It is recommended to keep all extracted files together in the same folder to ensure that the application functions correctly and that all required resources are accessible. Additionally, users are advised to review the README file for any specific instructions or system requirements before launching the application.

As shown in Screenshot 2, the extracted files include a README file and the Xplor3D executable. The executable file serves as the main entry point for running the application. To start the system, the user opens the Xplor3D executable file by double-clicking it. The application initializes and loads the main interface, enabling access to the features of the system for anomaly detection and analysis in 3D printing. This installation and launch process allows the application to be used immediately after extraction.

Screenshot 2. Xplor3D File System Downloaded.

C. Application Manual

The splash screen is the first page displayed when opening the application. As shown in Screenshot 3, it displays the “Xplor3D” header, a tagline, and a short description of its real-time anomaly detection features. A “Start Exploring” button is also displayed, which initiates the application. This page provides an overview of the purpose of the system and helps orient the user before proceeding to the next screen.

Screenshot 3. Splash Screen.

After clicking “Start Exploring,” an introduction video plays, as shown in Screenshot 4. The video explains the types of anomalies the system detects and how they appear during a print. It provides a brief overview of the main functionalities of the application and prepares the user for navigating the interface efficiently. If the user prefers to skip the video, the “Skip Intro” button directs the user straight to the Home Page. The video serves as a simple visual guide before the application features are accessed.

Screenshot 4. Introduction Video.

The Home Page, shown in Screenshot 5, allows the user to select how data is provided to the system. The user selects either live monitoring or uploads images and videos using the buttons on the right side of the interface. By clicking “Start Monitoring”, it activates the camera for real-time detection. For analysis of existing prints, the options “Detect from Image(s)” or “Detect from Video” are available. This page offers flexible inspection options depending on the needs of the user.

Screenshot 5. Home Page.

Upon clicking “Start Monitoring,” the system begins analyzing the print in real time. As shown in Screenshot 6, a pop-up alert appears when an anomaly is detected, accompanied by an audio warning to immediately capture the attention of the user. The user selects “Continue Monitoring” if the issue is minor or ends the session by selecting “Stop Monitoring” when necessary.

Screenshot 6. Live Monitoring Session.

The detected anomaly is visually highlighted on the live feed through bounding boxes, enabling clearer identification of the affected area. All interactions with alerts are logged in the system for later review and analysis, supporting documentation and continuous improvement. In addition, the monitoring process continues seamlessly after the alert is addressed. This feature supports immediate response during an active print and helps prevent minor defects from escalating into major failures.

User uploads images for anomaly detection using the Upload Buttons, specifically the “Detect From Image(s)” button, as shown in Screenshot 7. After clicking the “Detect From Image(s)” button, a task manager appears as a modal window, allowing the user to select one or more images for analysis. The system supports both single and multiple image uploads, enabling efficient processing of multiple print samples in a single session. Once the images are selected, the application automatically prepares them for detection and displays the results after analysis is completed.

Screenshot 7. Upload Images.

As shown in Screenshot 8, the uploaded image is displayed on the left section of the Home Page along with bounding boxes indicating detected anomalies. When multiple images are uploaded, navigation arrows appear, allowing the user to move between images. This feature enables individual inspection of each image and supports anomaly analysis without relying on live monitoring.

Screenshot 8. Navigation Buttons.

The “Detect from Video” button allows video uploads for analysis, as shown in Screenshot 9. Videos are selected and uploaded using the same process as image uploads. The system scans the entire video to identify anomalies that occur during the printing process. Video playback controls allow replay or interruption of the analysis. This feature is useful for reviewing prints recorded prior to system use.

Screenshot 9. Replay and Stop Button.

When an anomaly is detected, detailed information appears on the right panel, as shown in Screenshot 10. The displayed details include the anomaly type, the frame in which it occurred, and the detection confidence level. Additional information, such as the location of the anomaly within the image, allows the user to quickly identify the affected area. The system also provides recommended actions to address the issue, guiding the user in taking appropriate steps to prevent further defects or errors during the printing process.

Screenshot 10. Anomaly Details.

When an anomaly is detected, the user selects “Log Results” to open the report modal shown in Screenshot 11. The modal organizes all relevant information in a clear and accessible format for the user. The modal includes the anomaly type, a description of its characteristics, possible causes, and suggested solutions. The report is saved locally for documentation or future reference. This feature allows systematic recording of detected issues and supports long-term review of the printing process.

Screenshot 11. Log Results.

During live monitoring, the system evaluates whether the environment lighting is too bright or too dark. The system immediately detects changes in lighting and updates the warning icon in real time. As shown in Screenshot 12, a warning icon appears on the upper-right section of the Home Page when lighting conditions are suboptimal. This alert prompts lighting adjustments to improve detection accuracy. The brightness alert operates continuously to ensure consistent visual conditions throughout the monitoring session. Proper lighting enhances image clarity and overall system performance.

Screenshot 12. Brightness Alert.

The menu shown in Screenshot 13 allows the user to move easily between different pages of the application. It includes links to the home, model, training results, and manual pages, organized in a way that keeps everything within reach. Each button takes the user directly to the selected section, reducing the need to navigate through multiple steps. The menu layout is simple and easy to follow, and its consistent placement helps users get familiar with the interface more quickly.

Screenshot 13. Menu.

The Model Page, shown in Screenshot 14, presents key information about the YOLOv10 model integrated into the application. It explains the architecture, feature extraction, and decision-making processes of the model, highlighting its role in real-time anomaly detection for 3D Printing. The page also emphasizes the advantages of the model, including high detection accuracy, low latency, and efficient processing of visual data, and illustrates how it identifies patterns and differentiates between normal and defective print features.

MODEL

You Only Look Once version 10 (YOLOv10)

YOLOv10 is one of the latest innovations in the YOLO (You Only Look Once) family, developed to deliver highly accurate, end-to-end object detection with minimal latency. Building upon the strengths of its predecessors, YOLOv10 introduces a refined architecture that significantly enhances real-time performance, even in complex environments.

This version integrates large-kernel convolutions and a dual-pathway mechanism to boost both accuracy and efficiency. Notably, YOLOv10 eliminates the need for Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) during inference, thereby simplifying the detection pipeline and reducing computational load. Its adaptive anchor-free detection system effectively addresses challenges such as occlusion and small object recognition, while a lightweight classification head and spatial-channel decoupled downsampling contribute to maintaining high speed without compromising detection quality.

— Home Results —

Screenshot 14. Model Page.

The Training Results Page, shown in Screenshot 15, provides a summary of the findings from training the YOLOv10-S model. It includes graphs, charts, and tables that illustrate the performance of the model across various metrics, testing conditions, and variables such as print quality, object geometry, and environmental factors. These results demonstrate the ability of the model to accurately detect anomalies and reveal patterns learned during training.

Screenshot 15. Training Results Page.

The User Manual Page, shown in Screenshot 16, offers comprehensive guidance on operating the system and using its features effectively. It includes labeled images, detailed step-by-step instructions, and recommended settings, such as optimal lighting conditions, camera placement, and hardware positioning for accurate detection. The page also provides notes on best practices, troubleshooting tips, and explanations of interface elements to help the user perform tasks efficiently. The use of interactive examples and visual demonstrations help users understand complex procedures and ensure proper execution of each function. By scrolling through the page, allows the user to access complete instructions for all system components, ensuring that the user is well-equipped to operate the application successfully and maximize its functionality in real-time anomaly detection. The manual also explains interface elements in detail and includes notes to help users avoid common mistakes while performing anomaly detection tasks.

Screenshot 16. Manual Page.

To exit the Xplor3D application, click the close button represented by the “X” icon located at the top-right corner of the interface, as shown in Screenshot 17. This action immediately closes the program and stops all active processes, including live monitoring and any ongoing detection tasks. Before closing, ensure that all results, logs, or analyzed files have been saved to prevent data loss. When the application is closed during active monitoring, the action interrupt detection, so it is recommended to stop monitoring before exiting.

Screenshot 17. Close Button.

By following this manual, users are able to operate Xplor3D efficiently and respond to detected anomalies during 3D printing. The instructions and visual guides support accurate monitoring, proper handling of alerts, and systematic logging of results. Users are equipped to maintain consistent print quality, troubleshoot issues, and make informed adjustments in real time. This ensures that the system functions reliably and contributes to more effective and precise 3D printing operations.

APPENDIX A

Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.
(Adopted from Philippine Association of Institutions for Research (PAIR), Inc.)

WE, the researcher, and research adviser/consultant, have worked together in a capstone project from August 2024 to January 2026.

WE have used various forms of contact during the thesis work such as Microsoft Teams, Facebook and other means of communication.

WE agree that :

- the academic partnership leads to publication of the manuscript with the research consultant as the author and the researcher, the primary author.
- the paper be presented in public forum by the researcher if available at such an opportunity or by the research adviser/consultant if the researcher is no longer around.
- only the name of the oral presenter shall be submitted to the Conference organizer.

WE agree to dress formally and prepare adequately for the formal oral presentation in both the oral defense panel and the public presentations.

Signed this 27th of July in the year of our Lord 2025 in Bacolod City, Philippines.

KAREN KAYE T. ALFONSO
Researcher

ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Technical Consultant/Adviser

JAENHELE M. MENCION
Researcher

CRISTINA E. BALIGUAT
Witness

ERN JAN A. PAINAGA
Researcher

APPENDIX B

Minutes of The Thesis Project Proposal Defense.

December 19, 2024 | 10:00 AM – 11:00 AM
 College of Information Technology
 University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos

Thesis Proposal Title	YOLOv10-S for 3D-Printing Anomaly Detection and Classification
Group Members	Karen Kaye T. Alfonso Jaenhel E. Mencidor Ern Jan A. Painaga
Panel Members	Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS Reymund L. Sabay, MBE, D.B.M
Interpellators	Rommel M. Bitco Daniel Jun S. Lamaton Rafael Jacov C. Medel

1. The group members were introduced by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso.
2. The oral presentation was delivered by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso.
3. After the presentation, questions were raised, and the following are the suggestions and recommendations from the interpellators and panel members.

Chapter/Section	Recommendation/Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken
Introduction	Analyze the model performance when trained on RGB versus Grayscale images.	Elmer T. Haro, Mehreen E. Dolendo	Addition of Statement of the Problem 3
Methodology	Consider adding data augmentation when processing the dataset.	Elmer T. Haro, Mehreen E. Dolendo	The option was not considered due to time constraint problems of the project implementation.
Methodology	Explain how the project is to be implemented.	Elmer T. Haro	Model Deployment section was added to methodology section, discussing the specific

			devices to be used for implementation.
Methodology	Evaluate whether the device specifications are suitable for training the model.	Rafael Jacov C. Medel	The Methodology section now specifies that a mid-range laptop was used as the training device, supported by a study
Prototype/Interface	Describe how the model detects anomalies during live-feed video of the process.	Elmer T. Haro, Mehreen E. Dolendo	Discussed in the methodology where camera captures each frame of the live feed video.
Prototype/Interface	Implement a progress bar to display the status of the printing process.	Reymund L. Sabay	A progress bar for the printing process was added to the graphical interface.
Prototype/Interface	Add color specifications based on the type of anomaly detected.	Reymund L. Sabay	The graphical interface was modified to have color specifications based on the type of anomaly detected.
Prototype/Interface	Set threshold for when the model detects an event as an anomaly.	Elmer T. Haro	The researchers have chosen the threshold of 0.5 for the IOU.
Prototype/Interface	Clarify what constitutes “early” in the context of early detection.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	An explanation was added to the Model Deployment of the Methodology section.

4. After the deliberations and clarifications of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with minor revisions in introduction and methodology of the documentation and in the prototype.
5. The conference ended at 11:00 AM

Transcribed by: Jaenhel E. Mencidor

Noted by: Elmer T. Haro, PhD.

APPENDIX C

Minutes of The Thesis Final Defense.

May 29, 2025 | 4:00 PM – 5:30 PM
 College of Information Technology
 University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos

Thesis Proposal Title	YOLOv10-S for 3D-Printing Anomaly Detection and Classification
Group Members	Karen Kaye T. Alfonso Jaenhel E. Mencidor Ern Jan A. Painaga
Panel Members	Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS Reymund L. Sabay, MBE, D.B.M
Interpellators	Rommel M. Bitco Daniel Jun S. Lamaton Rafael Jacov C. Medel

1. The group members were introduced by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso.
2. The oral presentation was delivered by Karen Kaye T. Alfonso.
3. After the presentation, questions were raised, and the following are the suggestions and recommendations from the interpellators and panel members.

Chapter/Section	Recommendation/Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken
Methodology	Justify the chosen 25% threshold of the model.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Added in Chapter 5 of the documentation.
Results and Analysis.	Include the threshold experimentation results.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Tables of the results related to the threshold is added in Chapter 5.
Conclusion and Recommendations.	Add to recommendation the multiple angles of camera for the application implementation.	Rommel M. Bitco	Recommendation of using multiple cameras for different angles in added in Chapter 6.
Conclusion and Recommendations.	Recommend requirements, hardware, lighting, and	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Suitable environment such as hardware and lighting requirements is

	proper environment for the implementation of the system.		indicated in Chapter 6 as well as in the application itself.
Prototype/Interface	Notify the light environment whether the subject is too bright or too dark.	Rafael Jacov C. Medel	An alert that notifies the user whenever the subject is too bright or too dark is added in the application.
Prototype/Interface	Adding the replay video button.	Mehreen E. Dolendo	A replay button is added in the application which is used whenever a video uploaded is finished playing.
Prototype/Interface	Report generation of the detection and recommendation of the course action.	Reymund L. Sabay	The home screen displays detected anomalies, providing users with key details and specific recommendations for action.
Prototype/Interface	Stopping 3D Printing whenever an anomaly is detected.	Reymund L. Sabay Daniel Jun S. Lamaton	Due to time and resources constraints, a modal that pops out with audio and visual alerts is added to notify the user when an anomaly is detected.

4. After the deliberations and clarifications of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with minor revisions in introduction and methodology of the documentation and in the prototype.

The conference ended at 5:30 PM

Transcribed by: Jaenhel B. Mencidor

Noted by: Elmer T. Haro, PhD.

APPENDIX D

PERT Table.

Activity	Description	Predecessor	a	m	b	ET	ES	EF	LS	LF	Slack
A	System Planning, Conceptualizing, and Title Proposal	-	4	6	8	6	0	6	0	6	0
B	Identify Project Requirements	A	1	1	1	1	6	7	6	7	0
C	Identify Project Functionalities	B	1	1	1	1	7	8	7	8	0
D	Data Gathering	C	2	3	5	3	8	11	8	11	0
E	Research (Literature Review and Model Selection)	C, D, B	3	4	5	4	11	15	11	15	0
F	Model Training and Evaluation	E, D	3	4	6	4	15	19	15	19	0
G	Coding (Development of Software and Core Features)	F, E, C	3	4	6	4	19	23	19	23	0
H	Software Testing (Unit Testing, Debugging, and Integration Testing)	F, G	2	3	5	3	23	26	23	26	0
I	Final Evaluation, Documentation, and Thesis Writing	H, G	3	4	6	4	26	30	26	30	0

APPENDIX E

Ethical Considerations.

Tool Used	Purpose	Prompt/Activity	Results	Location
ChatGPT	Creating Splash Screen to prompt user in starting the application.	Generate a splash screen to be added before loading the whole system that displays the logo and the tagline. Add also button that the user can click to start the application.	A Splash screen that appears while the application initializes.	First page that pops out when the application is clicked to start.
	Assistance in adding alert notification for brightness warning.	Add brightness warning during live camera feature is used by the user.	User is notified when the environment is too bright or too dark.	Upper section of the right container in home section during the live camera session.
	To ask for help fixing a problem where old detection results weren't clearing properly when new images or videos were uploaded.	Can you help me with my problem here as I am having trouble when new images are uploaded or video is uploaded the information about the detection is not properly removed	As new detections are made, previous detection information on the previously uploaded images and videos are cleared and replaced by the current information.	Anomaly Details in the Home Page during detection process.
	To ask for assistance in adding a brightness detection feature to the live camera feed.	Would you make it possible to add the feature wherein when the live camera feed feature is used and if the object or the environment is low on brightness it will show a	A simple warning sign indicating object is either too bright or too dark will appear whenever conditions are met.	Appears at the top of the Anomaly Details section in the Home Page during detection.

		warning on the right side as well as when it is too low?		
	Assist in expanding research ideas, paraphrasing technical content, and refining documentation.	Provide research-related prompts such as “expand this paragraph,” “summarize methodology,” or “rephrase in academic tone.”	Expanded and refined thesis content with improved clarity, coherence, and academic writing style.	Applied in Chapter I, Chapter II, and Chapter III for proper page formatting and spacing.
	Provide alternative wording for complex concepts.	Paraphrase this section in simpler academic language.	More accessible explanations that maintain technical accuracy.	Applied in Chapter II to improve readability and comprehension.
Gemini	Provide notification to immediately halt the printing operation.	Can you add a pop-up modal with audio queue that alerts user whenever an anomaly is detected during live camera feature.	A message box appears with audio alert that warns the user to pause printing.	Pop-up modal that is triggered when an anomaly is detected during live detection.
	Implement replay button for upload video feature.	I am having a problem inserting such feature, can you help add button that can replay the uploaded video once it is finished playing.	Button that the user clicks to replay the uploaded video to be processed again.	In home page during video processing under the video shown in the page.
Roboflow	Collect and organize dataset images suited for training the model.	Collect images of 3D printed product and processes that belongs to different anomaly type such as Extrusion Problems, Spaghetti,	Prepared and organized dataset ready for annotation, preprocessing, and training.	

		Stringing, and Warping.		
	Annotate the dataset images.	Uses annotation tools to specify the location and label respective anomaly type of the defects in the images of 3D printed products and process.	Images labeled with respective anomaly type ready for model training.	
	Application of preprocessing technique such as data augmentation.	Augmentations such as rotation between -10% and +10% and noise of up to 1.5% of pixels were applied to the training dataset.	Populated and enhanced the dataset images prepared for training the model.	
	Splitting dataset into three sets: training set, validation set, and test set.	Set correct number of images for each set that corresponds to the ratio 80:10:10.	Dataset organized into balanced subsets for the model performance to be assessed correctly.	
Grammarly	Ensure grammar, spelling, and tone correctness in thesis documentation.	Upload draft content or paste sections for grammar and clarity check.	Polished and error-free documentation for suitable academic submission.	All chapters (I–VI)
	Maintain formal academic writing style.	Use suggestions to rephrase informal or unclear statements.	Improved readability and adherence to academic writing standards.	All chapters (I–VI)
	Improve sentence structure and clarity.	Use suggestions to refine complex or run-on sentences.	Enhanced readability and flow of thesis writing.	All chapters (I–VI)
	Identify excessive	Review highlighted parts	Concise sentences with	Chapters II–V

	wording and redundancy.	that can be shortened.	reduced repetition.	
Jupyter Notebook	Serve as the main workspace for writing, running, and documenting code for the 3D printing anomaly detection project.	Used notebook cells to execute YOLOv10s model training, dataset preparation, and evaluation commands. Integrated code execution, visualization, and documentation in one environment.	Helped keep everything in one place, from datasets to results, making the workflow easy to follow and repeat.	
	Record and track model training progress.	Added cells for displaying graphs, outputs, and checkpoints during training and validation.	Allowed easy monitoring of training performance and saved results for review.	Output and markdown cells in the notebook.
	Document all experiment steps and parameters.	Included notes on dataset versions, model settings, and metrics. Combined visuals and explanations in one structured file.	Ensured a clear and reproducible record of the entire experiment.	
Google Colab	Provide cloud-based computing resources (GPU/CPU) to speed up model training and testing.	Used Colab's runtime to access GPU acceleration without needing a high-end local machine.	Training ran much faster and smoother, avoiding hardware limitations.	
	Manage datasets and trained models through Google Drive.	Mounted Google Drive to access dataset ZIP files and automatically save trained YOLOv10s model weights.	Data and model files were easily accessible and safely stored online.	
	Execute YOLO commands for	Ran shell commands like	Successfully trained models	

	training and validation.	!yolo train and !yolo val to train and test models on 3D printing datasets.	that detected extrusion problems, spaghetti, stringing, and warping.	
	Visualize and test results directly in the browser.	Viewed image outputs and model predictions without needing external software.	Quick and easy way to see detection results after each training session.	

APPENDIX F

System Budget.

Development Cost	Free
Hardware Cost	
Laptop	Php 47,995
Windows 11 Operating System	Php 6,999
TOTAL:	Php 54,994

APPENDIX G

Extrusion Problem Training Images (1-20).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (21-40).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (41-60).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (61-80).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (81-100).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (101-120).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (121-140).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (141-160).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (161-180).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (181-200).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (201-220).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (221-240).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (241-260).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (261-280).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (281-300).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (301-320).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (321-340).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (341-360).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (361-380).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (381-400).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (401-420).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (421-440).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (441-460).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (461-480).

Extrusion Problem Training Images (481-500).

APPENDIX H

Spaghetti Training Images (1-20).

Spaghetti Training Images (41-60).

Spaghetti Training Images (61-80).

Spaghetti Training Images (81-100).

Spaghetti Training Images (101-120).

Spaghetti Training Images (121-140).

Spaghetti Training Images (141-160).

Spaghetti Training Images (161-180).

Spaghetti Training Images (181-200).

Spaghetti Training Images (201-220).

Spaghetti Training Images (221-240).

Spaghetti Training Images (241-260).

Spaghetti Training Images (261-280).

Spaghetti Training Images (281-300).

Spaghetti Training Images (301-320).

Spaghetti Training Images (321-340).

Spaghetti Training Images (341-360).

Spaghetti Training Images (361-380).

Spaghetti Training Images (381-400).

Spaghetti Training Images (401-420).

Spaghetti Training Images (421-440).

Spaghetti Training Images (441-460).

Spaghetti Training Images (461-480).

APPENDIX I

Stringing Training Images (1-20).

Stringing Training Images (21-40).

Stringing Training Images (41-60).

Stringing Training Images (61-80).

Stringing Training Images (81-100).

Stringing Training Images (101-120).

Stringing Training Images (121-140).

Stringing Training Images (141-160).

Stringing Training Images (161-180).

Stringing Training Images (181-200).

Stringing Training Images (201-220).

Stringing Training Images (221-240).

Stringing Training Images (241-260).

Stringing Training Images (261-280).

Stringing Training Images (281-300).

Stringing Training Images (301-320).

Stringing Training Images (321-340).

Stringing Training Images (341-360).

Stringing Training Images (361-380).

Stringing Training Images (381-400).

Stringing Training Images (401-420).

Stringing Training Images (421-440).

Stringing Training Images (441-460).

Stringing Training Images (461-480).

Stringing Training Images (481-500).

APPENDIX J

Warping Training Images (1-20).

Warping Training Images (21-40).

Warping Training Images (41-60).

Warping Training Images (61-80).

Warping Training Images (81-100).

Warping Training Images (101-120).

Warping Training Images (121-140).

Warping Training Images (141-160).

Warping Training Images (161-180).

Warping Training Images (181-200).

Warping Training Images (201-220).

Warping Training Images (221-240).

Warping Training Images (241-260).

Warping Training Images (261-280).

Warping Training Images (281-300).

Warping Training Images (301-320).

Warping Training Images (321-340).

Warping Training Images (341-360).

Warping Training Images (361-380).

Warping Training Images (381-400).

Warping Training Images (421-440).

Warping Training Images (441-460).

Warping Training Images (461-480).

Warping Training Images (481-500).

APPENDIX K

Product Logo.

The Xplor3D logo features a stylized line-art illustration of a 3D printer nozzle extruding filament onto a print bed, providing a clear visual shorthand for the Fused Deposition Modeling process. This central icon is purposefully enclosed within a hexagonal frame composed of concentric lines. This specific geometric shape was selected to mirror the honeycomb infill patterns that are essential to additive manufacturing for optimizing structural integrity.

A gradient of vibrant cyan merging into deep royal blue serves as the foundational color scheme for Xplor3D. This transition is intended to symbolize the depth and clarity required for computer vision, evoking a balance between cutting-edge development and corporate stability. By incorporating sharp white highlights, the design ensures that the central 3D printing nozzle remains a focal point of technical accuracy within the modern interface.

APPENDIX L

Team Logo.

The logo integrates the letters "D" and "X" into a cohesive monogram, the logo utilizes the silhouette of a magnifying glass to represent the act of scientific discovery. The deliberate use of sharp, geometric angles in the lettering underscores the mathematical and technical accuracy required for computer vision research. Furthermore, the inclusion of the lens motif reinforces the focus of the study on visual inspection, specifically the identification of microscopic anomalies during the manufacturing phase.

The strategic palette of the logo uses deep blue and vibrant red to define the visual presence of the project. The blue components signify a disciplined, systematic methodology, while the contrasting red "X" serves as a focal point for the primary research objective. This color choice functions as a visual metaphor for the detection process, mirroring how computer vision systems flag defects in real-time.

APPENDIX M

Product Poster.

YOLOv10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION

SHARPER VISION FOR SMARTER PRINTING

1 RESEARCH DESCRIPTION

Additive manufacturing (3D printing) has transformed the way physical objects are produced, offering efficiency and flexibility compared to traditional methods. Affordable fused deposition modeling (FDM) printers have made this technology accessible to individuals and small businesses, but **print defects** remain a common issue. These defects cause **wasted time, resources, and materials**, contributing to plastic waste and higher costs. Addressing this problem supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), particularly **SDG 9 on sustainable industry** and **SDG 12 on responsible consumption and production**. To reduce waste and improve efficiency, this study develops a **real-time anomaly detection system** using YOLOv10-S to identify and classify 3D printing defects. By minimizing rework and defective outputs, the system aims to **enhance productivity, lower costs, and promote sustainability** in additive manufacturing.

9 SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRY AND INFRASTRUCTURE

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

2 OBJECTIVES

- Evaluate YOLOv10-S performance by comparing training loss and validation loss
- Determine accuracy in terms of precision, recall, and mAP50 when classifying anomalies
- Compare performance between RGB and grayscale images

3 METHODOLOGY

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Training vs. Validation Loss

Loss Type	p-value
Box	< 0.05
Class	0.03 - 0.47
DFL	< 0.05

Box and DFL losses (p-value <0.05) show significant differences, indicating a degree of overfitting in localization, while Class Loss shows no consistent difference, reflecting stable and reliable classification.

Performance per Anomaly Type

Anomaly	Precision	Recall	mAP50
Extrusion	0.52	0.53	0.49
Spaghetti	0.80	0.74	0.80
Stringing	0.69	0.62	0.67
Warping	0.65	0.70	0.65

Spaghetti shows the highest accuracy across all metrics, while Extrusion Problem has the lowest detection performance, making it the most challenging anomaly to classify.

Deployment Model Performance

The model showed stable performance across validation and test sets. The aligned scores demonstrate consistent and reliable anomaly detection across different data samples.

Performance in RGB

69.4% precision
66.6% recall
67.6% mAP50

Performance in Grayscale

63.8% precision
62.6% recall
63.2% mAP50

RGB images consistently outperformed Grayscale across all metrics, demonstrating that color information provides richer features for more accurate anomaly detection.

5 CONCLUSION

The YOLOv10-S model showed consistent accuracy across validation and test sets, indicating strong generalization with minimal overfitting. It performed best in detecting spaghetti, stringing, and warping, while extrusion remained more difficult to classify. The system proved dependable for real-time deployment, helping reduce failed prints, save materials, and improve the efficiency of 3D printing processes.

The per-anomaly comparison shows that Spaghetti was the easiest to detect with the highest accuracy across datasets. Stringing and Warping also performed well, with only minor drops between validation and test. Extrusion remained the most difficult to classify, showing the lowest accuracy.

Developed by: Karen Kaye T. Alfonso | Jaanel H. Mencilor | Ern Jan A. Painega

APPENDIX N

Product Packaging.

APPENDIX O

Grammarly Results (Chapter I-III).

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION CHAP 1-3

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

70,943	10,168	525	40 min 40 sec	1 hr 18 min
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

95

This text scores better than 95%
of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

129	1	128
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

1

%

122

sources

1% of your text matches 122 sources on the web
or in archives of academic publications

Report was generated on Friday, Jan 23, 2026, 02:07 PM Page 1 of 104

APPENDIX P

Grammarly Results (Chapter IV-VI).

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION CHAP 4-6

by UNO-R Researcher

General metrics

80,073	11,403	550	45 min 36 sec	1 hr 27 min
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

96

This text scores better than 96%
of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

<p style="font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold; margin: 0;">123</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">Issues left</p>	<p style="font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold; margin: 0;">✓</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">Critical</p>	<p style="font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold; margin: 0;">123</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">Advanced</p>
---	--	--

Plagiarism

2

%

160

sources

2% of your text matches 160 sources on the web
or in archives of academic publications

Report was generated on Friday, Jan 23, 2026, 02:37 PM Page 1 of 125

APPENDIX Q

Turnitin Results.

YOLOV10-S FOR 3D PRINTING ANOMALY DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION			
ORIGINALITY REPORT			
6% SIMILARITY INDEX	4% INTERNET SOURCES	4% PUBLICATIONS	3% STUDENT PAPERS

REFERENCES

A. Journal Articles

- {AL2021} Ashiku, Lirim, and Cihan Dagli. "Network Intrusion Detection System Using Deep Learning." *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 185, Jan. 2021, pp. 239–47, doi:10.1016/j.procs.2021.05.025.
- {BD2021} Bhatt, Dulari, et al. "CNN Variants for Computer Vision: History, Architecture, Application, Challenges and Future Scope." *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 20, Oct. 2021, p. 2470. doi.org/10.3390/electronics10202470.
- {BY2021} Bozkurt, Yahya, and Elif Karayel. "3D Printing technology; methods, biomedical applications, future opportunities and Trends." *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 14, Sept. 2021, pp. 1430–1450, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2021.07.050>.
- {DU2018} Delli, Ugandhar, and Shing Chang. "Automated Process Monitoring in 3D Printing Using Supervised Machine Learning." *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 26, Jan. 2018, pp. 865–70, doi:10.1016/j.promfg.2018.07.111.
- {DS2021} Dong, Shi, et al. "A Survey on Deep Learning and Its Applications." *Computer Science Review*, vol. 40, Mar. 2021, p. 100379, doi:10.1016/j.cosrev.2021.100379.
- {EK2020} Elif Karayel, and Bozkurt, Yahya. "Additive Manufacturing Method and Different Welding Applications." *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 5, Aug. 2020, pp. 11424–38, doi:10.1016/j.jmrt.2020.08.039.
- {FL2020} Floridi, Luciano. "AI and Its New Winter: From Myths to Realities." *Philosophy & Technology*, vol. 33, no. 1, Feb. 2020, pp. 1–3, doi:10.1007/s13347-020-00396-6.
- {HM2023} Hussain, Muhammad. "When, Where, and Which?: Navigating the Intersection of Computer Vision and Generative AI for Strategic Business Integration." *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, Jan. 2023, pp. 127202–15, doi:10.1109/access.2023.3332468.

- {HW2024} Hu, WenJing, et al. "Real-time Defect Detection for FFF 3D Printing Using Lightweight Model Deployment." *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 134, no. 9-10, Sept. 2024, pp. 4871–85, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-024-14452-4>.
- {JC2021} Janiesch, Christian, et al. "Machine Learning and Deep Learning." *Electronic Markets*, vol. 31, no. 3, Apr. 2021, pp. 685–95, doi:10.1007/s12525-021-00475-2.
- {JY2022} Jiang, Yuchen, et al. "Quo Vadis Artificial Intelligence?" *Discover Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 2, no. 1, Mar. 2022, doi:10.1007/s44163-022-00022-8.
- {JZ2023} Jiang, Zhouqian, and John I. Messner. "Computer Vision Applications in Construction and Asset Management Phases: A Literature Review." *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, vol. 28, Apr. 2023, pp. 176–99, doi:10.36680/j.itcon.2023.009.
- {KV2021} Kadam, Vaibhav, et al. "Real-Time Monitoring of FDM 3D Printer for Fault Detection Using Machine Learning: A Bibliometric Study." *Library Philosophy and Practice*, May 2021, digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5440/.
- {KA2020} Khan, Asifullah, et al. "A Survey of the Recent Architectures of Deep Convolutional Neural Networks." *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 53, no. 8, Apr. 2020, pp. 5455–516, doi:10.1007/s10462-020-09825-6.
- {LS2024} Lu, Shuai, et al. "Anomaly Detection for Medical Images Using Heterogeneous Auto-Encoder." *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 33, Jan. 2024, pp. 2770–82, doi:10.1109/tip.2024.3381435.
- {LY2019} Li, Yadan, et al. "YOLOv3-Lite: A Lightweight Crack Detection Network for Aircraft Structure Based on Depthwise Separable Convolutions." *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 18, Sept. 2019, p. 3781, doi:10.3390/app9183781.
- {MN2024} Manakitsa, Nikoleta, et al. "A Review of Machine Learning and Deep Learning for Object Detection, Semantic Segmentation, and Human Action Recognition in Machine and Robotic Vision." *Technologies*, vol. 12, no. 2, Jan. 2024, p. 15, doi:10.3390/technologies12020015.
- {PK2020} Paraskevoudis, Konstantinos, et al. "Real-Time 3D Printing Remote Defect Detection (Stringing) With Computer Vision and Artificial

- Intelligence.” *Processes*, vol. 8, no. 11, Nov. 2020, p. 1464, doi:10.3390/pr8111464.
- {PP2020} Penumakala, Pavan Kumar, et al. “A Critical Review on the Fused Deposition Modeling of Thermoplastic Polymer Composites.” *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 201, Nov. 2020, p. 108336, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.108336>.
- {SA2020} Saluja, Aditya, et al. “A Closed-loop In-process Warping Detection System for Fused Filament Fabrication Using Convolutional Neural Networks.” *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 58, Aug. 2020, pp. 407–15, doi:10.1016/j.jmapro.2020.08.036.
- {SI2021} Sarker, Iqbal H. “Deep Learning: A Comprehensive Overview on Techniques, Taxonomy, Applications and Research Directions.” *SN Computer Science*, vol. 2, no. 6, Aug. 2021, doi:10.1007/s42979-021-00815-1.
- {SM2023} Soori, Mohsen, et al. “Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning in Advanced Robotics, a Review.” *Cognitive Robotics*, vol. 3, Jan. 2023, pp. 54–70, doi:10.1016/j.cogr.2023.04.001.
- {TT2022} Tang, Ta-Wei, et al. “Industrial Anomaly Detection With Skip Autoencoder and Deep Feature Extractor.” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 23, Nov. 2022, p. 9327, doi:10.3390/s22239327.
- {TM2023} Taye, Mohammad Mustafa. “Theoretical Understanding of Convolutional Neural Network: Concepts, Architectures, Applications, Future Directions.” *Computation*, vol. 11, no. 3, Mar. 2023, p. 52, doi:10.3390/computation11030052.
- {TJ2023} Terven, Juan, et al. “A Comprehensive Review of YOLO Architectures in Computer Vision: From YOLOv1 to YOLOv8 and YOLO-NAS.” *Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction*, vol. 5, no. 4, 20 Nov. 2023, pp. 1680–1716, <https://doi.org/10.3390/make5040083>.
- {TC2022} Thakar, Chetan M., et al. “3D Printing: Basic Principles and Applications.” *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 51, 2022, pp. 842–849, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.06.272>.
- {TH2019} Tian, Hongkun, et al. “Computer Vision Technology in Agricultural Automation—A Review.” *Information Processing in Agriculture*, vol. 7, no. 1, Sept. 2019, pp. 1–19, doi:10.1016/j.inpa.2019.09.006.

- {WS2020} Wan, Shaohua, et al. "An Intelligent Video Analysis Method for Abnormal Event Detection in Intelligent Transportation Systems." *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 7, Sept. 2020, pp. 4487–95, doi:10.1109/tits.2020.3017505.
- {YR2021} Yang, Ruixin, and Yingyan Yu. "Artificial Convolutional Neural Network in Object Detection and Semantic Segmentation for Medical Imaging Analysis." *Frontiers in Oncology*, vol. 11, Mar. 2021, doi:10.3389/fonc.2021.638182.
- {ZC2021} Zhang, Caiming, and Yang Lu. "Study on Artificial Intelligence: The State of the Art and Future Prospects." *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, vol. 23, May 2021, p. 100224, doi:10.1016/j.jii.2021.100224.

B. Website/Blogs

- {WR2021} 6Wresearch. "Philippines 3D Printing Market: Trends & Outlook 2030." *Philippines 3D Printing Market | Trends & Outlook 2030*, www.6wresearch.com/industry-report/philippines-3d-printing-market. Accessed 1 Oct. 2024.
- {AN2023} Ahmed, Nisha Arya. "Mean Average Precision (mAP): A Complete Guide." *Kili-website*, 2023, kili-technology.com/data-labeling/machine-learning/mean-average-precision-map-a-complete-guide.
- {AA2022} Anwar, Aqeel. "What Is Average Precision in Object Detection and Localization Algorithms and How to Calculate It?" *Medium*, 13 July 2022, medium.com/towards-data-science/what-is-average-precision-in-object-detection-localization-algorithms-and-how-to-calculate-it-3f330efe697b.
- {AS2024} Arya, Sahitya. "YOLOv10: Revolutionizing Real-Time Object Detection." *Analytics Vidhya*, 15 July 2024, www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2024/07/yolov10-for-realtime-object-detection.
- {BA2024} Bhandari, Aniruddha. "Confusion Matrix in Machine Learning - Analytics Vidhya." *Analytics Vidhya*, 18 Nov. 2024,

- www.analyticsvidhya.com/articles/confusion-matrix-in-machine-learning.
- {EA2025} Evidently AI. "How to Use Classification Threshold to Balance Precision and Recall." www.evidentlyai.com/classification-metrics/classification-threshold.
- {EM2024} Elgendy, Mohamed. AI Failure Detection in 3D Printing | Obico Knowledge Base, 23 July 2024, www.obico.io/blog/ai-failure-detection-in-3d-printing.
- {HM2023} Hogan, Madeline. "Ultimate List of 3D Printing Statistics & Trends [2023]." Nexa3D, 13 Oct. 2023, nexa3d.com/blog/3d-printing-statistics/.
- {HP2024} Huilgol, Purva. "Precision and Recall in Machine Learning - Analytics Vidhya." Analytics Vidhya, 18 Nov. 2024, www.analyticsvidhya.com/articles/precision-and-recall-in-machine-learning/#What_Is_a_Confusion_Matrix?
- {JA2022} Jakk. "7 Common 3D Printing Problems with Solutions." Additive, 27 Oct. 2022, additive-x.com/blog/7-common-3d-printing-problems-with-solutions.
- {KW2024} Kenton, Will. "What Is the Pearson Coefficient? Definition, Benefits, and History." Investopedia, 28 Aug. 2024, www.investopedia.com/terms/p/pearsoncoefficient.asp.
- {KS2024} Kent State University Libraries. "SPSS Tutorials: Paired Samples T Test." LibGuides, libguides.library.kent.edu/spss/pairedsamplestest.
- {KE2025} Kim, Elven. "Distribution Focal Loss (DFL) in YOLO Colab - Elven Kim - Medium." Medium, 23 Jan. 2025, medium.com/@elvenkim1/dual-focal-loss-dfl-in-yolo-colab-0c9ac722f917.
- {KR2022} Kundu, Rohit. "Confusion Matrix Guide: Understanding Precision, Recall, and F1 Score." V7, 13 Sept. 2022, www.v7labs.com/blog/confusion-matrix-guide.
- {LS2024} "One-way MANOVA in SPSS Statistics - Step-by-step Procedure With Screenshots | Laerd Statistics." Laerd Statistics, statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/one-way-manova-using-spss-statistics.php.

- {PK2024} “Print Quality Troubleshooting.” Prusa Knowledge Base, help.prusa3d.com/category/print-quality-troubleshooting_225. Accessed 24 Nov. 2024.
- {SD2022} Shah, Deval. “Mean Average Precision (mAP) Explained: Everything You Need to Know.” V7, 7 Mar. 2022, www.v7labs.com/blog/mean-average-precision.
- {SJ2025} Solawetz, Jacob. “mAP in Object Detection: Mean Average Precision Explained.” Roboflow Blog, 1 June 2025, blog.roboflow.com/mean-average-precision.
- {UN2024} “Sustainable Development Goals.” UNDP, www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals.
- {FI2020} “The 3D Printing Waste Problem.” Filamentive, www.filamentive.com/the-3d-printing-waste-problem.
- {BD2024} “Training and Validation Loss in Deep Learning.” Baeldung, 27 Nov. 2024, <https://www.baeldung.com/cs/training-validation-loss-deep-learning>.
- {TJ2024} Torres, Jane. “What Is Box Loss in YOLOv8? Understanding Detection Metrics.” YOLOv8, 9 Sept. 2024, yolov8.org/what-is-box-loss-in-yolov8.
- {GE2024} “Ultimate Guide to FDM: Applications, Materials, History, Request a 3D Printed Part, & More.” GoEngineer, www.goengineer.com/3d-printing/fused-deposition-modeling. Accessed 24 Nov. 2024.
- {UL2024} Ultralytics. “YOLO Performance Metrics.” 26 June 2025, docs.ultralytics.com/guides/yolo-performance-metrics/#object-detection-metrics.
- {VL2024} Vimuth, Lakshitha. “Mastering YOLOv9: The Ultimate Guide for Enhanced Object Detection.” Medium, 3 Mar. 2024, lvimuth.medium.com/mastering-yolov9-the-ultimate-guide-for-enhanced-object-detection-1017f0af1c5.

C. Conference Proceedings

- {AA2021} Aboah, Armstrong, et al. "A Vision-based System for Traffic Anomaly Detection Using Deep Learning and Decision Trees." *Proceedings of the 2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*, IEEE, June 2021, doi:10.1109/cvprw53098.2021.00475.
- {AB2023} Aydin, Burcu Ataer, et al. "Domain Modelling For A Lightweight Convolutional Network Focused On Automated Exudate Detection in Retinal Fundus Images." *Proceedings of the 2023 9th International Conference on Information Technology Trends (ITT)*, IEEE, May 2023, doi:10.1109/itt59889.2023.10184244.
- {BD2022} Bogdoll, Daniel, et al. "Anomaly Detection in Autonomous Driving: A Survey." *2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*, June 2022, doi:10.1109/cvprw56347.2022.00495.
- {ZA2023} Zahid, Arsalan, et al. "Lightweight Convolutional Network for Automated Photovoltaic Defect Detection." *International Conference on the Current Trends in Information Technology (CTIT)*, May 2023, doi:10.1109/itt59889.2023.10184236.
- {HT1996} Huang, T. (1996). "Computer vision: Evolution and promise". 19th CERN School of Computing, CERN, Geneva, 1996, pp. 21–25 <https://doi.org/10.5170/CERN-1996-008.21>; ISBN 978-9290830955.
- Bachelor of Science in
**COMPUTER
SCIENCE**
D. Research Paper
- {BJ2023} Bharadiya, Jasmin Praful. "Convolutional Neural Networks for Image Classification." *Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research)*, May 2023, doi:10.5281/zenodo.7952031
- {WA2024} Wang, Ao, et al. YOLOv10: Real-Time End-to-End Object Detection, arxiv.org/pdf/2405.14458. Accessed 24 Oct. 2024.

E. Published Thesis

- {CE2022} Cenedese, Elisa. “3D Printing Anomaly Detection: Implementation of a ML System Using Yolov5 and EfficientNet-Lite.” *Webthesis*, 20 Dec. 2022, webthesis.biblio.polito.it/id/eprint/25499.

F. Datasets

- {BS2025} Bast, Sebastian, et al. “Quality Control in Additive Manufacturing: Image Dataset for Defect Detection in Fused Filament Fabrication.” Zenodo, Jan. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14712897>.
- {CO2025} Charia, Oumaima, et al. “YOLO-Strings: A YOLO-compatible Dataset for Detecting Stringing During 3D Printing.” Zenodo, Jan. 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14711320>.
- {HW2024} Hu, Wenjing, et al. “FDM 3D Printing Defect Dataset.” Kaggle, 2024, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/wengmhu/fdm-3d-printing-defect-dataset>.
- {RU2024} Roboflow Universe. “[Explore the Roboflow Universe]” Roboflow, 2025, universe.roboflow.com.

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : KAREN KAYE T. ALFONSO
ORCID : 0009-0007-8075-3369
Program of Study : BS in Computer Science
Date of Birth : September 11, 2003
Contact Details : 09453010692
alfonsokarenkaye@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Front-end Developer, Machine Learning

Name : JAENHEL E. MENCIDOR
ORCID : 0009-0007-7412-9893
Program of Study : BS in Computer Science
Date of Birth : April 25, 2003
Contact Details : 09498649830
jaeeeenm@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Back-end Developer, Machine Learning

Name : ERN JAN A. PAINAGA
ORCID : 0009-0008-1916-5426
Program of Study : BS in Computer Science
Date of Birth : August 4, 2003
Contact Details : 09617597012
painagaern@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Web Development, Machine Learning

